

Conoidean gastropods of the outer continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula)

Gasterópodos conoideos de la plataforma y talud continental de Galicia (Noroeste de la Península Ibérica)

Joan Daniel OLIVER*, Juan HORRO**, Victoriano URGORRI***, Emilio ROLÁN**** and José TEMPLADO*****,¹

Recibido el 31-III-2022. Aceptado el 31-V-2022

ABSTRACT

More than 800 shells and specimens of 38 species belonging to several conoidean families have been found in the samples collected during several campaigns on the continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Spain). The most frequent species in the samples were *Spirotropis confusa*, *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma*, *Micropleurotoma travailleuri* and *Oenopota graphica*. Some of the species have only been found in samples from the continental shelf above 260 m depth (*Comarmondia gracilis*, *Bela menkhorsti*, *Bela nuperrima*, *Mangelia costata*, *M. costulata*, *M. tenuicosta*, *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma* and *Cyrellia aequalis*). Eight species have been found below 1500 m depth (*Aforia* sp., *Spirotropis confusa*, *Oenopota* cf. *tenuicostata*, *Gymnobela subaraneosa*, *Neopleurotomoides callem-bryon*, *Pleurotomella* cf. *benedicti*, and two species described as new, belonging to the genera *Spirotropis* and *Neopleurotomoides*). Furthermore, fossil shells, fragments or shells in poor condition of another eight species have been also found in the samples.

RESUMEN

Algo más de 800 conchas y ejemplares de 38 especies pertenecientes a diferentes familias de la superfamilia Conoidea se han encontrado en muestreos llevados a cabo en la plataforma y talud continental de Galicia. Las especies más frecuentes en las muestras fueron *Spirotropis confusa*, *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma*, *Micropleurotoma travailleuri* y *Oenopota graphica*. Algunas de estas especies se encontraron solo en la plataforma continental por encima de los 250 m de profundidad (*Comarmondia gracilis*, *Bela menkhorsti*, *Bela nuperrima*, *Mangelia costata*, *M. costulata*, *M. tenuicosta*, *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma* y *Cyrellia aequalis*). Ocho de las especies se encontraron por debajo de los 1500 m (*Aforia* sp., *Spirotropis confusa*, *Oenopota* cf. *tenuicostata*, *Gymnobela subaraneosa*, *Neopleurotomoides callem-bryon*, *Pleurotomella* cf. *benedicti* y dos especies descritas como nuevas en los géneros *Spirotropis* y *Neopleurotomoides*). Además se encontraron en las muestras conchas fosilizadas, fragmentos o conchas en mal estado de otras 8 especies.

* Alcorisa 83, 28043 Madrid, Spain

** Montero Ríos 30, 3º, 36201 Vigo, Spain

*** Estación de Biología Mariña da Graña, REBUSC, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Spain

**** Museo de Historia Natural, Campus Universitario Norte, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain

***** Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (CSIC), José Gutiérrez Abascal 2, 28006 Madrid, Spain

¹ Corresponding autor: templado@mncn.csic.es

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:620B714A-D3D9-4950-8CD1-9803783DA37B

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Northeast Atlantic, Cochlespiridae, Borsoniidae, Clathurellidae, Drilliidae, Horaiclavidae, Mangeliidae, Raphitomidae.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Atlántico nordoriental, Cochlespiridae, Borsoniidae, Clathurellidae, Drilliidae, Horaiclavidae, Mangeliidae, Raphitomidae.

INTRODUCTION

We present a new contribution to the knowledge of the gastropods along the continental shelf and slope off the coast of Galicia (NW Spain), based on samples obtained in several cruises carried out between 2002 and 2009 by the Marine Biology Station of A Graña (belonging to Santiago de Compostela University). Results regarding several benthic taxa have been already published (e.g. MOREIRA & PARAPAR, 2007; 2008; PARAPAR & MOREIRA, 2009; MOREIRA, LUCAS & PARAPAR, 2011; LUCAS, SAN MARTÍN & PARAPAR, 2012; ZAMARRO, GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ & URGORRI, 2013, 2015, 2016, 2019; SEÑARÍS, GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ & URGORRI, 2017; TATO & MOREIRA 2017; TATO, MOREIRA & URGORRI, 2019; GUERRA-GARCÍA, TATO & MOREIRA, 2018; URGORRI *ET AL.*, 2021, among others). Among the gastropod molluscs collected in this series of deep-sea expeditions, BARRIO (2015) studied the slit-shells (subfamily Emarginulinae, family Fissurellidae) in her unpublished PhD thesis. Here we present the results regarding the species belonging to the conoidean families.

Conoidea is a group of hyperdiverse venomous gastropods, within which Conoidea (cone snails) and Terebridae (auger snails) are well-defined families, but all the other constituents were traditionally lumped in the single artificial family Turridae, more or less separated into different families or subfamilies by different authors (e.g. POWELL, 1966; KILBURN, 1983). TAYLOR *ET AL.* (1993), who extensively used anatomical characters, established a new rearrangement of this traditional family and subdivided it into several new families and subfamilies. Subsequently, some authors have

continued to use subfamilies within the family Turridae (e.g. FEDOSOV & KANTOR, 2008; ROSENBERG, 2009; FIGUEIRA & ABSALÃO, 2010a,b, 2012).

It is remarkable that over the last years the family-level classification of the Conoidea has undergone notable breakthrough, based mainly on the study of extensive new material from the tropical western Pacific. This has led to a comprehensive molecular phylogeny of the entire superfamily (PUILLANDRE *ET AL.* 2008, 2011) followed by subsequent descriptions of new families and the proposal of a new deeply modified classification (BOUCHET *ET AL.* 2011; KANTOR, STRONG & PUILLANDRE, 2012). More recently, new phylogenetic analyses (URIBE, ZARDOYA & PUILLANDRE, 2018; ABDELKRIM *ET AL.*, 2018) raise the number of Conoidea families to 17, 15 of which correspond to the traditional 'Turridae'.

Whatever, the so-called 'turrid' gastropods are the most diverse group of marine molluscs that includes small to medium sized specialist predators on annelids and other molluscs, and occupies all marine habitats from the tropics to the poles, from shallow to deep water, and from hard to soft substrates (BOUCHET, LOZOUET & SYSOEV, 2009). They represent one of the most abundant groups of molluscs in bathyal and abyssal environments and occupy a high level in the food chains (PUILLANDRE, FEDOSOV & KANTOR, 2016).

The North-East Atlantic deep-water conoidean species were revised by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980), who included 102 species (in 25 genera) occurring below 300 m, thirteen of which they described as new. Since then, only scat-

tered data has been published on the NE Atlantic bathyal ‘turrid’ gastropods, included in general faunistic studies or in taxonomic reviews of some groups (i.e. BOUCHET & TAVIANI, 1989; JANSSEN, 1993; LUNDBERG, SCHANDER & STOKLAND, 1996; MARIOTTINI *ET AL.*, 2008, 2015; GOFAS, 2011; GOFAS, LUQUE & KANTOR, 2014a; HØISÆTER, 2016; ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019; UTRILLA *ET AL.*, 2020). Previously FECHTER (1979a, b) studied the abyssal turrid gastropods from the Canaries basin and Iberian margin. Recently GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021) published an illustrated and commented checklist of the molluscs from Galicia Bank, which include 15 conoidean species. This large seamount is located about 120 nautical miles off W Galician coast and separated from the bathyal depths here studied by the Galicia Inner Basin.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material studied was obtained in different expeditions along continental shelf and slope off the coast of Galicia (NW Spain) from the “A Selva” and “A Quiniela” fishery banks and off Ártabro Gulf in the Northwest (43°30’N-44°15’N; 008°10’W-009°10’W) to off the Rías Baixas in the South (42°11’N-42°20’N; 009°26’W-011°10’W). Sampling methodology and processing of samples were described in PARAPAR & MOREIRA (2009) and in the previous work (OLIVER *ET AL.*, 2022) with the data related to the cruises carried out. A list of the stations cited in this paper, with coordinates, depth and habitat and the acronyms of all projects, is given in the Appendix 1. A map of sampling stations covered along Galician Continental Margin (NW Iberian Peninsula) is shown in Figure 1.

Benthic samples were taken in the depth range 100-3200 m by means of the following gears: Naturalist Dredge (DRN), Agassiz trawl (AT), Rock dredge (DRR) and Epibenthic sledge (EBS). Figure 2 shows several habitats representative of the diversity of bottoms sampled. Samples obtained were sieved and specimens were fixed with 70%

ethanol neutralized with borax. Animals retained in sieves of ≥ 2 mm were sorted to high taxonomic levels on the Marine Biological Station of A Graña (University of Santiago de Compostela).

The entire collection of more than 800 shells and specimens from the samples studied have been deposited (preserved dry and in 70% ethanol respectively) at the Museo de Historia Natural of the Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Galicia (Spain), with the deposit number: MHN-USC-10125.

Other material from different geographical areas housed in the malacological collection of the National Museum of Natural History of Madrid and those of the authors themselves was used as comparison.

The following abbreviations have been used:

frg: fragment

juv: juvenile

sh: empty shell

spc: specimen with soft parts

SEM/MEB: Scanning Electron Microscope

sta.: sampling station

Expeditions:

D-AI(02): DIVA-Artabria I (2002)

D-AI(03): DIVA-Artabria I (2003)

VE(04): Vertidos (2004)

APLA(06): APLACOPHORA (2006)

SAR(06-07): Sarridal (2007)

D-AII(08): DIVA-Artabria II (2008)

SE(08): A Selva (2008)

FO(09): Forsagal (2009)

Institutions:

EXEM: Royal Albert Memorial Museum & Art Gallery, Exeter

MCSNM: Museo Civico di Storia Naturale, Milano

MCZ: Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard

MCZR: Museo Cívico de Zoología, Roma

MNCN: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid

MHNS: Museo de Historia Natural, University of Santiago de Compostela.

Figure 1. Sampling stations along Galician Continental Margin (NW Iberian Peninsula) covered in the present study (figure made with GeoMapApp (www.geomapapp.org) / CC BY).
 Figura 1. Estaciones de muestreo a lo largo del margen continental de Galicia (NO Península Ibérica) objeto del presente estudio (figura realizada con GeoMapApp (www.geomapapp.org) / CC BY).

(Right page) Figure 2. Habitats representative of the diversity of bottoms sampled. A: phosphorites from DA-I(03): DRN-600; B: phosphorites and carbonate crusts from SE(08): DRN-30-1; C: stones and white clay from DA-II(08): DRNp-21; D: large stones, phosphorites, sand and coral from SE(08): AT-12; E: dead corals and small phosphorites from VE(04): GA-DRN-1000; F: gravel of *Megabalanus* plates from DA-II(08): DRNp-15; G: dead coral gravel from DA-I(03): DRN-1000; H: sand with live and dead corals from SE(08): DRN-7; I: calcareous plates and muddy sand from DA-II(08): DRNp-22; J: sand and small phosphorites from SE(08): DRN-11; K: slightly muddy sand from SE(08): DRN-11-4; L: mud from SE(08): DRN-22.

Figura 2. Hábitats representativos de la diversidad de los fondos muestreados. A: fosforitas de DA-I(03): DRN-600; B: fosforitas y costras carbonatadas de SE(08): DRN-30-1; C: piedras y arcillas blancas de DA-II(08): DRNp-21; D: piedras grandes, fosforitas, arena y coral de SE(08): AT-12; E: corales muertos y pequeñas fosforitas de VE(04): GA-DRN-1000; F: grava de placas de *Megabalanus* de DA-II(08): DRNp-15; G: grava de coral muerto de DA-I(03): DRN-1000; H: arena con corales vivos y muertos del SE(08): DRN-7; I: placas calcáreas y arenas fangosas de DA-II(08): DRNp-22; J: arena y pequeñas fosforitas de SE(08): DRN-11; K: arena ligeramente fangosa de SE(08): DRN-11-4; L: fango de SE(08): DRN-22.

MNHN: Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris.
 MNHNSC: Museo Nacional de Historia Natural de Santiago de Chile.
 MOM: Musée Océanographique de Monaco.
 NHMUK: Natural History Museum of the U.K., London
 SMNH: Swedish Museum of Natural History, Stockholm
 UIO: Natural History Museum at the University of Oslo
 USNM: United States National Museum, Washington D.C.
 ZMB: Zoological Museum of Bergen
 ZMO: Zoological Museum, Oslo
 ZMPU: Zoological Museum of the Palermo University.
 ZMUH: Zoological Museum of the Humboldt University, Berlin.

RESULTS

The species-rich Conoidea superfamily was represented in the studied samples (in the bathymetric range of 110-2520 m) by more than 800 shells and specimens of 38 species belonging to 7 families and 21 genera: Cochlespiridae (genus *Aforia*), Borsoniidae (genera *Drilliola*, *Typhlomangelia*), Clathurellidae (genus *Comarmondia*), Drilliidae (genus *Spirotropis*), Horaiclavidae (genus *Micropleurotoma*), Mangeliidae (genera *Mangelia*, *Bela*, *Kurtziella*, *Oenopota*, *Propebela* and *Sorgenfreispira*), and Raphitomidae (*Raphitoma*, *Cyrillia*, *Leufroyia*, *Pleurotomella*, *Gymnobela*, *Austrobela*, *Teretia*, *Neopleurotomoides* and *Phymorhynchus*).

Thirty eight species were identified, two of them only to generic level, seven with doubtful specific identification and some of them represented by subfossil or

quite eroded shells (Tables I and II). The most frequent species were *Spirotropis confusa*, *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma*, *Micropleurotoma travailleuri* and *Oenopota graphica*. Some of the species have only been found in samples from the continental shelf above 260 m depth: *Comarmondia gracilis*, *Bela menkhorsti*, *Bela nuperrima*, *Mangelia costata*, *M. costulata*, *M. tenuicosta*, *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma* and *Cyrillia aequalis*. Eight species have been found below 1500 m depth: *Aforia* sp., *Spirotropis confusa*, *Spirotropis galiciensis* Oliver & Horro, n. sp., *Oenopota* cf. *tenuicostata*, *Gymnobela subaraneosa*, *Neopleurotomoides callembryon*, *Neopleurotomoides senharisi* Oliver, Horro & Urgorri, n. sp., *Phymorhynchus* sp. and *Pleurotomella* cf. *benedicti*. The remaining species were found at intermediate depth (*Drilliola emendata*, *Drilliola loprestiana*, *Typhlomangelia nivalis*, *Micropleurotoma spirotopoides*, *Micropleurotoma travailleuri*, *Kurtziella serga*, *Oenopota graphica*, *Propebela* cf. *bergensis*, *Austrobela pyrrhogramma*, *Pleurotomella gibbera*, *P. demosia*, *Raphitoma* aff. *echinata*, *Leufroyia erronea*, *Taranis* cf. *moerchi* and *Teretia teres*).

Nineteen of the species (50%) were represented by specimens with soft parts, the remaining by empty shells only (Table I). Furthermore, fossil shells or shells in poor condition of eight species have been also found in the samples (*Aforia clytotropis*, *Propebela* cf. *assimilis*, *Phymorhynchus* sp., *Pleurotomella eurybrocha*, *Pleurotomella* cf. *benedicti*, *Cyrillia linearis*, *Leufroyia erronea* and *Leufroyia* cf. *inflata*).

Thirteen of the species found have paucispiral protoconch (those of the genera *Aforia*, *Spirotropis*, *Micropleurotoma*, *Oenopota*, *Propebela*, plus *Drilliola emendata* and *Typhlomangelia nivalis*) (see Table I).

SYSTEMATIC PART

GASTROPODA
 CAENOGASTROPODA
 Order NEOGASTROPODA
 Superfamily CONOIDEA
 Family BORSONIIDAE

Genus *Drilliola* Locard, 1897

Type species: *Taranis emendata* Monterosato, 1872

Drilliola emendata (Monterosato, 1872) (Figs. 3, 42A)

Drilliola emendata (Monterosato, 1872) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 32-34, figs. 29, 83, 207); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 68); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 316); GOFAS (2011: 330); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2014: 98); NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016: 65-66, figs. 17, 34).

Type material: lectotype in MNHN selected by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980) (photo in the MNHN website). Photo of a paralectotype in APPOLLONI *ET AL.* (2018, fig. 21M, p. 111). Type locality: Palermo (Sicily).

Material examined (1 shell): SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°33.53'N, 009°13.28'W to 43°33.90'N, 009°12.93'W; 725-737 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-03.

Description: The only shell found in the samples studied measured 9.9 mm (Figs. 3A-C, 42A). Sculpture of thin spiral keels with superimposed collabral riblets (Fig. 3D). Its wide paucispiral protoconch (830 µm in diameter) has two spiral keels (Fig. 3E-F) and a microsculpture consisting of tiny granules (Fig. 3G).

Remarks: This species is known across the Mediterranean, in the Atlantic coast of the Iberian Peninsula and in north-western African coasts in the bathymetric range 70-1800 m (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980; NEGRI & CORSELLI, 2016). ARDOVINI

& COSSIGNANI (1999) recorded it in the Adriatic Sea at 270 m, GOFAS *ET AL.* (2014b) recorded it alive in the Avempace Seamount (Djibouti Bank, Alboran Sea) at 349-365 m depth in a bottom dominated by the crinoid *Leptometra*, NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016) in the Apulian margin (S Italian coast) at 525-560 m in a bottom with cold-water corals, and UTRILLA *ET AL.* (2020) in a mud volcano of the Gulf of Cádiz within the 400-500 m depth range. A single subadult fresh shell has been found (in a sample at about 725 m depth) that reveals its presence in the study area.

Drilliola loprestiana (Calcara, 1841) (Figs. 4, 42B)

Microdrilla loprestiana (Calcara, 1841) - ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: p. 70); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: p. 316).

Drilliola loprestiana (Calcara, 1841) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 32, figs. 82, 208-209); NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016: 65-66, figs. 15 a-d); GOFAS (2011: 330); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2010: 100), GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021: 67, fig. 26 F-G).

Type material: not found. FIGUEIRA & ABSALÃO (2010: 740, fig. 3H-K) illustrated a shell of *D. emendata* housed in MZPU as supposed holotype of *D. loprestiana*. Type locality: near Messina, Sicily (Plio-Pleistocene fossil).

Material examined (8 specimens with soft parts and 44 empty shells in 23 samples): SPAIN • 1 spc; 43°48.421'N, 008°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 008°51.091'W; 599-607 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-600. • 1 sh; 43°53.575'N, 008°56.868'W to 43°54.015'N, 008°56.959'W; 965-974 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-1000 • 1 spc; 43°41.590'N, 008°45.328'W to 43°42.396'N, 008°44.286'W; 301-301 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-300 • 1 sh (juv) + 4 spc; 43°48.587'N, 008°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 008°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 1 spc; EBS-800 • 2 sh (1 juv); 43°38.812'N, 009°07.949'W to 43°39.841'N, 009°07.405'W; 999-1001 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-DRN-1000 • 2 sh; 43°35.611'N, 008°58.536'W to 43°36.104'N, 008°57.284'W; 384-345 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-EBS-400 • 1 sh (juv); polygon delimited by points 44° 10.000' N, 009° 00.000' W / 44° 10.000' N, 008° 35.000' W / 44° 00.000' N; 009° 00.000' W / 44° 07.000' N; 008° 35.000' W; 417-668 m; SARRIDAL (2006-2007) SARRI-4 • 7 sh; 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 5 sh (4

Table I. Species found in the samples studied indicating those with paucispiral protoconch, those collected with soft parts, and their finding in the different expeditions. The last right column (BG) indicates the species recorded in the neighbouring Galicia Bank by GOFAS ET AL. (2021).

Tabla I. Especies encontradas en las muestras estudiadas indicando aquellas con protoconcha pauciespiral, las recolectadas con partes blandas, y su hallazgo en las diferentes expediciones. La última columna de la derecha (BG) indica las especies registradas en el vecino Banco de Galicia por GOFAS ET AL. (2021).

Species	Paucispiral protoconch	Species found alive	DAI(02)	DAI(03)	VE(04)	APIA(06)	SAR(06-07)	SE(08)	DAII(08)	FOR(09)	TOTAL	BG
<i>Drilliola emendata</i>	●								■		1	
<i>Drilliola loprestiana</i>		◆		■	■		■	■	■		5	■
<i>Typhlomangelia nivalis</i>	●	◆	■	■	■		■	■	■	■	7	
<i>Comarmondia gracilis</i>		◆	■		■			■			3	
<i>Aforia clytrotropis</i>	●							■			1	
<i>Aforia</i> sp.	●							■	■		2	
<i>Spirotropis confusa</i>	●	◆	■	■	■		■	■	■	■	7	
<i>Spirotropis galiciensis</i> n. sp.	●	◆	■						■		2	
<i>Micropleurotoma spirotopoides</i>	●		■					■	■		3	
<i>Micropleurotoma travailleurii</i>	●	◆	■	■	■		■	■	■		6	
<i>Bela menkharsti</i>			■		■			■			3	
<i>Bela nuperrima</i>		◆	■		■						2	
<i>Kurtziella serga</i>		◆	■					■			2	■
<i>Mangelia costata</i>				■	■			■			3	
<i>Mangelia costulata</i>		◆		■	■						2	
<i>Mangelia tenuicosta</i>		◆	■	■	■	■		■			5	
<i>Oenopota grafica</i>	●	◆		■			■	■			3	
<i>Oenopota</i> cf. <i>tenuicostata</i>	●								■		1	
<i>Propebela</i> cf. <i>bergensis</i>	●	◆		■			■	■	■		3	
<i>Propebela</i> cf. <i>assimilis</i>	●								■		1	
<i>Sorgenfreispira brachystoma</i>		◆	■	■	■	■		■			5	
<i>Gymnobela abyssorum</i>		◆						■	■		2	■
<i>Gymnobela subaraneosa</i>		◆						■	■		2	■
<i>Austrobela pyrrhogramma</i>		◆						■	■		2	■
<i>Neopleurotomoides callembrion</i>								■			1	■
<i>Neopleurotomoides senharisi</i> n. sp.		◆						■			1	
<i>Phymorhynchus</i> sp.								■	■		2	
<i>Pleurotomella</i> cf. <i>benedicti</i>								■			1	
<i>Pleurotomella gibbera</i>		◆						■	■		2	■
<i>Pleurotomella demosia</i>							■	■			2	■
<i>Pleurotomella eurybrocha</i>								■			1	■
<i>Cyrellia aequalis</i>				■	■			■			3	
<i>Cyrellia linearis</i>					■							
<i>Raphitoma</i> aff. <i>echinata</i>								■			1	
<i>Leufroyia erronea</i>								■			1	
<i>Leufroyia</i> cf. <i>inflata</i>								■			1	
<i>Taranis</i> cf. <i>moerchii</i>	●							■			1	
<i>Teretia teres</i>		◆	■	■	■		■	■			6	
TOTAL sp.:38	13	19	13	12	13	2	8	31	16	2		10

Figure 3. *Drilliola emendata* (DAII(08) DRNp-03). A-C: shell (9.9 mm); D: detail of its microsculpture; E-G: protoconch and details of its microsculpture (B, C: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 3. *Drilliola emendata* (DAII(08) DRNp-03). A-C: concha (9,9 mm); D: detalle de su microsculptura; E-G: protoconcha y detalles de su microsculptura (B, C: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

juv); 44°08.65'N, 008°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 008°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 2 sh; 44°08.461'N, 009°04.634'W to 44°08.607'N, 009°04.413'W; 917-896 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7-1 • 1 sh; 44°06.84'N, 009°03.692'W to 44°07.075'N, 009°03.655'W; 911-886 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7-2 • 1 sh (juv); 44°06.113'N, 008°45.102'W to 44°06.282'N, 008°44.606 W; 434-433 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-10-2B • 1 spc + 3 sh; 44°09.896'N, 008°39.581'W to 44°10.129'N, 008°39.494'W; 438-459 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-11 • 1 sh; 43°58.356'N, 008°52.149'W to 43°57.685'N, 008°52.903'W; 1054-1064 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-1 • 5 sh; 43°56.478'N, 008°54.199'W to 43°55.934'N, 008°54.849'W; 620-933 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2 • 3 sh; 43°55.886'N, 008°54.846'W to 43°55.291'N, 008°55.65'W; 933-930 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2B • 1 sh; 43°42.289'N, 008°49.804'W to 43°43.019'N, 008°49.24'W; 629-542 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-17 • 1 sh; 43°48.511'N, 008°51.393'W to 43°49.092'N, 008°50.959'W; 312-576 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-30-1 • 1 sh (juv); 44°00.806'N, 008°33.098'W to 44°01.967'N, 008°32.57'W; 346-344 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-14 • 1 sh (juv); 44°05.923'N, 008°45.586'W to 44°06.046'N, 008°43.886'W; 432-453 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-10-2B • 5 sh; 43°33.24'N,

009°30.39'W to 43°33.7'N, 009°29.75'W; 1207-1206 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRN-10 • 1 sh (juv); 43°19.92'N, 009°38.13'W to 43°21.25'N, 009°37.11'W; 1267-1286 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-15.

Description: Up to 10.7 mm with 7 whorls in the shells studied. The shell has a characteristic sculpture of sharp spiral keels, the most prominent bordering the subsutural shelf, and thin and sinuous collabral riblets in the interspaces (Fig. 4A-C). Its multispiral protoconch (Fig. 4D-E) has just over 4 whorls and has a brown colour that contrasts with the white of the teleoconch. Protoconch I ornamented with roughly aligned granules. Protoconch II with curved opisthocline ribs which emerge from the upper suture, curve and taper in their basal area and disappear slightly above the lower suture. The roughly aligned granules remain between the ribs (Fig. 4F).

Remarks: Unlike the previous species, *D. loprestiana* has a multispiral protoconch of somewhat more than four whorls and thus presumable high dispersal ability. In fact, it has a wide geographic distribution on both sides of the

Atlantic, from Georgia to Brazil and from the Bay of Biscay to West Africa (including Macaronesian islands and the Gorringe and Josephine seamounts) and the Mediterranean, mainly in soft bottoms of the continental slope, being apparently shallower at some Mediterranean locations (BOUCHET & WARÉN 1980; GRIBET & PEÑAS, 1997; ABSALÃO, PIMENTA & CAETANO, 2005; BECK, METZGER & FREIWALD, 2006; PEÑAS ET AL. 2006; GOFAS, 2011; GOFAS ET AL., 2014b; NEGRI & CORSELLI, 2016). FIGUEIRA & ABSALÃO (2010) used the name *Drilliola pulchella* (Verrill, 1880) for this species in the Eastern Atlantic. UTRILLA ET AL. (2020) reported it in a mud volcano of the Gulf of Cádiz in the 400-500 m depth range. This species is also present in the Galicia Bank, found between 880 and 1125 m (GOFAS ET AL., 2021). About fifty shells and specimens were found in the studied samples from the depth range 428-1300 m.

Genus *Typhlomangelia* G.O.Sars, 1878

Type species: *Pleurotoma nivalis* Lovén, 1846

Typhlomangelia nivalis (Lovén, 1846) (Figs. 5, 6, 42C)

Typhlomangelia nivalis (Lovén, 1846) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 27-29, figs. 74-76, 200); FRETTER & GRAHAM (1985: 518-519); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 71); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 315).

Type material: syntypes in SMNH. Type locality: Bergen (Norway).

Material examined (3 specimens with soft parts and 20 empty shells in 15 samples): SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°51.265'N, 008°54.480'W to 43°51.498'N, 008°53.123'W; 827-819 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-800 • 2 sh; 43°57.030'N, 008°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 008°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 1 sh; 43°53.575'N, 008°56.868'W to 43°54.015'N, 008°56.959'W; 965-974 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-1000 • 1 spc; 43°36.544'N, 009°03.064'W to 43°36.816'N, 009°04.339'W; 601-619 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-EBS-600 • 2 sh; polygon delimited by points 44° 10.000' N, 009° 00.000' W / 44° 10.000' N, 008° 35.000' W / 44° 00.000' N; 009° 00.000' W / 44° 07.000' N; 008° 35.000' W; 720 m; SARRIDAL (2006-2007) SARRI-1 • 3 sh; 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 sh (juv); 44°08.461'N, 009°04.634'W to 44°08.607'N, 009°04.413'W; 917-896 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7-1 • 1 sh; 44°06.113'N, 008°45.102'W to 44°06.282'N, 008°44.606'W; 434-433 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-10-2B • 1 sh + 2 frg; 44°07.628'N, 008°45.871'W to 44°07.989'N, 008°45.542'W; 412-411 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-11-4 • 1 sh; 43°58.356'N, 008°52.149'W to 43°57.685'N, 008°52.903'W; 1054-1064 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-1 • 4 sh (2 juv); 43°56.478'N,

Figure 4. *Drilliola loprestiana* (SE(08) DRN-7). A, B: shells (6.3 and 5.4 mm, respectively); C: detail of the microsculpture; D: protoconch and details of its microsculpture (SEM images).

Figura 4. *Drilliola loprestiana* (SE(08) DRN-7). A, B: conchas (6,3 mm y 5,4 mm, respectivamente); C: detalle de la microescultura; D: protoconcha y detalles de su microescultura (imágenes de MEB).

008°54.199'W to 43°55.934'N, 008°54.849'W; 620-933 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2 • 1 sh; 43°55.886'N, 008°54.846'W to 43°55.291'N, 008°55.65'W; 933-930 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2B • 1 spc; 43°34.19'N, 009°22.12'W to 43°35.77'N, 009°21.23'W; 1005-1070 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-04 • 2 sh; 43°16.50'N, 009°34.52'W to 43°16.71'N, 009°33.79'W; 565-503 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNr-18 • 1 spc; 42°23'N, 009°24' 33.40" W to 42°23'N, 009°23' 32.05" W; 455-378 m; 14-25 Feb. 2009; FORSAGAL DRN-18.

Description: Slender fusiform shell with convex and somewhat angular profile of the whorls and moderately sunken suture (Figs. 5A, G, 6A, G, 42C). With about seven whorls, it reaches up to 13.6 mm in the specimens studied. Sub-sutural zone slightly concave that reaches almost half of the whorl and does not form a clear ledge (Fig. 5D, J). Spiral cords somewhat narrower than their interspaces over the entire shell, including the subsutural zone (Fig. 5F, J). The

teleoconch begins with two spiral cords to which others are progressively added. Axial ribs weak, weaker or absent at the subsutural ramp, fading below the periphery of the last whorl. Microsculpture of fine growth lines over the entire surface of the shell and tiny granules, similar to those of the protoconch (Figs. 5K, 6I). Paucispiral protoconch (Figs. 5E, I, 6B, C, H) of about 1.25 whorls with microgranules over its entire surface (Fig. 6E-F), roughly aligned towards the end.

Figure 5. *Typhlomangelia nivalis*. A-F: shell (13.6 mm) (SE(08) DRN-15-2), its protoconch and details of its microsculpture; G-I: young shell (4.6 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-04), detail of the aperture and protoconch; J, K: sculpture and microsculpture of its teleoconch (A: stereo microscope image; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 5. *Typhlomangelia nivalis*. A-F: concha (13,6 mm) (SE(08) DRN-15-2), su protoconcha y detalles de su microescultura; G-I: concha joven (4,6 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-04), detalle de la apertura y protoconcha; J, K: escultura y microescultura de su teleoconcha (A: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

Figure 6. *Typhlomangelia nivalis*. A-F: young shell (7.7 mm) (VE(04) GA-EBS600), protoconch and details of its microsculpture; G-I: young shell (4.6 mm) (SE(08) DRN7-1); protoconch and details of the teleoconch microsculpture (SEM images).

Figura 6. *Typhlomangelia nivalis*. A-F: concha joven (7,7 mm) (VE(04)GA-EBS600), protoconcha y detalles de su microscultura; G-I: concha joven (4,6 mm) (SE(08)DRN7-1); protoconcha y detalles de la microscultura de la teleoconcha (imágenes de MEB).

Marked and flexuous transition between proto- and teleoconch, which begins with dense arcuate growth lines (Fig. 6D).

Remarks: *Typhlomangelia nivalis* extends from Norway to Cape Verde Islands (also in the Azores and Madeira), and in the Mediterranean Sea, in the depth range of 100–3000 m (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980). ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999) recorded it in the Tyrrhenian Sea at 450 m depth. Twenty shells (3 of them with remains of soft parts) have been found in the studied samples in the depth range 411–1070 m.

BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980) pointed out that this species shows great variability; in fact LOCARD (1897) described up to 4 species nowadays considered synonyms of *T. nivalis*. Based on this

variability, ABSALÃO *ET AL.* (2005) and FIGUEIRA & ABSALÃO (2010a) identified as *T. nivalis* some shells collected off Brazilian coasts between 500 and 1320 m. Indeed, in the specimens here studied we observed notable differences in size and shape, including the height/width ratio, the size of the last whorls in proportion to the total height, and especially in sculpture, both in number and development of the axial ribs, as well as in the number and size of the spiral cords (Figs. 5A, G, 46, G). However, the protoconchs showed a general coincidence. Given its paucispiral protoconch, it can be assumed that the dispersal capacity of this species is very limited, which could lead to local speciation processes within this lineage.

Family CLATHURELLIDAE

Genus *Comarmondia* Monterosato, 1884

Type species: *Murex gracilis* Montagu, 1803

Comarmondia gracilis (Montagu, 1803) (Figs. 7, 42D)

Comarmondia gracilis (Montagu, 1803) - FRETTER & GRAHAM (1985: 532–534); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 68); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 315); GOFAS (2011: 341); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2012: 100).

Type material: lectotype in EXEM, 5 paralectotypes in NHMUK (OLIVER, MORGENROTH & SALVADOR (2017, fig.32, p. 384: lectotype). Type locality: Biddeford Bay, Devon (British Islands).

Material examined (3 specimens with soft parts and 8 empty shells in 6 samples): SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°40.036'N, 008°43.789'W to 43°39.706'N, 008°44.610'W; 201–198 m; 08–15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-200 • 2 sh (1 juv); 43°35.451'N, 008°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 008°35.407'W; 153–151 m; 08–15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-150 • 3 sh; 43°29.412'N, 008°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 008°28.240'W; 110–111 m; 17–28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-110 • 2 spc + 1 sh; • 1 spc; 43°31.970'N, 008°37.670'W to 43°32.697'N, 008°3.171'W; 151 m; 17–28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-EBS-150 • 1 sh; 43°58.719'N, 008°15.691'W to 43°58.942'N, 008°15.362'W; 231–233 m; 15–24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-20.

Description: Adult shells (up to 18.3 mm in the shells studied) are shown in figures 7A–C and 42D, a juvenile in figure 7D. Microsculpture of minute granules all over the teleoconch (Fig. 7J). Multispiral protoconch of about 3 whorls (Fig. 7E) with a characteristic pattern of somewhat star-like cross-linked sculpture (Fig. 7F–I). Protoconch II with two fine spiral keels, one in the middle of the whorls and other over the

suture (Fig. 7G). Transition to teleoconch well-marked.

Remarks: Common and well known species, it extends from the British Islands to the south of the Iberian Peninsula and the Mediterranean in infralittoral and circalittoral coarse bottoms of the continental shelf (FRETTER & GRAHAM, 1985; PEÑAS *ET AL.*, 2006; GOFAS, 2011; SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.*, 2012). We have found it in samples collected between 110 and 233 m depth.

Figure 7. *Comarmondia gracilis*. A-C: shell (18.3 mm) (VE(04)GA-AT110); D: juvenile shell (2.1 mm) (DAI(03) EBS-150); E-I: protoconch and details of its microsculpture; J: detail of teleoconch microsculpture (A-C: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 7. Comarmondia gracilis. A-C: *concha* (18,3 mm) (VE(04) GA-AT110); D: *concha* juvenil (2,1 mm) (DAI(03) EBS-150); E-I: *protoconcha* y detalles de su microescultura; J: *detalle* de microescultura de la *teleoconcha* (A-C: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

Family COCHLESPIRIDAE

Genus *Aforia* Dall, 1889

Type species: *Pleurotoma circinata* Dall, 1873

Aforia clytotropis (Sykes, 1906) n. comb. (Fig. 8A-B)

Ancistrosyrinx clytotropis (Sykes, 1906) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 23, fig. 67).

Type material: holotype in NHMUK. Type locality: off W Portugal ("Porcupine" sta. 17: 39°42'N - 009°43'W, 1980 m).

Material examined (one fossil shell): SPAIN • 1 sh (fossil); 44°00'N, 008°32'W to 44°01'N, 008°32'W; 344-343 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-14.

Description: Shell large, fusiform and pagodiform, with a high spire, and a moderately long and open siphonal canal (Fig. 8A-B). The studied shell measured 31 x 13 mm. Clearly angulated whorls due to a protruding double spiral keel, located in the lower third of the whorls and delimiting a wide and convex subsutural ramp. About thirty weak spiral threads run under the keel to the base of the shell, two of which more prominent, one above the anal sinus and the other below, that disappear with growth of the shell. Weak spiral cords are also observed above the keel, one of them more prominent close to the suture. In the subsutural zone,

flexuous growth lines are present following the shape of the anal sinus. Protoconch paucispiral, globose with about 2 whorls.

Remarks: BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980) found a shell of 25 mm from the northern coast of Spain (at 700-1120 m) figured under the name *Ancistrosyrinx clytotropis*. GOFAS ET AL. (2014a) suggested that this species may belong to the genus *Aforia*, a view shared here.

The only shell studied comes from a sample taken at 320 m. BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980) and GOFAS ET AL. (2014a) pointed out that all the few known shells of this species, including the type, are possibly fossils.

Aforia sp. (Fig. 8C-E)

Material examined (6 empty shells in 4 samples): SPAIN • 2 sh; 43°34.19'N, 009°22.12'W to 43°35.77'N, 009°21.23'W; 1005-1070 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-04 • 2 sh; DRNp-22. • 1 sh; 43°58.356'N, 008°52.149'W to 43°57.685'N, 008°52.903'W; 1054-1064 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-1 • 1 sh; 43°56.478'N, 008°54.199'W to 43°55.934'N, 008°54.849'W; 620-933 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2.

Description: Some subfossil shells found in the studied samples are attributed to the genus *Aforia* by their morphological characteristics (large, fusiform and pagodiform shells with high spire and long siphonal canal). However, their characteristics do not fully fit with any of described species of the genus. They measured up to 20 x 9 mm. A conspicuous protruding keel in the periphery towards the middle of the whorls divides them into two slightly

concave parts (Fig. 8C-E). Two thin spiral cords run somewhat below the suture. Under the keel, about thirty weak spiral threads run to the base of the shell, the two more prominent just above the anal sinus. Axial ornamentation of irregularly spaced growth lines all over the shell. Globose paucispiral protoconch, smooth and pale greyish in colour.

Remarks: The genus *Aforia* groups about 20 species of somewhat conserva-

Figure 8. A, B: *Aforia clytrotropis* (31.0 mm) (SE(08) AT14); C-E: *Aforia* sp. (19.7 mm) (DAII(08) DRN-22) (Stereo microscope images).

Figura 8. A, B: *Aforia clytrotropis* (31,0 mm) (SE(08) AT14); C-E: *Aforia* sp. (19,7 mm) (DAII(08) DRN-22) (imágenes de lupa binocular).

tive shell morphology, with a broad distribution, nearly bipolar with very few species known in mid-latitudes (KANTOR *ET AL.*, 2016). Twelve of the species occur in the Antarctic. However, the exact number of species remains obscure and most are known from very few shells.

The shells here studied resemble *Aforia gonioides* (Watson, 1881). A detailed description and figures of this species, included the holotype, were provided by PASTORINO & SÁNCHEZ (2016, p. 460-463, figs. 1A-P, 2 A-H; 3A-C) and the species was also illustrated by KANTOR, HARASEWYCH & PUILLANDRE (2016, p. 41, fig. 18A-E). This latter species ranges from off Argentina southward throughout the Magellanic Province to the South Shetland Islands,

at depths of 150 m to 2212 m depth. The lectotype is a single and badly worn shell (illustrated by PASTORINO & SÁNCHEZ, 2016, fig. 1A-C, p. 461, and by KANTOR *ET AL.*, 2016, fig. A-C, p. 41). For this reason, the assignment of the specimens studied by these authors to *A. gonioides* is not entirely clear. PASTORINO & SÁNCHEZ (2016) also illustrated the type of *Pleurotoma clara* Martens, 1880, which they considered synonym of *A. gonioides* and which closely resembles the shells found in the samples studied by us. Nevertheless, we have preferred to refer these shells as *Aforia* sp. because of the geographical distance from the known distribution of *A. gonioides*.

The studied shells also resemble *Aforia circinata* Dall, 1873 (type species of the genus), a quite larger and more

slender species widely distributed in the North Pacific in the depth range 350-1500 m (HASEGAWA, 2009). Regarding the species of the genus inhabiting the same geographic area (*A. serranoi* Gofas, Luque & Kantor, 2014 and the fossil *A. clytrotropis*), the shells here studied exhibit intermediate characteristics, but the spiral

keel is located near the lower third of the whorls in both species, instead of in the middle, and the latter is larger and more slender. *Aforia serranoi* was found in a sample from 1720 m depth at the foot of the Galicia Bank (GOFAS ET AL., 2014a). The shells from our samples were obtained in the depth range 1000-1700 m.

Family DRILLIIDAE

Genus *Spirotropis* G.O.Sars, 1878

Type species: *Pleurotoma carinata* Bivona, 1838

Spirotropis confusa (Seguenza, 1880) (Figs. 9, 10, 42G)

Spirotropis sarsi Warén, 1975 - WARÉN (1075: 49, fig. 1a-f).

Spirotropis confusa confusa (Seguenza, 1880) - JANSSEN (1993: 252-253, pl. 4, figs. 19-21; pl. 5, fig. 22).

Spirotropis confusa (Seguenza, 1880) - SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2012: 97).

Type material: lost. Type locality: Riace, Calabria (S Italy), Later Pliocene.

Material examined (28 specimens with soft part and more than 70 empty shells in 25 samples): SPAIN • 1 spc + 2 sh (1 juv); 43°57.030'N, 008°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 008°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA IAT-1000 • 2 spc + 2 sh; 43°48.421'N, 008°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 008°51.091'W; 599-607 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-600 • 2 spc + 4 sh; 43°53.575'N, 008°56.868'W to 43°54.015'N, 008°56.959'W; 965-974 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-1000 • 2 sh; 43°53.847'N, 008°57.324'W to 43°54.621'N, 008°57.261'W; 993-1004 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 2 spc + 1 sh (1 juv); 43°51.873'N, 008°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 008°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-800 • 2 spc (1 juv) + 7 sh + 3 frg; 43°38.812'N, 009°07.949'W to 43°39.841'N, 009°07.405'W; 999-1001 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-DRN-1000 • 1 sh; polygon delimited by points 44° 10.000' N, 009° 00.000' W / 44° 10.000' N, 008° 35.000' W / 44° 00.000' N; 009° 00.000' W / 44° 07.000' N; 008° 35.000' W; 417-668 m; SARRIDAL (2006-07) SARRI-3 • 3 sh (2 juv); 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 sh; 44°06.84'N, 009°03.692'W to 44°07.075'N, 009°03.655'W; 911-886 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7-2 • 1 spc + 2 sh (1 juv); 44°06.113'N, 008°45.102'W to 44°06.282'N, 008°44.606'W; 434-433 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-10-2B • 6 juv + 1 frg 44°09.896'N, 008°39.581'W to 44°10.129'N, 008°39.494'W; 438-459 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-11 • 1 sh; 43°58.356'N, 008°52.149'W to 43°57.685'N, 008°52.903'W; 1054-1064 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-1 • 4 spc (3 juv) + 9 sh (2 juv); 43°56.478'N, 008°54.199'W to 43°55.934'N, 008°54.849'W; 620-933 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2 • 1 spc (juv); • 1 spc (juv) + 13 sh (3 juv); 43°55.886'N, 008°54.846'W to 43°55.291'N, 008°55.65'W; 933-930 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2B • 2 sh; 43°56.51'N, 008°49.869'W to 43°57.448'N, 008°749'W; 781-839 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-16-1 • 1 sh; 43°48.511'N, 008°51.393'W to 43°49.092'N, 008°50.959'W; 312-576 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-30-1 • 1 spc + 1 sh; 44°07.495'N, 008°46.999'W to 44°07.675'N, 008°45.225'W; 416-407 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-11-2 • 1 sh; 44°06.496'N, 008°23.522'W to 44°07.16'N, 008°23.201'W; 337-324 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-13 • 4 spc + 3 sh; 43°34.19'N, 009°22.12'W to 43°35.77'N, 009°21.23'W; 1005-1070 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-04 • 1 spc + 1 sh + 2 frg; 43°24.64'N, 009°31.56'W to 43°25.38'N, 009°30.97'W; 880-814 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp3-08 • 5 sh (1 juv) + 1 frg; 43°20.49'N, 009°34.03'W to 43°21.22'N, 009°32.96'W; 846-771 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-16 • 2 sh; 43°17.26'N, 009°36.4'W to 43°18.12'N, 009°36.32'W; 947-1011 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNr-17 • 1 spc + 3 sh + 2 frg; DRNr-18. • 1 sh; DRNp-31. • 1 frg; EBS-28 • 1 sh; 42°23'N, 009°24' 33.40" W to 42°23'N, 009°23' 32.05" W; 455-378 m; 14-25 Feb. 2009; FORSAGAL DRN-18 • 1 sh; 42°23.135'N, 009°35.76'W to 42°22.45'N, 009°35.59'W; 1043-1062 m; 14-25 Feb. 2009; FORSAGAL DRC-2.

Figure 9. *Spirotropis confusa*. A: shell (13.0 mm) (SE(08) DRN15-2); B: shell (13.1 mm) (DAI(03) DRN1000); C: shell (14.5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-15-2B); D, E: juvenile shell (6.3 mm) (SE(08) DRN-15-2B) and its protoconch; F-I: juvenile shell (4.1 mm) (SE(08) DRN-15-2B), protoconch and details of the microsculpture (A-C: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 9. *Spirotropis confusa*. A: concha (13,0 mm) (SE(08) DRN15-2); B: concha (13,1 mm) (DAI(03) DRN1000); C: concha (14,5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-15-2B); D, E: concha juvenil (6,3 mm) (SE(08) DRN-15-2B) y su protoconcha; F-I: concha juvenil (4,1 mm) (SE(08)DRN-15-2B), protoconcha y detalles de la microescultura (A-C: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

Description: Shell biconical, usually smooth and glossy (Figs. 9A-C, 10A, 42G), which with 8 teleoconch whorls reaches up to 14.5 x 5.2 mm in the

studied material. The tall and turreted spire is characterized by a rather prominent keel at the middle of the whorls (Figs. 8C, E, G, 9A, G). Siphonal canal

short and wide and labial notch well developed and deep over the subsutural ramp. Surface apparently smooth, but at high magnification sinuous growth lines are distinguished (Figs. 10C-D, G-H). Paucispiral, dome shaped protoconch of about 1.5 whorls and 1 mm in diameter (Figs. 9E, G, 10B, F). Delicate vertical and straight lines of growth can be observed at high magnification (Fig. 9E).

Remarks: *Spirotropis confusa* is mainly distributed from the western European Atlantic coasts to the Mediterranean. Some specimens were found off Portugal (1370-1430 m), Gulf of Cádiz (462-472 m), Alboran Sea (480 m), and off Sicily (480-500 m) (JANSSEN, 1993). SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2012) recorded it in the Sicily Chanel at 700 m. UTRILLA ET AL. (2020) have also found it alive in a mud volcano of the Gulf of Cádiz in the depth range 400-500 m. In the studied samples this species has been found in a wide depth range (324-1979 m).

Five species of *Spirotropis* are recognized in the NE Atlantic/Mediterranean area by the WoRMS data base: *S. confusa* (Seguenza, 1880), *S. monterosatoi* (Locard, 1897), *S. azorica* Bouchet & Warén, 1980, *S. centimata* (Dall, 1889) and *S. guancha* Ortega & Gofas, 2019. The last two are distinguished from the others

by exhibiting axially elongate knobs instead of the peripheral keel of the whorls (see figure 20, p. 537 in ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019), and *S. azorica* is more turreted. On the other hand, the two more widespread species in the area (*S. confusa* and *S. monterosatoi*) are rather variable and could encompass a species complex. WARÉN (1975, figs. 1A-F) showed the variability of *S. confusa* (as *S. sarsi*) and BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980, figs. 55-57, p. 18) synonymized *S. sarsi* with *S. monterosatoi*, illustrating its variability. Nevertheless, GOFAS (2011) pointed out that eyespots could be observed in the specimens with soft parts of *S. confusa* (as *S. sarsi*) coming from the BALGIM campaign (1984), while *S. monterosatoi* lacks eyes. A remarkable variability has been also found among the material here studied (see shells in Figs. 9A-C, 10A, 42G). We have only considered as a different species two notably larger specimens that we describe below as a new species (Figs.11, 42H) and we have identified all the others as *S. confusa*, since the eyespot could be observed in the specimens with soft parts. JANSSEN (1993) distinguished the subspecies *S. confusa confusa*, widely distributed, and *S. confusa sarsi* Warén, 1975 for the Norwegian populations.

Spirotropis galiciensis Oliver & Horro n. sp. (Figs.11, 42H)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:1439deFC-d07d-4aF1-b3b4-ba509713e2ea

Type material. *Holotype:* SPAIN • 1 specimen with soft parts (holotype); 43°19.29'N, 009°45.95'W to 43°20.17'N, 009°45.08'W; 1580-1518 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-14; MNHS, deposit number MHN-USC-10125. *Paratype:* SPAIN • 1 empty shell; 43°57.030'N, 008°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 008°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000

Type locality: bathyal depths of the continental slope off the W Galician coast (43°19.29'N, 009°45.95'W to 43°20.17'N, 009°45.08'W, 1518-1580 m depth).

Derivatio nominis: *galiciensis* refers to the fact that this species is described from off Galicia.

Description: Shell large, claviform, slender, spindle-shaped, smooth and glossy, with a strong blunt carina at about mid-whorls that divides them into a concave upper subsutural ramp and an almost straight lower part (Figs. 11A-C, 42H). The last whorl occupies about a third of the total height. Labial

notch well developed and deep, at the termination of the subsutural ramp (Fig. 11B). Siphonal channel wide and moderately short. Surface smooth, polished, without axial sculpture except on the last whorl, where it has irregular axial folds or swellings in the basal part protruding over the carina. Microsculpture

Figure 10. *Spirotropis confusa*. A: shell (11.8 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7); B: protoconch; C: second whorl of the teleoconch; D: growth lines; E-H: shell (11.0 mm), protoconch, second whorl of the teleoconch and growth lines (VE(04) GA-DRN-1000) (A, E: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 10. Spirotropis confusa. A: concha (11,8 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7); B: protoconcha; C: segunda vuelta de la teleoconcha; D: líneas de crecimiento; E-H: concha (11,0 mm), protoconcha, segunda vuelta de la teleoconcha y líneas de crecimiento (VE(04) GA-DRN-1000) (A, E: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

Figure 11. *Spirotropis galiciensis* Oliver & Horro, n. sp. A-D: holotype (21.5 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-14) and its protoconch (1.3 x 1.5 mm); E: paratype (24.0 mm) (DAI(02) AT1000) (A-C, E: stereo microscope images; D: SEM image).

Figura 11. *Spirotropis galiciensis* Oliver & Horro, n. sp. A-D: holotipo (21,5 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-14) y su protoconcha (1,3 x 1,5 mm); E: paratipo (24,0 mm) (DAI(02)AT1000) (A-C, E: imágenes de lupa binocular D: imagen SEM).

of growth lines and a weak spiral striation mainly visible in the subsutural ramp. Smooth paucispiral protoconch, rather large (1.3 mm in diameter and 1.6 mm height), mammillate, with somewhat more than 1.5 whorls and a clear sinusoidal limit with the teleoconch (Fig. 11D). Dimensions of the holotype: height 21.5 mm, width 7.8 mm, with 8 teleoconch whorls; paratype somewhat larger (height 24.0 mm). Ivory white colour (Fig. 2H).

Remarks: Only known from the two shells found in the studied samples at 1100 and 1518-1580 m depth. These two shells are clearly separable from the abovementioned five known species of *Spirotropis* inhabiting NE Atlantic. *S. azorica* is smaller (with more whorls) and much more slender. *S. centimata* and *S. guancho* have much more developed axial knobs.

Only *S. confusa* and *S. monterosatoi* resemble the new species by their overall shape and appearance. In spite of the high degree of variability usually admitted within these species, *S. gali-*

ciensis n. sp. presents a set of characters which together are conclusive about its specific condition:

- It is larger, since the other mentioned species do not usually exceed 14/15 mm, although exceptionally they reach 20/22 mm, and BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980, p. 18, figs. 55-57) even figured as *S. monterosatoi* a 26 mm shell.

- It has a larger protoconch. JANSSEN (1993) indicates 1.00 to 1.25 mm in *S. confusa* (with an average of 1.06 mm), and 0.85 to 1.075 mm in *S. monterosatoi* (with an average of 1,005). Only the subspecies *S. confusa sarsi* reaches a protoconch size similar to this new species, but it is restricted to Norwegian waters, has a wider shape and is smaller (it does not usually exceed 15 mm).

- Its siphonal canal is more constricted and more closed.

- The last whorl is proportionally shorter than in any other known European species of the genus, and has wide axial ribs, absent in *S. confusa* and *S. monterosatoi*.

Figure 12. *Micropleurotoma spirotropoides* (DAII(08) EBS-27). A-D: shell (5.1 mm), protoconch and details of the growth lines of the teleoconch; E, F: Shell (6.8 mm); G-I: juvenile shell (1.9 mm), detail of the transition to the teleoconch, and teleoconch microsculpture (F: stereo microscope image; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 12. *Micropleurotoma spirotropoides* (DAII(08) EBS-27). A-D: concha (5,1 mm), protoconcha y detalles de las líneas de crecimiento de la teleoconcha; E, F: concha (6,8 mm); G-I: concha juvenil (1,9 mm), detalle de la transición a la teleoconcha y microescultura de la teleoconcha (F: imagen de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

- It presents a microscopic spiral striation, absent in the above mentioned species.

This new species also resembles the polymorphic *Leucosyrinx verrilli* (Dall, 1881) (see BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980, pp.

23-25, figs. 68-69, 2002), but this latter species has a longer, straighter and narrower siphonal canal, obvious spiral sculpture (instead of a weak spiral striation in the new species), and axial ribs forming knobs on the keel.

Family HORAICLAVIDAE Bouchet, Kantor, Sysoev & Puillandre, 2011

Genus *Micropleurotoma* Thiele, 1929

Type species: *Pleurotoma spirotropoides* Thiele, 1925

Micropleurotoma spirotropoides (Thiele, 1925) (Figs. 12, 42K)

Micropleurotoma spirotropoides (Thiele, 1925) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 20, figs. 61-62).

Type material: syntypes in ZMUH. Type locality: in Agulhas Bank, southern African continental shelf.

Material examined (5 empty shells and some fragments in 4 samples): SPAIN • 1 sh (juv); 43°57.030'N, 008°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 008°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 1 frg; 44°08.461'N, 009°04.634'W to 44°08.607'N, 009°04.413'W; 917-896 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7-1 • 2 sh + 2 frg; 43°56.478'N, 008°54.199'W to 43°55.934'N, 008°54.849'W; 620-933 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2 • 3 sh; 42°45.9'N, 009°41.68'W to 42°47.00'N, 009°42.12'W; 1499-1373 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-27.

Description: Pagodiform shell similar to those of the genus *Spirotropis* (Figs. A, E-F, 42K). It is characterized by a pronounced keel slightly above the middle of the whorls, which delimits a somewhat concave subsutural ramp. The shells examined reach 6.8 x 3.5 mm with 6 whorls. Siphonal canal short and wide; labial notch at the peripheral keel. There is no axial sculpture except growth lines (Figs. 12C-D). At high magnification, in well-preserved shells, a microsculpture formed by very thin spiral threads sepa-

rated by wide interspaces can be appreciated (Fig. 12I). Paucispiral globose protoconch of somewhat more than one smooth whorl (Figs. 12B, G). Flexuose growth lines appear at the transition to the teleoconch (Fig. 12H).

Remarks: *Micropleurotoma spirotropoides* is known from few localities of northeast Atlantic and Mediterranean in the depth range 112-2028 m (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980). The few shells and fragments here studied were found in samples obtained between 900 and 1500 m.

Micropleurotoma travailleuri Bouchet & Warén, 1980 (Figs. 13, 42L)

Micropleurotoma travailleuri Bouchet & Warén, 1980 (p. 22, figs. 63-64).

Type material: lectotype in MNHN. Type locality: not known exactly; probably off Portugal.

Material examined (13 specimens and 39 empty shells in 16 samples): SPAIN • 2 sh; 43°57.030'N, 008°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 008°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 6 spc + 3 sh (2 juv); 43°53.575'N, 008°56.868'W to 43°54.015'N, 008°56.959'W; 965-974 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-1000 • 1 spc + 1 sh; 43°53.847'N, 008°57.324'W to 43°54.621'N, 008°57.261'W; 993-1004 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 2 spc + 1 sh + 1 frg; 43°48.587'N, 008°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 008°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 2 spc; 43°51.873'N, 008°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 008°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-800 • 7 sh; 43°38.812'N, 009°07.949'W to 43°39.841'N, 009°07.405'W; 999-1001 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-DRN-1000 • 1 sh; 43°38.105'N, 009°02.006'W to 43°37.738'N, 009°00.905'W; 836-826 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-800 • 1 spc; polygon delimited by points 44° 10.000' N, 009° 00.000' W / 44° 10.000' N, 008° 35.000' W / 44° 00.000' N; 009° 00.000' W / 44° 07.000' N; 008° 35.000' W; 480-600 m; SARRIDAL (2006-2007) SARRI-2 • 3 sh (1 juv); 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 2 sh; 43°56.478'N, 008°54.199'W to 43°55.934'N, 008°54.849'W; 620-933 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2 • 1 spc + 10 sh; 43°55.886'N, 008°54.846'W to 43°55.291'N, 008°55.65'W; 933-930 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2B • 1 sh; 43°33.53'N, 009°13.28'W to 43°33.90'N, 009°12.93'W;

Figure 13. *Micropleurotoma travailleuri*. A, B: shell (7.4 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7) and its protoconch; C, D: shell (4.2 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7) and its protoconch; E-G: shell (8.1 mm) (DAI(03) DRN1000) (E-G: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 13. Micropleurotoma travailleuri. A, B: *concha* (7,4 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7) y su *protoconcha*; C, D: *concha* (4,2 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7) y su *protoconcha*; E-G: *concha* (8,1 mm) (DAI(03) DRN1000) (E-G: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

725-737 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-03 • 6 sh; 43°24.64'N, 009°31.56'W to 43°25.38'N, 009°30.97'W; 880-814 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp3-08 • 1 sh; 43°17.26'N, 009°36.4'W to 43°18.12'N, 009°36.32'W; 947-1011 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNr-17 • 1 sh; 43°16.50'N, 009°34.52'W to 43°16.71'N, 009°33.79'W; 565-503 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNr-18 • 1 sh (juv); 43°34.86'N, 009°21.95'W to 43°36.44'N, 009°20.71'W; 1010-1112 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-04.

Description: Shell elongate, turritiform, with a high spire, attaining 8.1 mm in height and slightly more than 3.4 mm in width with 5 ½ whorls in the shells studied. Whorl profile angulated, with concave subsutural ramp and deep suture (Figs. 13A, F-G, 42L). There is no spiral sculpture. Axial ribs of variable

development, from weak sinuous to more strongly pronounced below shoulder, which starting from the base of the spire reach their greatest relevance towards the middle, where they form pointed tubercles, to later fade or weaken on the subsutural shelf. Broad labial notch and widely open siphonal

canal. Paucispiral protoconch, globose, with a little more than one whorl and without sculpture (Figs. 13B-D). Diameter 850 μm , height 680 μm . Transition to teleoconch sharp and prosocline growth lines just before (Fig. 13B).

Remarks: This species is only known in the continental slope of the Iberian Margin (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980). These authors proposed the replacement name of *Micropleurotoma travailleuri* for *Pleurotoma obtusa* Locard,

1897 (preoccupied by *Pleurotoma obtusa* Reeve, 1846) and noted that the generic position of this taxon is uncertain. Since then this matter remains unresolved.

We have found many shells and specimens in samples collected in the depth range 600-1100 m, which showed some variability in the sculpture and length of the siphonal canal. Because the existence of intermediate forms, we provisionally consider all of them belonging to the same species.

Family MANGELIIDAE Fischer, 1883

Genus *Bela* Leach, 1847

Type species: *Murex nebula* Montagu, 1803

Bela menkhorsti van Aartsen, 1988 (Figs. 14A-D, 42I)

Bela menkhorsti van Aartsen, 1988 - MARIOTTINI ET AL. (2009: 7-8); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 317); GOFAS (2011: 332); SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2015: 100).

Type material: lectotype selected by PEÑAS ET AL. (2008: fig. 18, p. 24) from three syntypes of *Pleurotoma nana* Scacchi, 1836 in MNHN. Type locality: Gulf of Naples (Italy).

Material examined (4 empty shells in 4 samples): SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°35.451'N, 008°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 008°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-150 • 1 sh (juv); 42°50.507'N, 009°25.773'W to 42°48.810'N, 009°25.198'W; 151-148 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS CA-EBS-150 • 1 sh; 43°29.412'N, 008°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 008°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-110 • 1 sh; 43°29.13'N, 008°43.233'W to 43°29.596'N, 008°42.838'W; 149-151 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-22.

Description: The few shells studied were all juvenile attaining up to 6.9 mm with almost 4 whorls. Axial sculpture of prominent rounded ribs as wide as their interspaces (Fig. 14A-C). Spiral sculpture of numerous very fine threads of variable size, densely alternating with narrower interspaces. Protoconch multispiral (Fig. 14D), dome shaped, of almost three smooth convex whorls except in the final part where closely set curved ribs can be observed. Protoconch-teleoconch transition not well marked, like in other species of the genus.

Remarks: *Bela menkhorsti* is a replacement name for *Pleurotoma nana* Scacchi, 1836 (not Deshayes, 1835). It is known from the entire Mediterranean Sea and from the neighbouring Atlantic (MARIOTTINI ET AL., 2009). These authors

reported it from shallow water down to 150 m in the Mediterranean and within the range 30-60 m off West Sahara. PEÑAS ET AL. (2008) recorded it in some localities of E Spain between 35 and 60 m, GOFAS (2011) in the Alboran Sea between 15 and 50 m and SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2015) in Croatia at 45 m depth. We have only found 4 juvenile and somewhat eroded shells collected in samples between 110 and 150 m depth, likely swept by the currents away from the coast.

One very damaged unidentifiable shell was found (Fig. 14E), which according to its size and shape seems to belong to the genus *Bela*. It could belong to the littoral species *Bela powisiana* (Dautzenberg, 1887) or *Bela nebula* (Montagu, 1803).

Figure 14. A, B: *Bela menkhorsti*, shell (6.9 mm) (DAI(02) EBS-150); C, D: shell (4.3 mm) (VE(04) GA-AT-110) and protoconch; E: *Bela* sp. (13.4 mm) (VE(04)GA-AT110); F-H: *Bela nuperrima*, shell (6.4 mm) (VE(04) GA-AT 110) (C, D: SEM images; the remaining: stereo microscope images).
 Figura 14. A, B: *Bela menkhorsti*, concha (6,9 mm) (DAI(02) EBS-150); C, D: concha (4,3 mm) (VE(04) GA-AT-110) y protoconcha; E: *Bela* sp. (13,4 mm) (VE(04)GA-AT110); F-H: *Bela nuperrima*, concha (6,4 mm) (VE(04) GA-AT 110) (C-D: imágenes de MEB; el resto: imágenes de lupa binocular).

Bela nuperrima (Tiberi, 1855) (Figs. 14F-H, 15, 42J)

Mangelia nuperrima (Tiberi, 1855) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 30-31, fig. 81); NEGRI & CORSELI (2016: 68, fig. 15e-h).

Bela nuperrima (Tiberi, 1855) - HORRO *ET AL.* (2018: 49-50, plate 2, figs. A-C, plate 3, figs. D-F).

Type material: two probable syntypes, adult and juvenile, in MCZR, illustrated by HORRO *ET AL.* (2018). Type locality: Gulf of Naples (Italy).

Material examined (3 specimens with soft parts and 3 empty shells in 4 samples): SPAIN • 1 sh (juv); 43°35.451'N, 008°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 008°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-150 • 2 spc (juv); 43°40.192'N, 008°43.760'W to 43°40.943'N, 008°42.366'W; 207-212 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-200 • 1 spc; 42°31.176'N, 009°23.380'W to 42°32.132'N,

009°24.151'W; 242-248 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS AG-EBS-250 • 1 sh (juv); 43°29.412'N, 008°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 008°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-110.

Description: The few specimens and shells found in the samples are all juveniles attaining up to 6.2 mm with about four whorls. Sculpture of opisthocline, somewhat sinuous, axial ribs narrower than their interspaces (Figs. 14G-G, 15A, K); fine and granular spiral threads, wider than their interspaces and pointed nodes at the intersection of ribs and threads (Fig. 15G). Dense microsculpture of granules throughout (Fig. 15-J). Multispiral and large protoconch of about 3.5 whorls (Fig. 15B-C). First whorl (protoconch I) with fine, discontinuous and granulose spiral threads (Fig. 15D-E). Transition to protoconch II poorly defined, where fine axial ribs gradually appear, being curved and

strongly opisthocline. Prominent spiral strands appear progressively, up to 5 in the final part of the protoconch (Fig. 15B). A microsculpture of tiny granules is initially located on the axial ribs, and homogeneously arranged over the entire surface near the transition to teleoconch (Fig. 15F-H).

Remarks: *Bela nuperrima* is an upper bathyal species distributed in the Mediterranean and NE Atlantic, from British waters to the West African coasts (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980). GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997, as *Mangelia*) found it deeper than 200 m off E Spain, and NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016) at 525-774 m depth in southern Italy. We have found it in samples within the depth range 110-250 m.

Genus *Kurtziella* Dall, 1918

Type species: *Pleurotoma cerinum* Kurtz & Simpson, 1851

Kurtziella serga (Dall, 1881) (Figs. 16, 42M)

Mangelia serga (Dall, 1881) - ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 69); BECK, METZGER & FREIWALD (2006: 80); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 322); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2012: 103); NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016: 68, fig. 15i).

Kurtziella serga (Dall, 1881) - ORTEGA & GOFAS (2019: 539, fig. 22C-E); GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021: fig. 27A-B).

Type material: holotype in MCZ (n° 7128). Type locality: bed of the Gulf Stream, W Atlantic, 810 m. **Material examined (1 specimen with soft parts and 2 empty shells in 2 samples):** SPAIN • 1 sh (juv); 43°57.030'N, 008°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 008°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 1 spc + 1 sh (juv) + 1 frg; 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

Description: Shell ovate-biconical, with a high spire and convex and angulated whorls, a slender aperture and a short siphonal canal (Fig. 42M). It attains 10 mm with 7 teleoconch whorls. Sculpture of axial ribs and spiral cords. There are two more relevant spiral cords and finer and granular spiral threads in the interspaces of the main cords. Last whorl with seven main spiral cords, two of them above the prolongation of the suture. Axial ribs somewhat sinuous, narrower than their interspaces and slightly opisthocline (16C). Between the

ribs, there are also sinusoidal growth lines (Fig. 16H). The entire surface of the shell is covered by a granular microsculpture (Fig. 16I-J). Multispiral protoconch of somewhat more than three whorls (Fig. 16D). Smooth protoconch I with ca. $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl and a somewhat twisted nucleus (Fig. 16E). Protoconch II with curved and opisthocline axial ribs. Irregularly arranged granules are observed on the ribs with high magnification (Fig. 16F-G).

Remarks: *Kurtziella serga* is a widespread amphiatlantic species distributed

Figure 15. *Bela nuperrima*. A: juvenile shell (3.1 mm) (DAI(03) EBS-200); B-H: protoconch and details of its microsculpture; I, J: details of the teleoconch microsculpture; K: juvenile shell (1.7 mm) (DAI(03) EBS-150) (SEM images).

Figura 15. Bela nuperrima. A: concha juvenil (3,1 mm) (DAI(03) EBS-200); B-H: protoconcha y detalles de su microscultura; I, J: detalles de la microscultura de la teleoconcha; K: concha juvenil (1,7 mm) (DAI(03) EBS-150) (imágenes de MEB)

Figure 16. *Kurtziella serga* (SE(08) DRN-7). A, B: shell (10.5 mm); C: juvenile shell (3.5 mm); D-G: protoconch and detail of its microsculpture; H-J: detail of the sculpture of the teleoconch (A, B: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 16. *Kurtziella serga* (SE(08) DRN-7). A, B: concha (10,5 mm); C: concha juvenil (3,5 mm); D-G: protoconcha y detalle de su microescultura; H-J: detalle de la escultura de la teleoconcha (A, B: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

in the northeastern Atlantic and throughout the Mediterranean (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980); in the western Atlantic from Bermudas to Brazil (DÍAZ & PUYANA, 1994; RIOS, 1994).

BOUCHET & TAVIANI (1992) recorded it in the depth range 440-1378 m in the

Ibero-Moroccan Gulf, and in 180-710 in the W Mediterranean, GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997 as *Mangelia*) deeper than 200 m in E Spain, ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999) in the Tyrrhenian Sea at 450 m, NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016) at 525-645 m in S Italy, ORTEGA & GOFAS (2019) in the depth range 480-665 m in Canary Islands, and

Figure 17. *Mangelia costata* (VE(04) GA-AT-110). A: shell (4.3 mm.); B, C: shell (4.2 mm) and its protoconch; D-F: juvenile shell (3.0 mm), protoconch and detail of its microsculpture (A: stereo microscope image; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 17. *Mangelia costata* (VE(04) GA-AT-110). A: concha (4,3 mm.); B, C: concha (4,2 mm) y su protoconcha; D-F: concha juvenil (3,0 mm), protoconcha y detalle de su microescultura (A: imagen de microscopio estereoscópico; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021) at 765-1100 m on the Galicia Bank, off NW Spain. GRACIA *ET AL.* (2004) recorded this species at 313-318 m in Colombian Caribbean. We have found it in samples from about

1000 m depth. The taxon *Raphitoma nuperrima* var. *corallinoides* Sturany 1896 (from Greece and Libya, 597-680 m depth) was considered a synonym of *Kurtziella serga* by ALBANO *ET AL.* (2018).

Genus *Mangelia* Risso, 1826

Type species: *Mangelia striolata* Risso, 1826

Mangelia costata (Pennant, 1777) (Figs.17, 42P)

Mangelia coarctata (Forbes, 1840) - FRETTER & GRAHAM (1985: 529-530); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 320).

Mangelia costata (Pennant, 1777) - ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 69); (GOFAS, 2011: 334).

Type material: probably in NHMUK. Type locality: not specified.

Material examined (13 empty shells in 3 samples): SPAIN • 1 sh (juv); 43°26.703'N, 008°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 008°29.612'W; 103-102 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-100 • 11 sh (juv);

43°29.412'N, 008°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 008°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-110 • 11 sh; 43°29.13'N, 008°43.233'W to 43°29.596'N, 008°42.838'W; 149-151 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-22.

Description: The few juvenile shells found in the studied samples attain up to 4.2 x 1.7 mm with about 7 convex whorls. Suture well defined and sinuous. Strong axial ribs narrower than the interspaces (Figs. 17A-B, D, 42P). Spiral sculpture of fine ridges wider than their interspaces. Microsculpture of curved growth lines, dense granulation and faint spiral striation (Fig. 17). Multispiral protoconch of about three whorls (Fig. 17C, E). First whorl apparently smooth, and sinuous axial ribs in the following.

Remarks: *Mangelia costata* is distributed from the Norwegian coasts to Morocco and the Mediterranean, wide-

spread in the continental shelf and upper slope (FRETTER & GRAHAM, 1985; GOFAS, 2011). GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997) and PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2006) recorded it in several Spanish Mediterranean localities from shallow water down to 350 m, and ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999) in the Tyrrhenian Sea at 350 m. GOFAS *ET AL.* (2014b) recorded it alive in the Avempace Bank (Alboran Sea) at 349-365 m depth in a bottom dominated by the crinoid *Leptometra*; UTRILLA *ET AL.* (2020) in a mud volcano of the Gulf of Cádiz in the 400-500 m depth range. The few shells found in the study samples were collected between 100 and 150 m.

Mangelia costulata Risso, 1826 (Figs. 18, 42O)

Cytherea smithi (Forbes, 1840) - FRETTER & GRAHAM (1985: 527-528).

Mangelia costulata Risso, 1826 - COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 320); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2010: 103); GOFAS (2011: 333); ÖZTÜRK (2021: 249, fig. 6).

Type material: lectotype in MNHN (photo in the MNHN website). Type locality: Alpes-Maritimes, France.

Material examined (2 specimens with soft parts and 11 empty shells in 3 samples): SPAIN • 1 spc (juv) + 10 sh (juv); 43°26.703'N, 008°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 008°29.612'W; 103-102 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-100 • 1 sh; 43°31.970'N, 008°37.670'W to 43°32.697'N, 008°3.171'W; 151 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-EBS-150 • 1 spc; 43°29.412'N, 008°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 008°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-110.

Description: The shells here studied were all juvenile (Figs. 18A-D, F, H, 40O) attaining up to 4.2 x 1.8 mm with 4 ½ whorls. Angulated in profile (in the upper part of the whorls) with sinuous axial ribs and a characteristic constrained spiral sculpture of ridges, square in cross section, a little broader than the interspaces, passing over the ribs (Fig. 18I). Multispiral protoconch with ca. 3 whorls (Fig. 18G, J). Smooth protoconch I with ¾ whorls (Fig. 18E). The transition to protoconch II is marked by a weak scar that is usually followed by some more prominent growth lines. At first, the surface continues to be smooth while the growth lines become increasingly sinuous and opisthocline. Some of these lines are

stronger and look like weak scars. Then, the sculpture gradually become more outstanding with up to seven spiral cords wider than its interspaces and equidistant curved ribs, also wider than its interspaces which protrude slightly above the suture. Transition to teleoconch not well defined.

Remarks: *Mangelia costulata* is distributed from the British Islands to Morocco and throughout Mediterranean, usually in soft bottoms in the upper part of the continental shelf (FRETTER & GRAHAM, as *Cytherea smithi*; 1985; GOFAS, 2011). ÖZTÜRK (2021) recorded it between 3 and 200 m along the Turkish coast. The shells here studied (including a specimen with soft parts) come from samples between 110 and 150 m depth.

Figure 18. *Mangelia costulata* (DAI(03) EBS-100). A: shell (4.2 mm); B: shell (3.0 mm); C-E: juvenile shell (1.1 mm) and its protoconch I; F, G: juvenile shell (1.2) and its protoconch; H, I: juvenile shell (1.5 mm), detail of its microsculpture and apical view (SEM images).

Figura 18. Mangelia costulata (DAI(03) EBS-100). A: concha (4,2 mm); B: concha (3,0 mm); C-E: concha juvenil (1,1 mm) y su protoconcha I; F, G: concha juvenil (1,2) y su protoconcha; H, I: concha juvenil (1,5 mm), detalle de su microescultura y vista apical (imágenes de MEB).

Mangelia tenuicosta (Brugnone, 1862) (Figs. 19, 42Q)

Mangelia tenuicosta (Brugnone, 1862) - COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 323); GOFAS (2011: 334), SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2015: 103); ÖZTÜRK (2021: 254, fig. 15).

Type material: probably in MCZR. Type locality: Near Palermo, Sicily.

Material examined (3 specimens with soft parts and 31 empty shells in 5 samples): SPAIN • 1 spc; 43°35.451'N, 008°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 008°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-150 • 26 sh (25 juv); 43°26.703'N, 008°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 008°29.612'W; 103-102 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-100 • 2 spc; 43°34.127'N, 008°36.562'W to 43°34.820'N, 008°35.585'W to 43°29.412'N, 008°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 008°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-110 • 1 sh; 43°58.719'N, 008°15.691'W to 43°58.942'N, 008°15.362'W; 231-233 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-20.

Description: Slender and tall shell, attaining 6.1 x 2.2 mm with over 6 whorls in the shells studied (Figs. 19A-B, 42Q). Convex whorls with the upper part somewhat flatter. Lanceolate aperture with a patent siphonal canal. Sharp and sinuous axial ribs, clearly narrower than their interspaces and adapically thinner, sigmoid on the juvenile shell (Fig. 19C) and becoming less curved as the shell grows. Weak spiral microsculpture of fine strap-like ridges, more evident at the base of the shell. Multispiral protoconch of 3 ½ whorls (Fig. 19D-F, H). Protoconch I almost smooth (Fig. 19H) although spiral micro-ridges can be seen crossing the growth lines in their transition to protoconch II at very high magnification in well-preserved shells, (Fig. 17G). The protoconch II begins without sculpture, with only the sinusoidal growth lines visible and sinusoidal micro-ribs progressively appear,

more evident at the final part protruding slightly above the adapical suture (Fig. 19E). Just above the suture there is a slight depression which at the end of the protoconch form a suprasutural ridge (Fig. 19I).

Remarks: *Mangelia tenuicosta* is distributed from the British Islands to Morocco and throughout the Mediterranean on the continental shelf (GOFAS, 2011). PEÑAS ET AL. (2008) recorded it in NE Spain at 30-60 m depth, SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2015) in some Italian and Greek localities between 12 and 40 m depth, and ÖZTÜRK (2021) found 2 shells of this species in a sample from the Levantine Turkish coast at 72 m in depth. It is quite similar to *Mangelia attenuata* (Montagu, 1803), from which it differs by its narrower and sharper axial ribs. Furthermore, *M. tenuicosta* and inhabits deeper bottoms. We have found it in samples from the depth range 100-200 m.

Genus *Oenopota* Mörch, 1852

Type species: *Fusus pleurotomarius* Couthouy, 1838

Oenopota graphica (Locard, 1897) (Figs. 20, 42N)

Oenopota graphica (Locard, 1897) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 72, fig. 152).

Type material: syntypes in MNHN. Type locality: off Morocco (TRAVAILLEUR expedition, 1882, drag. 40, 33°09'N - 9°38'W, 1900 m).

Material examined (5 specimens with soft parts and 37 empty shells in 8 samples): SPAIN • 1 spc (juv) + 3 sh; 43°53.575'N, 008°56.868'W to 43°54.015'N, 008°56.959'W; 965-974 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-1000 • 1 sh; 43°51.774'N, 008°53.640'W to 43°52.516'N, 008°53.478'W; 798-801 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-800 • 3 spc + 3 sh; 43°48.587'N, 008°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 008°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 1 sh (juv);

Figure 19. *Mangelia tenuicosta* (DAI(02) EBS-150). A, B: shell (6.1 mm) VE(04)GA-AT110; C: juvenile shell (4.1); D, E: juvenile shell (1.3 mm) and its protoconch; F, G: juvenile shell (1.1 mm), its embryonic protoconch and detail of the transition to protoconch II; H, I: lateral of a juvenile shell (1.2 mm) and detail of its sculpture (A, B: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).
 Figura 19. *Mangelia tenuicosta* (DAI(02) EBS-150). A, B: concha (6,1 mm) VE(04)GA-AT110; C: concha juvenil (4.1); D, E: concha juvenil (1,3 mm) y su protoconcha; F, G: concha juvenil (1,1 mm), su protoconcha embrionaria y detalle de la transición a la protoconcha II; H, I: vista lateral de una concha juvenil (1,2 mm) y detalle de su escultura (A, B: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB)

44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 4 sh; 44°08.461'N, 009°04.634'W to 44°08.607'N, 009°04.413'W; 917-896 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7-1 • 1 sh; 44°05.043'N, 008°57.977'W to 44°05.186'N, 008°57.821'W; 829-813 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7-3 • 1 spc + 8 sh; 43°56.478'N, 008°54.199'W to 43°55.934'N, 008°54.849'W; 620-933 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2 • 12 sh; 43°55.886'N, 008°54.846'W to 43°55.291'N, 008°55.65'W; 933-930 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2B.

Figure 20. *Oenopota graphica* (SE(08) DRN-7-1). A, B: shell (6.0 mm); C-F: shell (5.2 mm), protoconch and detail of its microsculpture (A, B: stereo microscope images; the remaining SEM images).
 Figura 20. *Oenopota graphica* (SE(08) DRN-7-1). A, B: concha (6,0 mm); C-F: concha (5,2 mm), protoconcha y detalle de su microescultura (A, B: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto de imágenes de MEB).

Description: Shell short, turriculated, characterized by its shouldered whorls and short aperture (Figs. 20A-C, 42N). Reaches up to 6 x 3 mm with five whorls in the shell studied. Whorls angled at about 2/3 of its height, leaving a slightly concave subsutural ramp. Sharp sculpture of straight or very slightly curved axial ribs narrower than their interspaces and strongly angulated at the periphery. Spiral cords clearly narrower than their interspaces. In the first whorl there are three cords and more are added as the shell grows. The adapical cord of each whorls delimits the subsutural ramp. Axial ribs start from the suture with a prosocline inclination and when they reach the first cord they form

an angle descending in an orthocline manner. Paucispiral dome-shaped protoconch (Figs. 20D) entirely covered of minute granules roughly aligned in irregular spiral ridges (Fig. 20E-F).

Remarks: *Oenopota graphica* is distributed along the bathyal bottoms of the Iberian and Moroccan margins (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980). The shell and specimens here studied come from samples between 600 and 1000 m depth.

Taranis monterosatoi Locard, 1897 is a synonym which was previously recorded in the studied area since its type locality is located off Galicia (43°01'N - 009°37'W, 2018 m, 13 Jun. 1881; R/V "Travailleur" 1881 sta. DR01).

Figure 21. *Oenopota* cf. *tenuicostata* (DAII (08) DRNp-14). A-C: shell (8,5 mm); D-G: shell (5,8 mm), protoconch and details of its microsculpture (A-C: stereo microscope images; the remaining SEM: images).
 Figura 21. *Oenopota* cf. *tenuicostata* (DAII (08) DRNp-14). A-C: concha (8,5 mm); D-G: concha (5,8 mm), protoconcha y detalles de su microsculptura (A-C: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

Oenopota cf. *tenuicostata* (G.O. Sars, 1878) (Figs. 21, 42S)

Oenopota tenuicostata (Sars, G.O., 1878) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 73-74, fig.142).

Type material: syntypes in ZMO. Type locality: Lofoten, Norway, 540 m.

Material examined (7 shells in 4 samples): SPAIN • 2 sh; 43°19.29'N, 009°45.95'W to 43°20.17'N, 009°45.08'W; 1580-1518 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-14 • 1 sh; 43°20.49'N, 009°34.03'W to 43°21.22'N, 009°32.96'W; 846-771 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-16 • 2 sh (juv); 43°34.86'N, 009°21.95'W to 43°36.44'N, 009°20.71'W; 1010-1112 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-04 • 2 sh (juv); 42°31.58'N, 009°40.14'W to 42°33.87'N, 009°38.75'W; 2030-1886 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-30.

Description: Ovate-biconical shell (attaining 8.5 x 3.7 mm in the studied shells) with a low spire and a high,

convex last whorl, angulated at the shoulder, reaching about two-thirds of the total height (Fig. 21A-D, 42S). Subsu-

tural ramp weakly concave to nearly straight. Wide aperture attaining slightly less than half the height of the shell with a short and wide siphonal canal. Sculpture of flexuous axial ribs and fine spiral threads. Microsculpture of weak granulation (Fig. 21G). Paucispiral obtuse protoconch, apparently smooth (Fig. 21E), but a weak and irregular spiral microsculpture can be observed at high magnification (Fig. 21F).

Remarks: The studied shells, coming from samples collected between 770 and 2000 m, are quite similar to the shell figured by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980, p. 69, fig. 142) as *O. tenuicostata*, and match the main specific characters they indicated for this species.

However, according to these authors, it is a bathyal pan-arctic species, reaching as far south as the northern British Islands and New England on the American side. Due to this geographic range and that slight difference, we keep this identification as tentative.

BOGDANOV (1990) considered *O. tenuicostata* junior synonym of *Curtitoma decussata* (Couthouy, 1839), while HØISÆTER (2009) cited it as one of the three most common species of the genus in western Norway, listing *O. decussata* as synonym. If the identification of the species is confirmed, the present records confirm the southernmost occurrence of *O. tenuicostata* reported by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 74)

Genus *Propebela* Iredale, 1918

Type species: *Murex turricula* Monagu, 1803

Propebela cf. *bergensis* (Friele, 1886) (Figs. 22-23, 42U)

Bela furfuraculata Locard, 1897 (p. 254, pl. 21, figs. 9-11).

Bela detegata Locard, 1897 (p. 256, pl. 21, figs. 12-14).

Oenopota bergensis (Friele, 1886) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 73, figs.146-148).

Propebela bergensis (Friele, 1886) - LUNDBERG ET AL. (1996).

Type material: syntypes of *Bela rugulata* var. *bergensis* Friele, 1886 in ZMB and NHMUK. Type locality: Bergen area, Norway, 180 m.

Material examined (6 specimens with soft parts and 17 empty shells in 11 samples): Form A: SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°53.847'N, 008°57.324'W to 43°54.621'N, 008°57.261'W; 993-1004 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 1 sh; 43°48.587'N, 008°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 008°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 1 sh; 43°51.873'N, 008°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 008°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-800 • 2 sh; 43°33.53'N, 009°13.28'W to 43°33.90'N, 009°12.93'W; 725-737 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-03 (p). Form B: SPAIN • 2 sh; 43°53.575'N, 008°56.868'W to 43°54.015'N, 008°56.959'W; 965-974 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-1000 • 1 sh; polygon delimited by points 44° 10.000' N, 009° 00.000' W / 44° 10.000' N, 008° 35.000' W / 44° 00.000' N; 009° 00.000' W / 44° 07.000' N; 008° 35.000' W; 417-668 m; SARRIDAL (2006-2007) SARRI-4 • 1 sh; polygon delimited by points 44° 10.000' N, 009° 00.000' W / 44° 10.000' N, 008° 35.000' W / 44° 00.000' N; 009° 00.000' W / 44° 07.000' N; 008° 35.000' W; 420-650 m; SARRIDAL (2006-2007) SARRI-5 • 1 spc + 5 sh + 1 frg; 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 5 spc + 1 sh (juv); 44°08.65'N, 008°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 008°55.104'W; 581-566 M; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 sh; 44°07.628'N, 008°45.871'W to 44°07.989'N, 008°45.542'W; 412-411 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-11-4 • 1 sh; 43°33.35'N, 009°08.31'W to 43°36.81'N. 009°07.34'W; 546-523 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-02.

Description: We have included a number of shells of somewhat variable morphology (Figs. 22A, 23A-B, E) within the name *Propebela* cf. *bergensis*,

which coincide with the descriptions and figures of this taxon.

Solid shell more or less oval to turriculate that reached up to 13.5 x 6 mm

Figure 22. *Propobela* cf. *bergensis* form A. A-C: shell (11.1 mm) (DAII(08) DRN-03) and protoconch; D, E: first whorl of another shell (DAII(08) DRN-03), detail of the columellar callus; F: detail of the lip insertion of another shell (SE(08) DRN7); G-I: microsculpture, protoconch and microsculpture of the protoconch, same shell as D; J-L: juvenile shell (6.0 mm), apical view and protoconch (DAI(03) EBS-800) (A, B, J: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 22. Propobela cf. *bergensis* forma A. A-C: concha (11,1 mm) (DAII(08) DRN-03) y protoconcha; D, E: primera vuelta de otra concha (DAII(08) DRN-03), detalle del callo columelar; F: detalle de la inserción del labio de otra concha (SE(08) DRN7); G-I: microescultura, protoconcha y microescultura de protoconcha, misma concha que D; J-L: concha juvenil (6,0 mm), vista apical y protoconcha (DAI(03) EBS-800) (A, B, J: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

with about 5 teleoconch whorls in the shells studied. Distinctly shouldered whorls with an oblique to almost horizontal subsutural ramp spanning between $\frac{1}{3}$ to $\frac{1}{4}$ of their upper part (Fig. 22D). Body whorl voluminous, exceeding $\frac{2}{3}$ of the total height. Undifferentiated anal sinus (Figs. 22F, 23C). Aperture lanceolate and distinct callus in its parietal wall (Fig. 22E). Short and wide siphonal canal. Between 14 and 18 orthocone axial ribs, narrower than the interspaces. Weaker spiral sculpture of numerous cords of variable width, closely spaced, and normally alternating wider with narrower. The sculpture weakens as the shell grows. Entire surface covered by microgranules (Fig. 22G). Large paucispiral protoconch about 1 whorl (Figs. 22C, H, K, L, 23D, G-H, J). Microsculpture of tiny granules and irregular spiral traces on which sketches of poorly marked and irregular spiral cords are superimposed (Figs. 22I, 23L) and gradually differentiate in the transition to teleoconch, at first of an irregular shape. The beginning of the teleoconch is determined by the appearance of the axial ribs (Figs. 22L, 23J).

Remarks: *Propebela bergensis* is known (as *Oenopota bergensis*) in the North Atlantic from the Arctic Sea to Morocco between 180 and 1900 m (BOUCHET &

WARÉN, 1980; BOGDANOV, 1990). HØISÆTER (2009) pointed out that this species is well represented on the upper slope of Norwegian waters from 502 to 830 m depth. LUNDBERG ET AL. (1996) transferred this taxon from *Oenopota* to *Propebela*. We have found specimens attributed to this species in samples collected between 400 and 1100 m.

The shells studied ranged between two extreme forms that we have called form A, more slender and slightly flatter protoconch (Fig. 22), and form B, wider, with a more marked shoulder and a higher protoconch (Fig. 23). However, we have considered them provisionally as belonging to the same species due to the variability in these characters and because the bathymetric range of both forms overlaps in the same area. LOCARD (1897-1898) distinguished the species *Bela furfuraculata* and *Bela detegata*, both considered by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980) as synonyms of *P. bergensis*, and whose holotypes are photographed in the database of the MNHN website. The shells of this taxon showed by these authors are similar to the holotype of *Bela furfuraculata* and to our form A, while *B. detegata* is closer to our form B. However, a detailed study of larger populations from different localities would be necessary to postulate specific differentiation.

Propebela cf. assimilis (Sars G.O., 1878) (Figs. 24A-B, 42R)

Oenopota scalaris (Möller, 1842) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 70, figs. 149-150).

Oenopota assimilis (Sars G.O., 1878) - BOGDANOV (1990: 181-183, figs. 322-237).

Propebela assimilis (Sars G.O., 1878) - LUNDBERG ET AL. (1996).

Type material: probably in UIO. Type locality: not designated in Arctic coast of Norway.

Material examined (1 subfossil shell): SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°04.16'N, 010°01.83'W to 43°05.00'N, 010°01.31'W; 3154-3160 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNr2-24.

Description: The subfossil shell studied measured 7.7 mm with four and a half whorl. Shell of rhomboid outline with rounded whorls and a subsutural ramp weakly defined (Figs. 24A-B, 42R). Orthocone axial ribs (near 20 in the body whorl) crossed by somewhat narrower spiral cords which gives the shell a cancellate appearance. Microsculpture

of numerous growth lines. Aperture lanceolate and developed callus in its parietal wall. Short siphonal canal. Paucispiral protoconch sculptured with spiral cords.

Remarks: The specific identification of the shell studied is tentative because this taxon has usually been mixed with other species of the genera *Oenopota* and

Figure 23. *Propobela cf. bergensis*, form B. A-D: shell (10.2 mm) (SE(08) DRN11-4), detail of the lip insertion and protoconch; E: shell (14.0 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-02); F-I: juvenile shell (7.4 mm), protoconch and details of its microsculpture (SE(08) DRN-7); J-L: apical view of a protoconch and details of its microsculpture (SE(08) DRN-7-C) (A, B, E: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 23. *Propobela cf. bergensis*, forma B. A-D: concha (10,2 mm) (SE(08) DRN11-4), detalle de la inserción del labio y protoconcha; E: concha (14,0 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-02); F-I: concha juvenil (7,4 mm), protoconcha y detalles de su microescultura (SE(08) DRN-7); J-L: vista apical de una protoconcha y detalles de su microescultura (SE(08) DRN-7-C) (A, B, E: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

Figure 24. A, B. *Propebela* cf. *assimilis* (7.7 mm) (DAII(08)DRNr2-24). C-G. *Phymorhynchus* sp. C-E: shell (31.1 mm) (DAII(08)DRNp-22); F, G: juvenile shell (14.0 mm) (SE(08)AT-12). H. *Phymorhynchus* sp. 2 (SE(08)AT-12) (Stereo microscope images).

Figura 24. A-B. *Propebela* cf. *assimilis* (7,7 mm) (DAII(08)DRNr2-24). C-G: *Phymorhynchus* sp. C-E: *concha* (31,1 mm) (DAII(08)DRNp-22); F, G: *concha* juvenil (14,0 mm) (SE(08)AT-12). H. *Phymorhynchus* sp. 2 (SE(08)AT-12) (imágenes de lupa binocular).

Propebela. BOGDANOV & ITO (1992) considered that the shells showed by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980, p. 70, figs. 149-150) belong to *O. assimilis*, and this taxon was transferred to the genus *Propebela* by LUNDBERG ET AL. (1996),

who commented some characters of its shell. This is an Arctic species (BOGDANOV, 1990; NEKHAEV, 2014), that is why the identification of the subfossil shell here studied (coming from the deepest sample, at 3160 m) is doubtful.

Genus *Sorgenfreispira* Moroni, 1979

Type species: *Cythara* (*Mangelia*) *moronii* Venzo & Pelosio, 1964.

Sorgenfreispira brachystoma (Philippi, 1844) (Figs. 25, 42V)

Mangelia brachystoma (Philippi, 1844) - FRETTER & GRAHAM (1985: 522-524, figs. 359-360).

Bela brachystoma (Philippi, 1844) - MARIOTTINI ET AL. (2008: 5, figs. 1-77); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 317); GOFAS (2011: 330).

Sorgenfreispira brachystoma (Philippi, 1844) - MARIOTTINI ET AL. (2015: 434-438, figs. 14-17).

Figure 25. *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma*. A: shell (3.3 mm) (VE(04) CA-EBS-150); B: shell (3.5 mm) from the same sample; C, D: details of its sculpture and microsculpture; E, F: juvenile shell (1.1 mm) and its protoconch (DAI(03)-EBS-100) (SEM images).

Figura 25. Sorgenfreispira brachystoma. A: concha (3,3 mm) (VE(04) CA-EBS-150); B: concha (3,5 mm) de la misma muestra; C, D: detalles de su escultura y microescultura; E, F: concha juvenil (1,1 mm) y su protoconcha (DAI(03)-EBS-100) (imágenes de MEB).

Type material: probably in MNHNSC according to MARIOTTINI *ET AL.* (2008). Type locality: Gulf of Naples.

Material examined (36 specimens with soft parts and about 100 empty shells in 11 samples): SPAIN • 1 spc (juv) + 1 sh; 43°35.451'N, 008°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 008°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-150 • 1 spc; 43°40.192'N, 008°43.760'W to 43°40.943'N, 008°42.366'W; 207-212 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-200 • 2 spc (juv); 43°41.113'N, 008°44.297'W to 43°41.905'N, 008°43.078'W; 256-258 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-250 • 1 spc (juv) + > 50 sh; 43°26.703'N, 008°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 008°29.612'W; 103-102 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-100 • 7 spc; 43°34.127'N, 008°36.562'W to 43°34.820'N, 008°35.585'W; 152-149 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-150 • 3 spc + 10 sh; 42°30.391'N, 009°19.517'W to 42°29.428'N, 009°17.924'W; 147-148 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS AG-EBS-150 • 9 spc + 3 sh; 42°50.507'N, 009°25.773'W to 42°48.810'N, 009°25.198'W; 151-148 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS CA-EBS-150 • 12 spc + 32 sh; 43°29.412'N, 008°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 008°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004;

VERTIDOS GA-AT-110 • 2 sh; 43°32.026'N, 008°37.520'W to 43°32.806'N, 008°35.993'W; 150-151 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-150 • 1 sh(juv); 43°36.686'N, 008°33.855'W to 43°38.066'N, 008°35.075'W; 166-165 m; 04-05 Jul. 2006; APLACOFORA Est1 EBS • 1 sh; 43°58.719'N, 008°15.691'W to 43°58.942'N, 008°15.362'W; 231-233 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-20 • 1 sh (juv); 43°29.13'N, 008°43.233'W to 43°29.596'N, 008°42.838'W; 149-151 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-22.

Description: Shell small (up to 7 x 2.5 mm according to MARIOTTINI *ET AL.*, 2015), attaining 4.5 mm in the shells here studied. Its sculpture is very characteristic, with prominent, flexuous and axial ribs, and a spiral sculpture of raised, granulated cords, separated by broader interspaces, one stronger cord at shoulder producing an angulated profile of the whorls (Figs. 25A-B, E, 42V). Entire surface covered by microgranules (Fig. 25C-D). Multispiral, dome shaped, protoconch (Fig. 25F). Smooth protoconch I and reticulated sculptured protoconch II with 5 nodose spirals (the upper

and lower less developed) crossed by opisthocline axial riblets.

Remarks: *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma* is known from Scandinavia to southern Morocco and the entire Mediterranean Sea. It is a continental shelf species, recorded between 25 m down to 350 m by MARIOTTINI *ET AL.* (2008, 2015). GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997) recorded it as abundant off NE Spain in samples collected between 200 and 450 m depth. The studied shells and specimens were found in samples collected within the 110-260 m depth range.

Family RAPHITOMIDAE

Genus *Phymorhynchus* Dall, 1908

Type species: *Pleurotomella castanea* Dall, 1896

Phymorhynchus sp. (Figs. 24C-G, 43G)

Material examined (two eroded subfossil shells, one of them juvenile, in 2 samples): SPAIN • 1 sh (juv); 44°14.929'N, 008°30.255'W to 44°15.367'N, 008°30.438'W; 2121-2516 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-12 • 1 sh; 43°05.28'N, 009°41.77'W to 43°06.25'N, 009°40.99'W; 1727-1763 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-22.

Description: Shell fusiform, slender, buccinoid, with slightly convex whorls and pronounced and regularly spaced spiral cords, with somewhat wider interspaces, crossed by weak axial ribs (Fig. 24C-E). Suture shallow and appressed subsutural ramp nearly flat, which occupies about a quarter of each whorl. The last whorl occupies two-thirds of the total height. Aperture high and elongate with thin outer lip, not thickened. Anal sinus very shallow, subsutural, indistinguishable on upper teleoconch whorls and absent on lower ones. Protoconch missing in the two shells studied. Dimensions of the adult shell studied 31 x 13 mm.

Remarks: The two shells studied are quite eroded, especially the first whorls, and the protoconch is missing in both. We presume that the smaller one (Fig. 24F-G)

could be a juvenile of the larger, but we are not sure. We have tentatively assigned the two studied shells to the genus *Phymorhynchus* Dall, 1908 because of its resemblance to *P. chevreuxi* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1897), only known from its type locality, at bathyal depths (1600 m) near the Azores Islands (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980). However, none of the NE Atlantic known species of the genus match enough with the shells here studied. Thus, *P. alberti* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1906), the largest turrid from our area, with a maximum size of 95 mm, is more globose and lacks an appressed subsutural ramp. *Phymorhynchus sulciferus* (Bush, 1893) has more convex and angulated whorls, and *P. chevreuxi* has more convex whorls and greater predominance of spiral sculpture. Another damaged shell, probably belong-

Figure 26. *Gymnobela abyssorum*. A, B: shell (18.8 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-04); C-H: juvenile shell (2.5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7), protoconch, details of its microsculpture and microsculpture of the teleoconch (A, B: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 26. *Gymnobela abyssorum*. A, B: *concha* (18,8 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-04); C-H: *concha juvenil* (2,5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7), *protoconcha*, detalles de su microsculptura y microsculptura de la *teleoconcha* (A, B: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

ing to this genus, was found (Fig. 24H as *Phymorhynchus* sp. 2).

The genus *Phymorhynchus* is common in vent/seep environments with about 11 known species in those

extreme environments (ZHANG & ZHANG, 2017). The two studied subfossil shells were collected in samples at about 1750 m and 2516 m depth in a bottom of large stones, phosphorites and corals.

Genus *Gymnobela* Verrill, 1884

Type species: *Gymnobela engonia* Verrill, 1884

Gymnobela abyssorum (Locard, 1897) (Figs. 26, 43A)

Gymnobela abyssorum (Locard, 1897) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 49-50, fig. 113); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 69); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 328); GOFAS (2011: 340); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2014: 98); MANOUSIS *ET AL.* (2018: Fig. 2c. p. 13-14); ORTEGA & GOFAS (2019: 539, fig. 22A, B); GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021: 67, fig. 26H-I).

Type material: Lectotype in MNHN. Type locality: Not specified; perhaps from off Northern Spain according to BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980).

Material examined (4 specimens with soft parts and 7 empty shells in 5 samples): SPAIN • 1 spc + 1 frg; 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 3 spc + 1 frg; 44°08.65'N, 008°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 008°55.104'W; 581-566 M; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 sh; 43°34.19'N, 009°22.12'W to 43°35.77'N, 009°21.23'W; 1005-1070 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-04 • 5 sh; 43°20.00'N, 009°38.06'W to 43°20.63'N, 009°37.59'W; 1268-1293 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-15 • 1 sh; 43°19.92'N, 009°38.13'W to 43°21.25'N, 009°37.11'W; 1267-1286 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-15.

Description: Shell stout, biconical, distinctly shouldered, with an almost flat subsutural ramp, occupying about 1/3 of the whorls below a shallow suture and bordered by a blunt keel (Figs. 26A-B, 43A). Sculpture of unequally spaced spiral cordlets and broader axial folds (Fig. 23C). The entire surface of the shell covered by microgranules (Fig. 26H). Large, multispiral protoconch, with more than 4 highly cancellate convex whorls (Fig. 26D), as in other Raphitomiidae. Protoconch I with a dozen spiral ridges of cruciform granules forming a kind of grid (Fig. 26F). Protoconch II of a characteristic diagonally cancellate sculpture (Fig. 26E, G).

Remarks: *Gymnobela abyssorum* is a quite common species known from the northern part of the Bay of Biscay to the Ibero-Moroccan Gulf and the Canary

Islands, and in the Mediterranean, in a wide bathymetric range (BOUCHET & WARÉN 1980; ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019). ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999) recorded it in the Tyrrhenian Sea at 450 m depth, PEÑAS ET AL. (2006) in the Alboran Island deeper than 200 m, GOFAS ET AL. (2014b) recorded it alive in the Avempace Bank (Alboran Sea) at 349-365 m in a bottom dominated by the crinoid *Leptometra*, SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2014) in the middle Adriatic at 80 m, MANOUSIS ET AL. (2018) found one shell at 400 m in the Aegean Sea, and ORTEGA & GOFAS (2019) in Canary Islands in a volcanic and bioclastic bottoms at 240-300 m. This species was also found in the summit of the Galicia Bank (GOFAS ET AL., 2021). The shells and specimens here studied were collected between 566 and 1317 m.

Gymnobela subaraneosa (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Figs. 27, 43C)

Gymnobela subaraneosa (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 58, figs. 114-115); GOFAS ET AL. (2021: 68, fig. 27I-J)

Type material: lectotype in MOM. Type locality: off São Miguel Island, Azores (Hirondelle and Princesse-Alice expeditions, sta. 553, 37°43'N - 25°05'W, 1385 m).

Material examined (2 specimens with soft parts and 2 empty shells in 3 samples): SPAIN • 1 spc + 1 sh (juv); 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 spc; 44°08.461'N, 009°04.634'W to 44°08.607'N, 009°04.413'W; 917-896 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7-1 • 1 sh; 43°09.47'N, 009°44.63'W to 43°10.23'N, 009°44.22'W; 2099-2104 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-21.

Description: Shell slender, somewhat thin and fragile (Figs. 27A-B, 43C). Profile of the whorls characterized by a subsutural keel that delimits a narrow ramp (Fig. 27C, G) with growth lines and curved elevations resulting from the growth of the anal notch (Fig. 27I). The sculpture was weak in the shells

studied, of little relevant spiral cords and curved axial ribs. Both cords and ribs are narrower than their interspaces. As in the two previous species, the entire surface of the shell is covered by microgranules (Fig. 27J). Aperture high, occupying more than half the height of the shell with a short and wide siphonal

Figure 27. *Gymnobela subaraneosa*. A, B: shell (8.9 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-21); C-F: juvenile shell (3.5 mm), (SE(08) DRN-7) protoconch and details of its microsculpture; G-J: juvenile shell (1.8 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7) and details of its microsculpture (A, B: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 27. *Gymnobela subaraneosa*. A-B: concha (8,9 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-21); C-F: concha juvenil (3,5 mm), (SE(08) DRN-7) protoconcha y detalles de su microescultura; G-J: concha juvenil (1,8 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7) y detalles de su microescultura (A, B: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

canal. Anal sinus subsutural, moderately shallow to deep (Fig. 27H). Multispiral protoconch with about 4 convex whorls, a somewhat twisted apex and sculpture quite similar to that of the pre-

vious species (Figs. 27D-F). Progressive transition between protoconch I and II.

Remarks: *Gymnobela subaraneosa* is a deep bathyal species which may extend to about 4000 m depth in NE Atlantic and

Mediterranean (BOUCHET & WARÉN 1980; SYSOEV, 2014). GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021) recorded many shells in the Galicia Bank between 675-1125 m depth. The few shell and specimens studied come from samples collected in the bathymetric range 900-2010 m.

BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980) pointed out that this species exhibits appreciable variability in the sculpture, from rather coarsely sculptured to nearly smooth. The shell here studied exhibit transitional characteristics.

Genus *Austrobel*a Criscione, Hallan, Puillandre & Fedosov, 2021

Type species: *Austrobel*a *rufa* Criscione, Hallan, Puillandre & Fedosov, 2021 by original designation

*Austrobel*a *pyrrhogramma* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Figs. 28, 43B)

*Gymnobel*a *pyrrhogramma* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 55, fig. 111); GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021: 67, fig. 26J-K).

*Austrobel*a *pyrrhogramma* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) - CRISCIONE, HALLAN, FEDOSOV & PUIL-
LANDRE (2021a, fig. 6j, k, p. 1730, including the holotype).

Type material: holotype in MOM (INV-18477), photographed in CRISCIONE *ET AL.* (2021a, p. 1730, fig. 6j). Type locality: off Pico Island, Azores (Hirondelle and Princesse-Alice expeditions sta. 234, 39°02'N - 27°56'W, 545 m).

Material examined (3 specimens with soft parts and 14 empty shells in 8 samples): SPAIN • 3 sh (juv); 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 3 spc; 44°08.65'N, 008°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 008°55.104'W; 581-566 M; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 sh; DRN-15-2. • 1 sh; DRN-15-2B. • 2 sh + 3 frg; 43°24.64'N, 009°31.56'W to 43°25.38'N, 009°30.97'W; 880-814 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp3-08 • 4 sh; 43°20.00'N, 009°38.06'W to 43°20.63'N, 009°37.59'W; 1268-1293 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-15 • 1 sh (juv); EBS-04. • 1 sh; 43°19.92'N, 009°38.13'W to 43°21.25'N, 009°37.11'W; 1267-1286 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-15.

Description: Shell slender, biconical, strongly shouldered (Figs. 28A-B, 43B). A concave subsutural zone with thin curved axial ribs (Fig. 28E) bordered by the shoulder (Fig. 28C, G). Sculpture of rounded orthocline axial ribs, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, and narrow spiral cords, somewhat wider than their interspaces. The entire surface of the shell covered by microgranules (Fig. 28F). Multispiral large protoconch with a blunt apex and about 4 cancellate whorls, similar to others Raphitomidae (Fig. 28D, H-J).

Remarks: *Austrobel*a *pyrrhogramma* is known (as *Gymnobel*a *pyrrhogramma*) in the upper bathyal of the Azores and Spanish Atlantic coasts and southwards (BOUCHET & WARÉN 1980). GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021) recorded it in the Galicia Bank at 985-1000 m. The shells here studied were found in samples coming in the 570-1300 m depth range and collected alive at 566-581 m depth. CRISCIONE *ET AL.* (2021a) proposed the formal transfer of this species to the genus *Austrobel*a.

Genus *Neopleurotomoides* Shuto, 1971

Type species: *Clathurella rufoapicata* Schepman, 1913

Neopleurotomoides callebryon (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Figs. 29, 43D)

Neopleurotomoides callebryon (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 43-44, figs. 100-101); BECK, METZGER & FREIWALD (2006: 81); ORTEGA & GOFAS (2019, figs. 22H-J, p. 539); GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021, fig. 27E-F, p. 68).

Figure 28. *Austrobelula pyrrogramma*. A, B: shell (16.8 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-03); C-F: juvenile shell (4.5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7), protoconch and details of the microsculpture; G-I: juvenile shell (2.7 mm), protoconch and details of its microsculpture from the same sample (A, B: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 28. *Austrobelula pyrrogramma*. A, B: concha (16,8 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-03); C-F: concha juvenil (4,5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7), protoconcha y detalles de la microescultura; G-I: concha juvenil (2,7 mm), protoconcha y detalles de su microescultura del mismo ejemplar (A, B: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

Type material: holotype in MOM. Type locality: off São Miguel Island, Azores (Hirondelle and Princesse-Alice expeditions sta. 553, 37°43'N - 25°05'W, 1385 m).

Material examined (5 juvenile shells in 1 sample): SPAIN • 5 sh(juv) + 1 frg; 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

Description: Shells small (attaining 4.5 x 2.3 mm with 2 ½ whorls in the shells here studied), with a short spire and whorl profile angulated at shoulder, delimiting a narrow subsutural ramp, slightly concave and nearly horizontal (Fig. 29A, C, 43D). Sculpture of narrow axial and spiral cords ribs, nearly equidistant and narrower than the interspaces, making spiny projections in the intersections and defining quadrangular areas (Fig. 29C). Convex base and sinuous columella, without thickening or parietal callus. Lanceolate aperture with a short and wide siphonal canal and shallow anal notch. A finer spiral cord runs along the lower part of the subsutural ramp, above which there are thick and curved growth lines (Fig. 29E), and a microsculpture of minute granules scattered on the surface (Fig. 29I-J). Multispiral protoconch with more than four whorls (diameter ca. 650 µm, height 775 µm), characterized by a spiral keel in the middle and perpendicular

fine axial ribs on the lower part below the keel (Fig. 29B, D, F-G).

Remarks: *Neopleurotomoides callem-bryon* is a bathyal to abyssal species recorded from the Eastern Atlantic margin, known off western Iberian Peninsula, Azores and Canary Islands, and in some NE Atlantic seamounts (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980; BECK *ET AL.*, 2006; ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019). GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021) pointed out that this species is common on the summit of the Galicia Bank somewhat deeper than 600 m. We have found it only in one sample collected between 908 and 1106 m.

The shells described by CAETANO *ET AL.* (2006) from off Brazil are more slender and with a wider subsutural ramp than the holotype and the shell here studied. Further, their protoconch microsculpture also differs somehow. Therefore the shells from SW Atlantic attributed by these authors to *N. callem-bryon* probably belong to a different species.

Neopleurotomoides senharisi Oliver, Horro & Urgorri, n. sp. (Figs. 30, 43E)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:931238ea-4d8d-40c0-9505-6975b2762ae6

Type material. *Holotype:* SPAIN • 1 specimen with soft parts 44°14.929'N, 008°30.255'W to 44°15.367'N, 008°30.438'W; 2121-2516 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-12; MNHS, deposit number: MHN-USC-10125.

Type locality: The fishing area locally known as A Selva, off the N Galician coast (44°14.929'N, 008°30.255'W to 44°15.367'N, 008°30.438'W, 2121-2516 m depth).

Derivatio nominis: This species is named after Dr. Marcos Pérez Señaris in recognition of his substantial contributions to the knowledge of the Mollusca Caudofoveata from the area covered in the present paper.

Description: Shell medium sized (11.6 x 6.6 mm), oval-fusiform, very thin, fragile, translucent and glossy (Fig. 43E). Teleoconch with four and a half convex whorls, with rounded profile and a deep suture (Fig. 30A). Subsutural ramp slightly concave and oblique, occupying slightly less than 1/3 of the whorl, with arcuate growth lines following the shape of the anal sinus (Fig. 30F). Sculpture of axial ribs and spiral cords of similar width, much narrower than their respective interspaces. Over twenty ribs on the last whorl. Two spiral cords at the beginning of the teleo-

conch and some more appear between them, almost equidistant. Another less developed cord runs along the lower part of the subsutural ramp. About 12 spiral cords in the last whorl, 7 of them below the anal sinus, and diagonal folds on the convex basal part (Fig. 30G). At the crossing of ribs with cords, acute nodules protrude and rectangles are clearly drawn (Fig. 30H). Entire surface of the teleoconch covered with very tiny granules densely distributed (Fig. 30I). Aperture wide and elliptical, outer lip thin (not thickened), smooth columella without parietal callus,

Figure 29. *Neopleurotomoides callembryon* (SE(08) DRN-7). A, B: shell (4.5 mm) and protoconch; C-E: shell (3.6 mm), protoconch and detail of its subsutural ramp; F-H: protoconch and details of its sculpture; I, J: microsculpture of the teleoconch (SEM images).

Figura 29. Neopleurotomoides callembryon (SE(08) DRN-7). A, B: concha (4,5 mm) y protoconcha; C-E: concha (3,6 mm), protoconcha y detalle de su rampa subsutural; F-H: protoconcha y detalles de su escultura; I, J: microescultura de la teleoconcha (imágenes de MEB).

wide and shallow anal sinus and siphonal canal. Multispiral protoconch (Fig. 30B), light brown in colour, 790 μm high and 775 μm width, with just over four whorls. Protoconch I of one and a half whorls (Fig. 30D), apparently smooth but with weak granules with slight traces of spiral lines, even less marked axial lines can be appreciated at high magnification (Figs. 30D-E). Protoconch II with a rounded profile and sculpture of axial ribs and a spiral keel at the lower third of the whorls, which does not give an angled appearance (Figs. 30B-C). The axial ribs are orthocline below the keel and curved and slightly prosocline in the upper two thirds.

Remarks: This new species resembles the NE Atlantic *N. callembrion* and the SW Atlantic *N. aembe* Figueira & Absalão, 2012, but it is noticeably larger, translucent and with a more rounded, less angular profile of the whorls, and steeper

and wider subsutural ramp. Their protoconchs also differ; it is also larger and despite the presence of a spiral keel in the new species, its whorls are rounded in profile instead of angular like in the other two mentioned species. The spiral keel of the protoconch has a somewhat lower position and the axial ribs are complete above the keel in the last whorl, incomplete in *N. callembrion* and stronger and more closely set in *N. aembe* (FIGUEIRA & ABSALÃO, 2012). *Neopleurotomoides distincta* Bouchet & Warén, 1980, from the North Atlantic, has weaker axial ribs and more closely spaced spiral cords, without spiny projections in the intersections (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980).

This new species is only known from the holotype, collected with soft parts in a bathyal bottom of large stones, phosphorites, sand and corals at 2121-2516 m depth.

Genus *Pleurotomella* A. E. Verrill, 1872

Type species: *Pleurotomella packardii* A. E. Verrill, 1872

Pleurotomella gibbera Bouchet & Warén 1980 (Figs. 31, 43M)

Pleurotomella gibbera Bouchet & Warén 1980 (p. 41, fig. 93) - GOFAS (2011: 340); NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016: 70, fig. 16a-c); MANOUSIS ET AL. (2018: 7, fig. 2d); GOFAS ET AL. (2021: 68, fig. 27G-H).

Pleurotomella cf. *gibbera* Bouchet & Warén 1980 - COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 329).

Type material: holotype in NHMUK (photo in BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980, fig. 93, p. 40). Type locality: Adventure Bank (Strait of Sicily), 166 m (PORCUPINE expedition).

Material examined (3 juvenile shells, one of them with soft parts, in 3 samples): SPAIN • 1 spc; 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 sh; 44°08.65'N, 008°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 008°55.104'W; 581-566 M; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 sh (juv); 43°24.64'N, 009°31.56'W to 43°25.38'N, 009°30.97'W; 880-814 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp3-08.

Description: The juvenile shells studied attained 3.8 mm with almost three convex whorls (Figs. 31A, 43M). Sculpture of rounded and rather prominent axial ribs (with interspaces slightly wider) and narrower spiral cords that become denser towards the base (Fig. 31A). Subsutural ramp with curved and well-marked growth lines and a thin spiral cord in its lower part (Fig. 31D). Microsculpture of small irregular granules (Fig. 31E). Multispiral protoconch,

proportionally large, of about 5 whorls (Fig. 31B, F). Protoconch I with spirally connected T-shaped granules forming a square reticulated pattern (Fig. 31C, G). Protoconch II with the characteristic cancellate reticulation of other raphitomidae and 2 additional prominent spirals just before its termination (Fig. 31F).

Remarks: *Pleurotomella gibbera* is a well-known species whose distribution extends from the north-west of the Iberian Peninsula to the Ibero-Moroccan

Figure 30. *Neopleurotomoides senharisi* Oliver, Horro & Urgorri, n. sp., holotype (SE(08) AT-12). A: shell (11.6 mm); B, C: protoconch and its sculpture; D, E: protoconch I and detail of its sculpture; F: detail of the subsutural ramp; G-I: details of the sculpture and microsculpture of the teleconch (SEM images).

Figura 30. Neopleurotomoides senharisi Oliver, Horro & Urgorri, n. sp., holotipo (SE(08) AT-12). A: concha (11,6 mm); B, C: protoconcha y su escultura; D, E: protoconcha I y detalle de su escultura; F: detalle de la rampa subsutural; G-I: detalles de la escultura y microescultura de la teleconcha (imágenes de MEB).

Gulf, northwestern African waters and Mediterranean, extending to the Aegean Sea, mainly in the outer shelf and upper slope (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980; GOFAS, 2011; MANOUSIS *ET AL.*, 2018).

PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2006) recorded it around the Alborán Islands at 200 m depth, MANOUSIS *ET AL.* (2018) found two shells at 400 m off Lemnos Island (Aegean Sea), GOFAS *ET AL.* (2014a) recorded it alive in the Avempace Bank (Alboran Sea) at 349-365 m in a bottom dominated by the crinoid *Leptometra*,

UTRILLA *ET AL.* (2020) found some empty shells in a mud volcano in the Gulf of Cádiz in the 400-500 m depth range, and GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021) in the upper part of the Galicia Bank between 600 and 1000 m. The few shells studied were collected in samples from 580 and 1100 m. They are similar to those described by the aforementioned authors, but somewhat different from the holotype shown by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980), which has less angular whorls and a steeper subsutural ramp.

Pleurotomella demosia (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Figs. 32-33, 43L)

Pleurotomella demosia (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 39, fig. 91); BECK, METZGER & FREIWALD (2006: 81); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 329); GOFAS (2011: 340); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2012: 101); NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016: 69); ORTEGA & GOFAS (2019: 539, fig. 22K, L); GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021: 68, fig. 27O-P).

Type material: holotype in MOM. Type locality: between Pico and São Jorge Islands, Azores (Hiron-delle and Princesse-Alice expeditions, sta. 233, 38°33'N - 28°09'W, 1385 m).

Material examined (11 empty shells, most of them juvenile, in 4 samples): SPAIN • polygon delimited by points 44° 10.000' N, 009° 00.000' W / 44° 10.000' N, 008° 35.000' W / 44° 00.000' N; 009° 00.000' W / 44° 07.000' N; 008° 35.000' W; 720 m; SARRIDAL (2006-2007) SARRI-1 • 2 sh (juv); 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 5 sh (4 juv); 44°08.65'N, 008°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 008°55.104'W; 581-566 M; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 2 sh (juv); 44°07.495'N, 008°46.999'W to 44°07.675'N, 008°45.225'W; 416-407 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-11-2.

Description: The shells studied attained up to 7 mm with 5 convex whorls and spire of stepped profile (Figs. 32A, E, G, 43L). Subhorizontal subsutural ramp. Sculpture of rounded orthocone axial ribs and superimposed thin spiral cords, both narrower than their interspaces. At high magnification, in well-preserved shells, the entire surface of the shell appears covered by roughly aligned microgranules (Figs. 32C-D). On the subsutural ramp these granules line up, highlighting the labial sinus. Oval aperture with a short and wide siphonal canal. Multispiral protoconch of about 3 globose whorls (Figs. 32B, F, H-I, 33C-D). Its sculpture is like in other Raphitomidae.

Remarks: *Pleurotomella demosia*, originally described from the Azores about 1400 m depth, is distributed from the northeastern Atlantic southward to the

Moroccan coast and the western Mediterranean in the 120-1980 m depth range (BOUCHET & WARÉN 1980; BOUCHET & TAVIANI 1992; GOFAS, 2011).

GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997) recorded this species off NE Spain in samples collected between 200 and 450 m depth, NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016) at 515-520 m in southern Italy, SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2012) in coral-ligenous bottoms of the Tyrrhenian Sea at 120 m, UTRILLA *ET AL.* (2020) in a mud volcano of the Gulf of Cádiz in the 400-500 m depth range, ORTEGA & GOFAS (2019) in the Canary Islands at 345 m depth, and GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021) in the depth range 675-1125 m. We have found some shells in samples collected between 400 and 1100 m. One of the juvenile shells had a smaller protoconch of more than 3 whorls (Figs. 33A-B, as *Pleurotomella cf. demosia*), but the other characters matched those of the species.

Figure 31. *Pleurotomella gibbera* (SE(08) DRN-7) A-C: juvenile shell (3.8 mm), protoconch and details of its microsculpture; D: subsutural ramp; E: details of microsculpture of the teleoconch of the same shell; F-I: protoconch and details of its microsculpture of other shell (SEM images).

Figura 31. Pleurotomella gibbera (SE(08) DRN-7) A-C: concha juvenil (3,8 mm), protoconcha y detalles de su microsculptura; D: rampa subsutural; E: detalles de microsculptura de la teleoconcha de la misma concha; F-I: protoconcha y detalles de su microsculptura de otra concha (imágenes de MEB).

Figure 32. *Pleurotomella demosia*. A-D: juvenile shell (3.2 mm) (SE(08) AT-11-2), protoconch and details of the microsculpture of its teleoconch; E, F: juvenile shell (2.0 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7-C) and protoconch; G-I: juvenile shell (2.2 mm) (SE(08) AT-11-2), protoconch and detail of the embryonic protoconch (SEM images).

Figura 32. *Pleurotomella demosia*. A-D: concha juvenil (3,2 mm) (SE(08) AT-11-2), protoconcha y detalles de la microescultura de su teleoconcha; E, F: concha juvenil (2,0 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7-C) y protoconcha; G-I: concha juvenil (2,2 mm) (SE(08) AT-11-2), protoconcha y detalle de la protoconcha embrionaria (imágenes de MEB).

Figure 33. A, B: *Pleurotomella cf. demosia* (SE(08) DRN-7-C), juvenile shell (2.3 mm) and its protoconch; C, D: *Pleurotomella demosia*, same locality, juvenile shell (2.9 mm) and its protoconch (SEM images).

Figura 33. A, B: *Pleurotomella cf. demosia* (SE(08) DRN-7-C), concha juvenil (2,3 mm) y su protoconcha; C, D: *Pleurotomella demosia*, misma localidad, concha juvenil (2,9 mm) y su protoconcha (imágenes de MEB).

Pleurotomella eurybrocha (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Figs. 34E-H, 43L)

Defrancia implicisculpta Sturany, 1896 - ALBANO, SCHNEIDL & ESCHNER (2018: 42, fig. 7).

Pleurotomella eurybrocha (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 39-41, figs. 224-225); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 70); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 329); NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016: 70, fig. 15j-l); ORTEGA & GOFAS (2019: 539, fig. 22M-N); GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021: 68, fig. 27M-N).

Type material: holotype in MOM. Type locality: between Pico and São Jorge Islands, Azores (Hiron-delle and Princesse-Alice expeditions, sta. 233, 38°33'N - 28°09'W, 1385 m).

Material examined (1 eroded shell): SPAIN • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

Description: The eroded shell here studied measures 3.5 x 2.1 mm with about 4 teleoconch whorls. Shell fusiform with convex whorls and a narrow concave subsutural ramp separated from the remaining part by 2 close spiral cords (Figs. 34E, 43L). Quite orthocline axial ribs, clearly narrower than their interspaces, starting from below the subsutural ramp and many arched growth lines are observed on this (Fig. 34H). Ribs and spiral cords form a lattice (Fig. 34G). Aperture pear-shaped and broad and short siphonal canal. The shell studied had the multispiral protoconch eroded (Fig. 34F), so the detail of

its sculpture is not clearly appreciated but agrees with that shown by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980).

Remarks: *Pleurotomella eurybrocha* ranges from the northeastern Atlantic, including the Azores and Canary Islands, and the Mediterranean in a wide depth range of 200-4425 m (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980; JANSSEN, 1989). PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2006) recorded it near the Alboran Island, NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016) found a single juvenile specimen at 680 m depth, ALBANO *ET AL.* (2018) off Egypt at 2420 m (type locality of *Defrancia implicisculpta* Sturany, 1896, a junior synonym of *Pleurotomella eurybrocha*), ORTEGA & GOFAS

(2019) in Canary Islands at 655-660 m, and GOFAS *ET AL.* (2021) in the Galicia Bank at about 680 and 1120 m). The shell here studied was found in a sample collected at 929 -1106 m.

A broken shell attributed to *Pleurotomella* cf. *packardii* was found in a sample at 2100 m (Fig. 34C-D). Due to the lack of protoconch it is not possible to ensure specific identification.

Pleurotomella cf. *benedicti* Verrill & S. Smith, 1884 (Figs. 34A-B, 43F)

Pleurotomella benedicti Verrill & S. Smith [in Verrill], 1884 - VERRILL (1884: 148-149, pl. 31, fig. 2); BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 37, figs. 86-87).

Type material: holotype in USNM. Type locality: off New England, W Atlantic (40°17'N - 67°05'W, 2360 m).

Material examined (1 subfossil shell): SPAIN: • 1 sh; 44°14.929'N, 008°30.255'W to 44°15.367'N, 008°30.438'W; 2121-2516 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-12.

Description: The shell studied was slender, fusiform, with elevated spire (Fig. 34A-B, 43F) and measured 13.1 mm. Teleoconch whorls weakly convex, slightly angulated at shoulder and with an appressed subsutural ramp, nearly flat, occupying $\frac{1}{4}$ of each whorl, with conspicuous growth lines. Axial ribs narrower than interspaces, crossed by a coarse and faint spiral striation. Aper-

ture moderately high and oval. Siphonal canal widely open, poorly differentiated from aperture. Protoconch not preserved in the studied shell.

Remarks: BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980) recorded few specimens in the Gulf of Biscay at 2170-2360 m. The subfossil shell here studied come from a sample taken at 2516 m. This shell agrees broadly with the description and figure of VERRILL (1884).

Genus *Cyrellia* Kobelt, 1905

Type species: *Murex linearis* Montagu, 1803

Cyrellia aequalis (Jeffreys, 1867) (Figs. 35, 36G-J, 43N)

Raphitoma aequalis (Jeffreys, 1867) - COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 324); GOFAS (2011: 339); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2012: 98); HØISÆTER (2016: 16-19, figs. 2B-C, 3B, 8-9, 11), MANOUSIS *ET AL.* (2018: 6, fig. 3 a-b); ÖZTÜRK & GEYRAN (2021: 432-433, fig. 1).

Cyrellia aequalis (Jeffreys, 1867) - FASSIO *et al.* (2019); HOARAU & HORST (2020: p. 13).

Type material: not found (according to WARÉN, 1980). Type locality: probably north of the British Islands.

Material examined (8 specimens with soft parts and 10 empty shells in 4 samples): SPAIN • 5 spc; 43°26.703'N, 008°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 008°29.612'W; 103-102 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-100 • 1 spc; 43°34.127'N, 008°36.562'W to 43°34.820'N, 008°35.585'W; 152-149 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-150 • 2 spc + 8 sh (juv); 43°29.412'N, 008°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 008°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-110 • 2 sh; 44°07.628'N, 008°45.871'W to 44°07.989'N, 008°45.542'W; 412-411 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-11-4.

Description: The shells studied attain up to 5.9 x 2.7 mm (Figs. 35A-B, 36G-G, 43N). The teleoconch microsculpture of minute granules (Fig. 35I), better visible between spiral cords, is characteristic.

Protoconch multispiral (Figs. 35C, G, 36I) with a clear-cut transition between protoconch I and protoconch II. Protoconch I of about one whorl with a fine crosslinking sculpture (Fig. 35H). Proto-

Figure 34. A, B: *Pleurotomella* cf. *benedicti* (13.1 mm) (SE(08) AT-12); C, D: *Pleurotomella* cf. *packardii*: broken shell (16.2 mm) (DAII DRNp-21); E-H: *Pleurotomella eurybrocha* (3.5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7), protoconch, detail of the subsutural ramp and microsculpture of the teleoconch (A-D: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 34. A, B: *Pleurotomella* cf. *benedicti* (13,1 mm) (SE(08) AT-12); C, D: *Pleurotomella* cf. *packardii*, *concha rota* (16,2 mm) (DAII DRNp-21); E-H: *Pleurotomella eurybrocha* (3,5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7), protoconcha, detalle de rampa subsutural y microescultura de la teleoconcha (A-D: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

conch II with diagonal cancellation on the lower 2/3 of the whorls and axial riblets on the upper part (Figs. 35C, D-F). Towards the end of the protoconch, a kind of cord appears in the central area of the whorls that gradually becomes a kind of central keel (Figs. 35C, 36I).

Remarks: *Cyrrillia aequalis* ranges from Norway to Morocco and the entire Mediterranean, on detritic bottoms of the continental shelf (GOFAS, 2011; HØISÆTER, 2016). HOARAU & HORST (2020) recorded this species at 70 m depth in the French Mediterranean coast, and ÖZTÜRK & GEYRAN (2021) between 25 and 70 m along the Aegean Turkish coast and mentioned 1 speci-

men in Iskenderun Bay (Levantine Sea) at 46 m. The studied specimens were collected between 100 and 200 m depth.

Cyrrillia aequalis has been often treated as a synonym of *C. linearis*, but the latter species has thicker axial ribs, more spiral cords, more prominent spirals with interrupted brown lines, and a microsculpture of minute granules (see for comparison figures 36 and 43N,O).

FASSIO *ET AL.* (2019) suggested treating *Raphitoma linearis* (Montagu, 1803), *R. aequalis* and *R. obesa* Høisæter, 2016 as a distinct genus for which they proposed the available name *Cyrrillia* Kobelt, 1905.

Figure 35. *Cyrrillia aequalis*. A: shell (5.9 mm) (SE(08) DRN-11); B-F: juvenile shell (3.3 mm), protoconch and its microsculpture (VE(04) GA-AT-110); G, H: apical view of the protoconch of other shell from the same sample and detail of the embryonic protoconch; I: microsculpture of its teleoconch (SEM images).

Figura 35. *Cyrrillia aequalis*. A: concha (5,9 mm) (SE(08) DRN-11); B-F: concha juvenil (3,3 mm), protoconcha y su microescultura (VE(04) GA-AT-110); G, H: vista apical de la protoconcha de otra concha de la misma muestra y detalle de la protoconcha embrionaria; I: microescultura de su teleoconcha (imágenes de MEB).

Figure 36. Comparison *Cyrillia linearis* / *C. aequalis* (VE(04) GA-AT-110). A, B: *Cyrillia linearis* (5.0 mm); C-E: *Cyrillia linearis*, juvenile shell (2.5 mm), protoconch and sculpture of the siphonal canal; F, G: *Cyrillia aequalis* (5.6 mm), H-J: *Cyrillia aequalis*, juvenile shell (2.4 mm), protoconch and sculpture of the siphonal canal (A, B, F, G: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 36. Comparación *Cyrillia linearis* / *C. aequalis* (VE(04) GA-AT-110). A, B: *Cyrillia linearis* (5,0 mm); C-E: *Cyrillia linearis*, Concha juvenil (2,5 mm), protoconcha y escultura del canal sifonal; F, G: *Cyrillia aequalis* (5,6 mm); H-J: *Cyrillia aequalis*, concha juvenil (2,4 mm), protoconcha y escultura del canal sifonal (A, B, F, G: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

Cyrellia linearis (Montagu, 1803) (Figs. 36A-E, 43O)

Raphitoma linearis (Montagu, 1803) - FRETTER & GRAHAM (1985: 535-37); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 324); GOFAS (2011: 338); SCAPERROTTA *ET AL.* (2012: 97); HØISÆTER (2016: 21-23, figs. 1A, 2A, 3A, 14-17); MANOUSIS *ET AL.*, 2018: 19, fig. 14d-f); ÖZTÜRK & GEYRAN (2021: 442-443, fig. 17).
Cyrellia linearis (Montagu, 1803) - FASSIO *ET AL.* (2019); HOARAU & HORST, 2020)

Type material: lectotype designated by ROLÁN *ET AL.* (1998, fig. 21, p. 106) from ten syntypes in NHMUK (1995090). Type locality: Falmouth Harbour, Cornwall, England.

Material examined (3 eroded shells, two of them juvenile, in 1 sample): SPAIN • 3 sh (2 juv); 43°29.412'N, 008°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 008°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-110.

Description: It is a very common and widespread littoral species in rocky bottoms, easy to identify. and illustrated in many publications, sometime confused with *C. aequalis*. OLIVER *ET AL.* (2017) illustrated the type material.

Cyrellia linearis ranges from northern Norway to Morocco and the entire Mediterranean (GOFAS, 2011). We only found 3 eroded shells in one of the studied samples collected at 110 m, probably washed away from coastal bottoms.

Genus *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847

Type species: *Raphitoma histrix* Bellardi, 1847

Raphitoma aff. *echinata* (Brocchi, 1814) (Figs. 37, 43K)

Raphitoma echinata (Brocchi, 1814) *sensu* AA - GOFAS (2011: 337); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2018: 9, 63, figs. 16B, 63F); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2019: 60, 63, figs. 8-10, 28); ÖZTÜRK & GEYRAN (2021: 438 figs. 10H-I).

Raphitoma cf. *echinata* (Brocchi, 1814) - COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 325).

Type material: three syntypes in MCSNM. PINNA & SPEZIA (1978) designated a lectotype, however PRKIĆ *ET AL.* (2020) pointed out that the three syntypes belong to 3 different entities and only one of the paralectotypes (fig. 14, p. 234 in PRKIĆ *ET AL.* (2020) corresponds to the figure and description of BROCCHI (1814) and to the currently accepted concept of *R. echinata*. Type locality: Pliocene (Piacentian) of Italy.

Material examined (1 empty shell): SPAIN • 1 sh; 44°07.495'N, 008°46.999'W to 44°07.675'N, 008°45.225'W; 416-407 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-11-2.

Description: The shell studied measured 10.2 mm with six teleoconch whorls. Fusiform, with high spire and convex and shouldered teleoconch whorls (Fig. 44A-C). Sculpture of orthocline axial ribs (15 on the body whorl), narrower than interspaces, crossed by about 5 spiral cords above the aperture forming spiny extensions. Smooth shell surface with no visible granules. Aperture oval, columella slightly sinuous, and wide siphonal canal. Light cream-colour with darker suture. The spiral cords are discontinuously coloured of

reddish-brown, especially at their intersections with the axial ribs. Multispiral protoconch of somewhat more than 3 whorls, of which the last two diagonally cancellate, and the last one carinate (Fig. 34F-I).

Remarks: The taxa "*Raphitoma echinata*" *sensu* authors is known in NE Atlantic from Norway to Morocco and the Mediterranean, mainly in detritic bottoms of the continental shelf GOFAS (2011). ÖZTÜRK & GEYRAN (2021) recorded it between 2 and 70 m along the Aegean Turkish coast and mentioned 1

Figure 37. *Raphitoma* aff. *echinata* (SE(08) AT-11-2) A-C: shell (10.2 mm); D-G: protoconch and details of its sculpture (SE(08) AT-11-2) (A-C: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).
 Figura 37. *Raphitoma* aff. *echinata* (SE(08) AT-11-2) A-C: concha (10,2 mm); D-G: protoconcha y detalles de su escultura (SE(08) AT-11-2) (A-C: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

specimen in the Sea of Marmara at 100 m. The studied shell comes from a sample collected at 407-416 m.

The identification of the taxon *R. echinata* is rather problematic and some authors have referred to it as *Raphitoma echinata* complex because under this name have been included several forms (HØISÆTER, 2016; GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.*, 2018; MANOUSIS *ET AL.*, 2018). PELORCE & HORST (2020) consider *R. echinata* as a fossil species and described three new extant species of this complex

in coastal waters of the French Mediterranean coast. One of the forms cited by MANOUSIS *ET AL.* (2018) as *R. echinata* was attributed by GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2019) to *R. hispidella* Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli, 2019, a nomen novum proposed by them to replace *Cordieria cordieri* var. *hispidella* Monterosato, 1890, non *Raphitoma hispidella* Bellardi, 1877. While this species-complex is not reviewed, we prefer to refer to the shell here studied as *Raphitoma* aff. *echinata*.

Genus *Leufroyia* Monterosato, 1884

Type species: *Pleurotoma leufroyi* Michaud, 1828

Leufroyia erronea Monterosato, 1884 (Figs. 38A-F, 43H)

Raphitoma erronea (Monterosato, 1884) - PUSATERI & GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI (2008: 123, fig. 15, syntype 16704); APPOLLONI ET AL. (2018: 60-61, 1 fig 22M syntype 17340); MANOUSIS ET AL. (2018: 14-17, fig. 11a-e).

Leufroyia erronea (Monterosato, 1884) - FASSIO ET AL. (2019); GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2020: 454-459, figs. 14-16).

Type material: two syntypes in MCZR (M-16704, M-17340. Type locality: unprecised localities (Corsica, Sardinia, Sicily, Dalmatia).

Material examined (1 shell somewhat eroded): SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°56.51'N, 008°49.869'W to 43°57.448'N, 008°749'W; 781-839 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-16-1.

Description: The only shell found in the samples (Fig. 38A) measured 16.2 mm with about 6 whorls. A photograph of this shell was included in the review of GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2020, fig. 15D, p. 456), who provided a very detailed descriptions, remarks and a bulk of illustrations of this species. Suboval profile, wide aperture, with equidistant, orthocone axial ribs, broader than the spiral cords. Narrow subsutural ramp covered with dense growth marks (38D-E). Whole surface covered with microgranules (Fig. 38F). The multispiral protoconch is similar to those of the other species of *Leufroyia* and *Raphitoma* (Figs. 34 B-C).

Remarks: *Leufroyia erronea* is known from the from the Shetland Islands to

Portugal (including Madeira and Azores) and the whole Mediterranean Sea, more frequently found on rocky bottoms of the continental shelf (GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL., 2020). PEÑAS & GIRIBET (2003) recorded it off NE Spain in samples collected between 200 and 450 m depth. The only shell studied was found at about 800 m, the deepest record for the species. As it is an old shell it could have been dragged from shallower depths.

FASSIO ET AL. (2019) assigned genus ranking *Leufroyia* Monterosato, 1884 to the lineage composed by *R. leufroyi* (Michaud, 1828), *R. concinna* (Scacchi, 1836), *R. vil-laria* (Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli, 2008) and *R. erronea*, genus subsequently revised by GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2020).

Leufroyia cf. inflata (de Cristofori & Jan, 1832) (Figs. 38G, 43I)

Leufroyia inflata De Cristofori & Jan, 1832 - GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2020: 464, fig. 21A-B).

Type material: lectotype in MCSNM (i4296) (after PINNA & SPEZIA, 1978, pl. 40; see also photograph in GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL., 2020, fig. 21A). Type locality: Tabiano (Parma), Italy, Piacentian (Pliocene).

Material examined (1 fossil shell): SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°56.478'N, 008°54.199'W to 43°55.934'N, 008°54.849'W; 620-933 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-15-2.

Description: The fossil shell studied was incomplete and somewhat deteriorated (Figs. 38G, 43I). It measured 9.9 mm with 5 convex whorls. Sculpture of wide axial ribs and closely spaced spiral cords (more than thirty in the last

whorl), clearly wider than their inter-spaces, with alternation of wider and narrower ones, and narrow spiral cords in the concave subsutural ramp. Deep suture. Multispiral protoconch similar to those of the other species of *Leufroyia*,

Figure 38. A-F. *Leufroyia erronea* (16.2 mm) (SE(08) DRN-16-1). A: shell; B, C: protoconch; D-F: details of the sculpture and microsculpture of the teleconch. G. *Leufroyia cf. inflata* (9.9 mm) (SE(08)DRN-15-2) (A, G: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 38. A-F *Leufroyia erronea* (16,2 mm) (SE(08) DRN-16-1). A: concha; B, C: protoconcha; D-F: detalles de la escultura y microescultura de la teleconcha. G. *Leufroyia cf. inflata* (9,9 mm) (SE(08)DRN-15-2) (A, G: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

genus in which we believe this shell should be included.

Remarks: *Pleurotoma inflata* was described as a Plio-Pleistocene species, which has been misinterpreted and confused with *Leufroyia leufroyi* (Michaud, 1828), *L. villaria* (Pusateri & Giannuzzi-Savelli, 2008) and *L. erronea* Monterosato 1884 by different authors fide GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL* (2020). The shell

here studied is similar to their figures 21B and C, which represent the true *L. inflata* according to these authors, just with stronger sculpture. It was collected in a sample taken between 620-933m. We are not sure if the fossil species is more related to recent forms of *L. leufroyi* or *L. villaria*, this is why we have preferred to mention it as *Leufroyia cf. inflata*.

Genus *Taranis* Jeffreys, 1870

Type species: *Trophon moerchii* Malm, 1861

Taranis cf. *moerchii* (Malm, 1861) (Figs. 39, 42W)

Taranis moerchii (Malm, 1861) - BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980: 80-81, figs. 163-165); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 71); NEKHAEV (2014: 103, fig. 10B-C); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 330); GOFAS (2011: 341); SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2015: 96); MANOUSIS ET AL. (2008: 34, fig. 25a).

Type material: lost. Type locality: Hagardskaren, Bohuslan, Swedish west coast, 90 m.

Material examined (1 empty shell): SPAIN • 1 sh; 44°06.113'N, 008°45.102'W to 44°06.282'N, 008°44.606'W; 434-433 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-10-2B.

Description: Minute fusiform shell (4.4 x 2.0 mm in the studied shell). High spire and convex, angulated whorls (Figs. 39A-C, 42W). A prominent spiral cord located somewhat above the middle of the whorls forms a kind of keel making a shoulder and delimiting an oblique subsutural ramp. Axial sculpture of fine sinuous ribs, narrower than their interspaces, overhanging the spiral cords and giving a cancellate appearance. Very tiny granules organized into spiral rows on the teleoconch (Fig. 39H). Aperture lanceolate, outer lip thin and a wide anal notch at the end of the keel. Siphonal canal short, open and truncated. Globose paucispiral protoconch of somewhat more than one whorl (Figs. 39D-E) and ornamented with roughly aligned anchor-shaped granules (Fig. 39F-G).

Remarks: *Taranis moerchii* is a widespread species in the outer shelf and

bathyal bottoms of both sides of the North Atlantic and the Mediterranean (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980). GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997) recorded it off NE Spain in samples collected between 200 and 450 m depth, ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999) in the Tyrrhenian Sea at 550 m, and SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2015) in Corsica (France) and Alboran Sea at 400 and 200 m respectively. Only one shell has been found in a sample from 433 m depth.

According to BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980) the sculpture of this species is very variable. Due to its supposed low dispersal capacity, coupled with its wide geographic distribution, from the Barents Sea (NEKHAEV, 2014) to the Mediterranean, a complex of species could be hidden under the name *Taranis moerchii*. The only shell studied matches those shown by GIRIBET & PEÑAS (1997) and GOFAS (2011).

Teretia teres (Reeve, 1844) (Figs. 40, 41, 43P)

Teretia teres (Reeve, 1844) - FRETTER & GRAHAM (1985: 543-544); ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999: 71); GOFAS (2011: 341); BECK, METZGER & FREIWALD (2006: 81); COSSIGNANI & ARDOVINI (2011: 328); GOFAS (2011: 341); MORASSI & BONFITTO (2015: 567, fig. 3A-F), SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2015: 97); NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016: 68-69); HORRO & ROLÁN (2017: 145-146, figs. 1A-D, 2A-D); MANOUSIS ET AL. (2018: 34 fig. 25c); GOFAS ET AL. (2021: 67, fig. 26N).

Type material: not found, probably lost. Type locality: Aegean Sea.

Material examined (more than 100 specimens with soft parts and 57 empty shells in 31 samples): SPAIN • 3 spc; 43°47.188'N, 008°53.053'W to 43°55.312'N, 008°53.101'W; 770-842 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-800 • 2 spc + 8 sh (juv); 43°35.451'N, 008°34.432'W to 43°34.810'N, 008°35.407'W; 153-151 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-150 • 5 spc; 43°40.192'N, 008°43.760'W to 43°40.943'N, 008°42.366'W; 207-212 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-200 • 1 spc; 43°41.689'N, 008°45.195'W to 43°42.556'N, 008°44.226'W; 298-303 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-300 • 1 spc; 43°42.427'N, 008°45.921'W to 43°43.253'N, 008°44.818'W; 347-

Figure 39: *Taranis cf. moerchii* (SE(08) DRN-10-2B). A-C: shell (4.4 x 2.0 mm); D-H: protoconch and details of its sculpture; F: microsculpture of the teleoconch (A, B: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 39: Taranis cf. moerchii (SE(08) DRN-10-2B). A-C: concha (4,4 x 2,0 mm); D-H: protoconcha y detalles de su esculptura; F: microescultura de la teleoconcha (A, B: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

243 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-350 • 1 spc; 43°45.892'N, 008°44.301'W to 43°46.966'N, 008°43.766'W; 390-381 m; 08-15 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-400 • 1 spc (juv); 43°48.421'N, 008°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 008°51.091'W; 599-607 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-600 • 1 spc (juv); 43°51.774'N, 008°53.640'W to 43°52.516'N, 008°53.478'W; 798-801 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-800 • 1 sh; 43°53.847'N, 008°57.324'W to 43°54.621'N, 008°57.261'W; 993-1004 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 15 spc (juv) + 1 sh; 43°26.703'N, 008°30.669'W to 43°27.452'N, 008°29.612'W; 103-102 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-100 • 6 sh (juv); 43°40.250'N, 008°43.755'W to 43°40.760'N, 008°42.120'W; 207-197 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-200 • 8 spc (juv) + 10 sh (juv); 43°41.590'N, 008°45.328'W to 43°42.396'N, 008°44.286'W; 301-301 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-300 • 1 spc; 43°42.348'N, 008°45.889'W to 43°43.269'N, 008°45.289'W; 344-354 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-350 • >100 spc (58 juv) + 6 sh (juv); 43°48.587'N, 008°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 008°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 2 spc 43°51.873'N, 008°53.683'W to 43°53.120'N, 008°53.301'W; 802-788 m; 10-20 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-800 • 1 sh (juv); 42°30.391'N, 009°19.517'W to 42°29.428'N, 009°17.924'W; 147-148 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS AG-EBS-150 • 2 spc + 2 sh (juv); 43°29.412'N, 008°28.362'W to 43°29.779'N, 008°28.240'W; 110-111 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-AT-110 • 1 spc (juv) + 4 sh

Figure 40. *Teretia teres*. A-C: shell (7.6 mm) (SE(08) DRN7); D: shell (6.1 mm) (DAI(03) AT-1000); E, F: protoconch and transition to teleoconch; G, H: sculpture and microsculpture of the teleoconch; I, J: apical view of the protoconch of other shell and detail of the deep sinus (DAI(03) EBS-100) (A-C: stereo microscope images; the remaining: SEM images).

Figura 40. *Teretia teres*. A-C: concha (7,6 mm) (SE(08) DRN7); D: concha (6,1 mm) (DAI(03) AT-1000); E, F: protoconcha y transición a teleoconcha; G, H: escultura y microescultura de la teleoconcha; I, J: vista apical de la protoconcha de otra concha y detalle del seno profundo (DAI(03) EBS-100) (A-C: imágenes de lupa binocular; el resto: imágenes de MEB).

Figure 41. *Teretia teres* (DAI(03) EBS-100). A-G: larval shell (1.1 mm) and details of its microsculpture (SEM images).

Figura 41. Teretia teres (DAI(03) EBS-100). A-G: concha larvaria (1,1 mm) y detalles de su microscultura (imágenes de MEB).

(juv); 43°35.611'N, 008°58.536'W to 43°36.104'N, 008°57.284'W; 384-345 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-EBS-400 • 1 sh (juv); 43°36.544'N, 009°03.064'W to 43°36.816'N, 009°04.339'W; 601-619 m; 17-28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-EBS-600 • 1 sh (juv); polygon delimited by points 44° 10.000' N, 009° 00.000' W / 44° 10.000' N, 008° 35.000' W / 44° 00.000' N; 009° 00.000' W / 44° 07.000' N; 008° 35.000' W; 480-600 m; SARRIDAL (2006-2007) SARRI-2 • 1 sh (juv); polygon delimited by points 44° 10.000' N, 009° 00.000' W / 44° 10.000' N, 008° 35.000' W / 44° 00.000' N; 009° 00.000' W / 44° 07.000' N; 008° 35.000' W; 417-668 m; SARRIDAL (2006-2007) SARRI-4 • 6 sh (3 juv); 44°11.652'N, 008°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 008°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 4 sh (juv); 44°08.65'N, 008°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 008°55.104'W; 581-566 M; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 sh (juv); 44°04.648'N, 008°47.849'W to 44°04.858'N, 008°47.599'W; 484-473 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-10-2 • 1 sh (juv); 44°07.309'N, 008°48.289'W to 44°07.488'N, 008°48.047'W;

445-438 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-11-5 • 2 spc; 44°06.496'N, 008°23.522'W to 44°07.16'N, 008°23.201'W; 337-324 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-13 • 1 sh (juv); 44°08.516'N, 008°40.788'W to 44°09.688'N, 008°39.721'W; 436-428 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-11 • 3 sh; 44°00.806'N, 008°33.098'W to 44°01.967'N, 008°32.57'W; 346-344 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-14 • 2 sh (juv); 43°58.84'N, 008°15.625'W to 43°59.621'N, 008°14.285'W; 233-237 m; 15-24 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-20 • 3 sh (juv); 43°34.86'N, 009°21.95'W to 43°36.44'N, 009°20.71'W; 1010-1112 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-04 • 1 sh (juv); 43°19.92'N, 009°38.13'W to 43°21.25'N, 009°37.11'W; 1267-1286 m; 15-30 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-15.

Description: Shell fusiform with high spire and predominant spiral sculpture (Figs. 40A-D, 43P) and fine opisthocline growth lines. Sharp spiral cords increasing in number by intercalation during growth, most prominent in the periphery of whorls. Subsutural ramp narrow with well-marked curved growth lines and delimited by a groove (Fig. 40G). There is a delicate micro-sculpture of granules, aligned axially in the areas where they are most abundant (Fig. 40H). Aperture lanceolate, outer lip simple forming a deep sinus immediately beneath the suture (Fig. 40J), and short and wide siphonal canal. Multispiral, brown protoconch, tall and narrowly conical, which can reach almost 5 whorls (Figs. 40E, I, 41A). Protoconch I begins with a sculpture of irregular granules arranged more or less in a spiral (Fig. 41B) becoming the cancellate sculpture, although coarser than in other Raphitomidae. Protoconch II with the typical oblique reticulated pattern fading in the last whorl (Fig. 41C-H). Transition to the teleoconch at sinusigera line (Fig. 40F).

Remarks: *Teretia teres* is a common and well-known species distributed from the British Islands to Mauritania (including the Macaronesian Islands and NE Atlantic seamounts) and the Mediterranean in the outer shelf and upper slope. ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI (1999) recorded it in the Tyrrhenian Sea at 550 m, PEÑAS ET AL. (2006) around the Alboran Island, SCAPERROTTA ET AL. (2015) in the Tuscan Archipelago (Italy) at 180-200 m depth, NEGRI & CORSELLI (2016) between 525 and 780 m in southern Italy, GOFAS ET AL. (2014b) in the Avempace Bank (Alboran Sea) at 349-365 m depth in a bottom dominated by the crinoid *Leptometra*, UTRILLA ET AL. (2020) found it alive in a mud volcano of the Gulf of Cádiz within the 400-500 m depth range, HORRO & ROLÁN (2017) in Mauritania at 60 m depth, and GOFAS ET AL. (2021) on Galicia Bank between 670 and 1000 m. The shells showed by GOFAS ET AL. (2021: figure 26N) has a greater number of spiral cords. *Teretia teres* was one of the most abundant species in the samples studied collected in the depth range 200-1300 m, most frequent around 600 m.

(Right page/Página derecha) Figure 42. A: *Drilliola emendata* (9.9 mm) (DAII/DRN-03); B: *Drilliola loprestiana* (10.7 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7); C: *Typhlomangelia nivalis* (13.6 mm) (SE(08) DRN-15-2); D: *Commarmondia gracilis* (18.3 mm) (VE(04)GA-AT110); E: *Aforia* sp. (19.7 mm) (DAII(08) DRN-22); F: *Aforia clytrotropis* (31.0 mm) (SE(08)AT14); G: *Spirotropis confusa* (13.0 mm) (SE(08)DRN-15-2); H: *Spirotropis galiciensis* n. sp., holotype (21.5 mm) (DAII (08)DRN-14); I: *Bela menkhorsti* (6.9 mm) (DAI(02) EBS-150); J: *Bela nuperrima* (6.2 mm) (VE(04) GA-AT 110); K: *Micropleurotoma spirotopoides* (6.8 mm) (DAII(08) EBS-27); L: *Micropleurotoma travailleuri* (8.1 mm) (DAI(03) DRN1000); M: *Kurtziella serga* (10.5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7); N: *Oenopota graphica* (6.0 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7-1); O: *Mangelia costata* (4.3 mm) (VE(04) GA-AT-110); P: *Mangelia costulata* (4.2 mm) (DAI(03) EBS-100); Q: *Mangelia tenuicosta* (6.1 mm) (DAI(02) EBS-150); R: *Propebela* cf. *assimilis* (7.7 mm) (DAII(08)DRNp2-24); S: *Oenopota* cf. *tenuicostata* (8.5 mm) (DAII (08) DRNp-14); T: *Propebela* cf. *bergensis* (forma A) (11.1 mm) (DAII(08)/DRN-03); U: *Propebela* cf. *bergensis* (forma B) (14.0 mm) (DAII(08)DRNp-02); V: *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma* (4.0 mm) (VE(04) CA-EBS-150); W: *Taranis* cf. *moerchii* (4.4 mm) (SE(08)/DRN-10-2b).

DISCUSSION

The so-called ‘turrids’ (used here as the colloquial term for conoideans not belonging to the families Conidae or Terebridae) are the most diverse group of deep-sea gastropods (REX *ET AL.*, 1999) and are considered an important group of specialized predators in deep-sea environments (BOUCHET & WARÉN 1980; SYSOEV 1996; KANTOR *ET AL.*, 2016).

Within the more than 800 shells and specimens studied belonging to these families, 38 different species (in 22 genera) have been identified. This contrasts with the 23 species of rissoids identified among more than 5,000 shells found in the same samples (OLIVER *ET AL.*, in press). Obviously this is due to the position in the food chain that both groups play. While rissoid species are mainly generalist grazers or deposit feeders on organic detritus, “turrids” are very specialized predators. Consequently, most species appear in low abundance and some of them are only known from single individuals (BOUCHET *ET AL.*, 2009; CRISCIONE *ET AL.*, 2021b; HALLAN *ET AL.*, 2021). Of 10 of the species studied only one specimen was found, 12 were found in a single sample and only 7 were found in ten or more samples. Nineteen of the species (50%) were represented by specimens with soft parts.

Maximum conoidean diversity is found offshore in deep-sea habitats, and deep-sea exploration remains one of the major frontiers for the discovery of marine biodiversity (BOUCHET *ET AL.*, 2016). All this means that knowledge of this extraordinarily diverse group of

gastropods is still very fragmentary (we only know a few pieces of a “huge puzzle”). Therefore, the data presented here must be interpreted in this context and are only indicative of the turrids diversity on the sea bottoms of the outer continental shelf and slope off NW Iberian Peninsula.

BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980) included 102 species in their seminal review of the North-East Atlantic bathyal and abyssal “turrids”, of which 22 were found in the studied samples, 4 of them with doubts (*Propebela cf. assimilis*, *Oenopota cf. tenuicostata* *Pleurotomella cf. benedicti* and *Taranis cf. moerchii*). Two of the remaining species are described here as new species (in the genera *Spitotropis* and *Neopleurotomoides*), 2 were only identified to the genus level (*Aforia* sp. and *Phymorhynchus* sp.) and 11 species inhabit the continental shelf above 250 m depth (those of the genera *Comarmondia*, *Bela*, *Mangelia*, *Sorgenfreispira*, *Raphitoma*, *Cyrillia* and *Leufroyia*), so were not included by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1980).

SYSOEV (2014) recorded 57 “turrid” conoideans occurring deeper than 2000 m in the seas bordering Europe, of which 8 were found in the studied samples (*Typhomangelia nivalis*, *Micropleurotoma spirotropoides*, *Oenopota cf. tenuicostata*, *Gymnobela abyssorum*, *Gymnobela subaraneosa*, *Pleurotomella cf. benedicti*, *P. eurybrocha* and *Taranis cf. moerchii*).

A study on the molluscs of the Galicia Bank (a large seamount located close to the area here studied) has recently been published (GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2021), where 15 species of conoidean gastropods were

(Right page/Página derecha) Figure 43. A: *Gymnobela abyssorum* (18.8 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-04); B: *Austrobelia pyrrogamma* (16.8 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp-03); C: *Gymnobela subaraneosa* (8.9 mm) (DAII(08)DRNp-21); D: *Neopleurotomoides callembryon* (4.5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7); E: *Neopleurotomoides senharisi* n. sp., holotype (11.6 mm) (SE(08) AT-12); F: *Pleurotomella cf. benedicti* (13.1 mm) (SE(08) AT-12); G: *Phymorhynchus* sp. (31.1 mm) (DAII(08)DRN22); H: *Leufroyia erronea* (16.2 mm) (SE(08) DRN-16-1); I: *Leufroyia cf. inflata* (9.9 mm) (SE(08)-DRN15-2); J: *Pleurotomella demosia* (6.9 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7C); K: *Raphitoma cf. echinata* (10.2 mm) (SE(08) AT-11-2); L: *Pleurotomella eurybrocha* (3.5 mm) (SE(08) DRN-7); M: *Pleurotomella gibbera* (3.6 mm) (DAII(08) DRNp3-08); N: *Cyrillia aequalis* (5.6 mm) (VE(04) GA-AT-110); O: *Cyrillia linearis* (5.0 mm) (VE(04)-GA/AT110); P: *Teretia teres* (7.6 mm) (SE(08)-DRN7).

recorded. Since its summit is located at a depth of 625 m, the malacofauna of this bank is constituted by deep-water species, therefore, coastal or continental shelf species are not present there. Of the 15 recorded conoideans found in the Galicia Bank, 11 were found in our neighbouring study area (*Drilliola loprestiana*, *Kurtziella serga*, *Austrobela pyrrhogramma*, *Neopleurotomoides callembrion*, *Gymnobela abyssorum*, *G. subaraneosa*, *Pleurotomella gibbera*, *P. demosia*, *P. eurybrocha*, *P. packardi* and *Teretia teres*). Surprisingly, 3 of the most frequent deep-water species in the studied samples were not found in the Galicia Bank (*Spirotropis confusa*, *Micropleurotoma travailleuri* and *Oenopota graphica*). Conversely *Aforia serranoi*, *Retidriilla pruina*, *Teretia megalembryon* and *Pleurotomella coelorhapha* recorded in the Galicia Bank (GOFAS ET AL., 2021) have not been found in the studied samples.

These differences found in these two close areas may be due to differences in the habitats that characterize them. While the sediments in the upper part of the Galicia Bank are bioclastic or of pelagic origin, in the area here studied they are of terrigenous origin with a significant proportion of mud. Furthermore, the Galicia Bank is subject to stronger currents, which typically affect seamounts. Otherwise, 8 of the species studied here are restricted to the continental shelf above 260 m depth (*Comarmondia gracilis*, *Bela menkhorsti*, *Bela nuperrima*, *Mangelia costata*, *M. costulata*, *M. tenuicosta*, *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma* and *Cyrellia aequalis*) and could not occur on Galicia Bank.

The species *Leufroyia erronea* and *Oenopota* cf. *tenuicostata* (if its identification is confirmed) are recorded for the first time in Spanish territorial waters, according to the national check list of marine Mollusca (GOFAS ET AL., 2017). It is noteworthy that most of the species studied (31 of the 40 species) were found in the fishing area called "A Selva" (sampled by the "Selva 08" expedition). It is an area located in the Northwest of Galicia (43°30'N-44°15'N; 008°10'W-009°10'W) including the continental shelf and slope with different types of bottoms and containing extensive car-

bonated hard grounds (ALDEA ET AL., 2010). One of the samples obtained in this area (DRN-7, 908-1100 m depth with sand and white corals) was the one where more species were found (15 of the species studied; see Appendix 1). In fact, the bathymetric range of 800-1000 m was where the highest number of species was found (20 species) and most of them were present between 400 and 1200 m (Table II).

Thirteen of the species studied have paucispiral protoconch (*Drilliola loprestiana* and those of the genera *Aforia*, *Spirotropis*, *Micropleurotoma*, *Oenopota*, *Propebela*, plus *Typhlomangelia nivalis*) (see Table I), indicative of a non-planktotrophic larval development and a supposed low dispersal capacity. Loss of planktotrophy has been a frequent phenomenon in the evolution of different lineages of Caenogastropoda and has been documented in many conoidean taxa, giving rise to adaptive radiation (PUIL-LANDRE ET AL., 2010; FEDOSOV & PUIL-LANDRE, 2012, among others). Supposedly, a planktotrophic larval development would lead to a wide distribution and high genetic integrity between distanced populations, while a non-planktotrophic development would lead to a patchy distribution with local speciation processes. In fact, some of the species studied with paucispiral protoconch showed great variability and taxonomic problems that could involve species complexes or local adaptations. This is the case of *Typhlomangelia nivalis*, *Spirotropis confusa*, *Micropleurotoma travailleuri*, *Propebela* cf. *bergensis* or *Taranis* cf. *moerchii*.

Anyway, knowledge on these deep-sea species is still very fragmentary and derived from a random sampling. Furthermore, because of their high diversity, low abundance and morphological complexity, the systematics of deep-sea conoideans remains tentative below the level of family and many species are only known from empty shells. Therefore genera and species are diagnosed primarily based on morphology, although extensive molecular studies are currently being carried out (ABDELKRIM

Table II.- Bathymetric range where each species was collected (spc: shell with soft parts; sh: empty shell; sf: subfossil; juv: juvenile specimen or shell; frg: fragment).

Tabla II.- Rango batimétrico donde se recolectó cada especie (spc: ejemplar con partes blandas; sh: concha vacía; sf: subfósil; juv: ejemplar o concha juvenil; frg: fragmento).

Species	100-200	200-400	400-600	600-800	800-1000	1000-1200	1200-1500	1500-2000	2000-2500	>2500
<i>Drilliola emendata</i>				sh						
<i>Drilliola loprestiana</i>			spc	sh	sh	sh	sh			
<i>Typhlomangelia nivalis</i>			spc	spc	spc	sh				
<i>Comarmondia gracilis</i>	spc	sh								
<i>Aforia clytrotropis</i>		sf								
<i>Aforia</i> sp.						sf		sf		
<i>Spirotropis confusa</i>			sh	spc	spc	spc	sh	sh		
<i>Spirotropis galiciensis</i> n. sp.						spc		sh		
<i>Micropleurotoma spirotropoides</i>				sh	sh		sh			
<i>Micropleurotoma travailleuri</i>				spc	spc	sh				
<i>Bela menkhorsti</i>	sh									
<i>Bela nuperrima</i>	sh	spc								
<i>Kurtziella serga</i>					spc	sh				
<i>Mangelia costata</i>	sh									
<i>Mangelia costulata</i>	spc									
<i>Mangelia</i> cf. <i>tenuicosta</i>	spc									
<i>Oenopota grafica</i>				spc	spc					
<i>Oenopota tenuicostata</i>				sh	sh	juv	sh	juv		
<i>Propebela</i> cf. <i>bergensis</i>			sh	sh	spc	sh				
<i>Propebela</i> cf. <i>assimilis</i>										sh
<i>Sorgentreispira brachystoma</i>	spc	sh								
<i>Gymnobela abyssorum</i>			spc		spc	sh	sh			
<i>Gymnobela subaraneosa</i>					spc	juv			sh	
<i>Austrobela pyrrhogramma</i>			spc	sh	sh	juv	sh			
<i>Neopleurotomoides callembrion</i>					sh	sh				
<i>Neopleurotomoides senharisi</i> n. sp.									spc	
<i>Phymorhynchus</i> sp.								sf	sf	
<i>Pleurotomella</i> cf. <i>benedicti</i>									sf	
<i>Pleurotomella gibbera</i>			juv		spc	sh				
<i>Pleurotomella demosia</i>			sh	juv	juv	juv				
<i>Pleurotomella eurybrocha</i>					sh					
<i>Cyrellia aequalis</i>	sh		sh							
<i>Cyrellia linearis</i>	sh									
<i>Raphitoma</i> cf. <i>echinata</i>			sh							
<i>Leufroyia erronea</i>					sh					
<i>Leufroyia</i> aff. <i>inflata</i>				sf						
<i>Taranis</i> cf. <i>moerchii</i>			sh							
<i>Teretia teres</i>	spc	spc	spc	spc	spc					
TOTAL 40	10	6	14	16	20	17	7	3	5	1

ET AL., 2018; FASSIO ET AL., 2019; RUSSINI ET AL., 2020; CRISCIONE ET AL., 2021a,b,c; HALLAN ET AL., 2021, among others).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Juan Moreira, Marcos P. Señarís, Ramiro R. Tato, Xandro G. Regueira, Marcos Abad, Eva Corral, Alba González, Ana Sorribas, Esther Gil-Mansilla and María Zamarro for sorting most of the specimens and Guillermo Díaz Agras, María Candás and Xela Cunha Veira for the custody and handling of all samples. SEM photos were made by Laura Tormo, Marta Furió and Pedro J. Valverde, technicians of the Scanning

Electron Microscopy Lab of the MNCN and by Inés Pazos from the CACTI of the University of Vigo. Anders Warén, Philippe Bouchet and Serge Gofas gave kind and valuable information and data on some species. Francesco Pusateri and Riccardo Giannuzzi-Savelli shared with us his enormous knowledge on Raphitomidae. The second author is grateful to Francisco Déniz, from Gran Canaria, Sandro Gori, from Livorno, and Frank Swinnen, from Lommel, for loaning rare specimens from their private collections for comparative studies. We are greatly indebted to Serge Gofas for many valuable suggestions, corrections, and for meticulous editing that led to great improvements in the manuscript.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- AARTSEN J.J. VAN 1988. European Mollusca: notes on less well-known species. 12. *Bela menkhorsti* nom. nov. = *Pleurotoma nana* Scacchi, 1836 not Deshayes, 1835 and *Fehria* (nov. gen.) *zenetouae* nov. spec. *La Conchiglia*, 20 (232-233): 30-31.
- ABDELKRIM J., AZNAR-CORMANO L., BUGE B., FEDOSOV A.E., KANTOR Y.I., ZAHARIAS P. & PUILLANDRE N. 2018. Delimiting species of marine gastropods (Turridae, Conoidea) using Rad-sequencing in an integrative taxonomy framework. *Molecular Ecology*, 27: 4591-4611.
- ABSALÃO R.S., PIMENTA A.D. & CAETANO C.H.S. 2005. Turridae (Mollusca, Neogastropoda, Conoidea) coletados no litoral Sudeste do Brasil, Programa REVIZEE "score" central. *Biociências*, 13 (1): 19-47.
- ALBANO P.G., SCHNEDL, S. & ESCHNER, A. 2018. An illustrated catalogue of Rudolf Sturany's type specimens in the Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Austria (NHMW): deep-sea Eastern Mediterranean molluscs. *Zoosystematics and Evolution*, 94 (1): 29-56.
- ALDEA C., DÍAZ-AGRAS G., GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ Ó., MOREIRA J., RODRIGUES M., TATO R.R., URGORRI V. & TRONCOSO J. 2010. Deep-sea macrobenthic diversity and assemblages of "A Selva" (NW Iberian Peninsula): first approach from samples taken aboard R/V Sarmiento de Gamboa. *Thalassas*, 26 (2): 169-179.
- APPOLLONI M., SMIRIGLIO C., AMATI B., LUGLIÈ L., NOFRONI I., TRINGALI L.P., MARIOTTINI P. & OLIVERIO M. 2018. Catalogue of the primary types of marine molluscan taxa described by Tommaso Allery Di Maria, Marquis of Monterosato, deposited in the Museo Civico di Zoologia, Roma. *Zootaxa*, 4477: 1-138.
- ARDOVINI R. & COSSIGNANI T. 1999. *Atlante delle conchiglie di profondità del Mediterraneo*. L'Informatore Piceno, Ancona, Italia: 112 pp.
- BARRIO L. 2016. *Estudio sistemático, anatómico y filogenético de los moluscos de la subfamilia Emarginulinae (Gastropoda, Vetigastropoda, Fisurellidae) de los fondos batiales del Atlántico norte*. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Universidad de Santiago de Compostela, 371 pp.
- BECK T., METZGER T. & FREIHALD A. 2006. *Biodiversity inventorial atlas of macrobenthic seamount animals*. FAU-Friedrich Alexander University of Erlangen-Nuremberg. Available from https://epic.awi.de/id/eprint/37314/7/OASIS_BIAS.pdf [accessed 15 Dec. 2021].
- BOGDANOV I. 1990. *Molluscs of Oenopotinae Subfamily (Gastropoda, Pectinibranchia, Turridae) in the seas of the USSR*. Leningrad, 221 pp.
- BOUCHET P., BARY S., HEROS V. & MARANI G. 2016. How many species of molluscs are there in the world's oceans, and who is going to describe them? *Mémoires du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle*, 208: 9-24.
- BOUCHET P., KANTOR Y.I., SYSOEV A. & PUILLANDRE N. 2011. A new operational classification of the Conoidea (Gastropoda). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 77 (3): 273-308.

- BOUCHET P., LOZOUET P. & SYSOEV A.V. 2009. An inordinate fondness for turrids. *Deep-Sea Research II*, 56 (19-20): 1724-1731.
- BOUCHET P. & TAVIANI M. 1989. Atlantic deep-sea gastropods in Mediterranean: new finding. *Bollettino Malacologico*, 25 (5-8): 137-148.
- BOUCHET P. & TAVIANI M. 1992. The Mediterranean deep-sea fauna: pseudopopulations of Atlantic species? *Deep-Sea Research*, 39 (2): 169-184.
- BOUCHET P. & WARÉN A. 1980. Revision of the North-East Atlantic bathyal and abyssal Turridae (Mollusca, Gastropoda): *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, Supplement 8: 119 pp.
- BROCCHI G.B. 1814. Conchiologia fossile subappennina, con osservazioni geologiche sugli Apennini e sul suolo adiacente. *Stamperia Reale, Milano* Vol. II: 241-712, 1-16 pls.
- CAETANO H.S., SANTOS F.N. & COSTA P.M.S. 2006. First record of *Neopleurotomoides callembrion* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Gastropoda: Turridae) from Brazilian deep waters. *Strombus*, 13 (1): 9-12.
- COSSIGNANI T. & ARDOVINI R. 2011. Malacologia Mediterranea. L'Informatore Piceno, Ancona, 536 pp.
- CRISCIONE F., HALLAN A., FEDOSOV A. & PULLANDRE N. 2021a. Deep Downunder: Integrative taxonomy of *Austrobeta*, *Spergo*, *Theta* and *Austrotheta* (Gastropoda: Conoidea: Raphitomidae) from the deep sea of Australia. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research*, 59: 1718-1753.
- CRISCIONE F., HALLAN A., PULLANDRE N. & FEDOSOV A. 2021b. Where the snails have no name: A molecular phylogeny of Raphitomidae (Neogastropoda: Conoidea) uncovers vast unexplored diversity in the deep seas of temperate southern and eastern Australia. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 191 (4): 961-1000.
- CRISCIONE F., HALLAN A., PULLANDRE N. & FEDOSOV A. 2021c. Snails in depth: Integrative taxonomy of *Famelica*, *Glaciotomella* and *Rimosodaphnella* (Conoidea: Raphitomidae) from the deep sea of temperate Australia. *Invertebrate Systematics*, 35 (8): 940-962.
- DÍAZ J.M. & PUYANA M. 1994. *Moluscos del Caribe colombiano. Un catálogo ilustrado*. Colciencias, Fundación Natura, Invemar, Bogotá, Colombia, 291 pp., 76 pls.
- FASSIO G., RUSSINI V., PUSATERI F., GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI R., HØISÆTER T., PULLANDRE N., MODICA M.V. & OLIVERIO M. 2019. An assessment of *Raphitoma* and allied genera (Neogastropoda: Raphitomidae). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 85 (4): 413-424.
- FECHTER, R. 1979a. Abyssale Turriden von der Horseshoe-Tiefsee-Ebene. *Spixiana*, 2 (1): 63-68.
- FECHTER R. 1979b. Gastropoden aus der Iberischen Tiefsee. *Meteor Forschungs-Ergebnisse (D)*, 30: 23-40.
- FEDOSOV A.V. & KANTOR Y. 2008. Toxoglossan gastropods of the subfamily Crassispirinae (Turridae) lacking a radula, and a discussion of the status of the subfamily Zemacinae. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 74: 27-35.
- FEDOSOV A.E. & PULLANDRE N. 2012. Phylogeny and taxonomy of the *Kermia-Pseudodaphnella* (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Raphitomidae) genus complex: a remarkable radiation via diversification of larval development. *Systematics and Biodiversity*, 10 (4): 447-477.
- FIGUEIRA R.M.A. & ABSALÃO R.S. 2010a. Deep-water Drilliinae, Cochlespirinae and Oenopotinae (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Turridae) from the Campos Basin, southeast Brazil. *Scientia Marina*, 74 (3): 471-481.
- FIGUEIRA R.M.A. & ABSALÃO R.S. 2010b. Deep-water Mangeliinae, Tarantinae and Clathurellinae (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Conoidea: Turridae) from the Campos Basin, southeast Brazil. *Scientia Marina*, 74 (4): 731-743.
- FIGUEIRA R.M.A. & ABSALÃO R.S. 2012. Deep-water Raphitomidae from the Campos Basin, Southeast Brazil, *Zootaxa*, 3527: 1-27.
- FRETTER V. & GRAHAM A. 1985. The Prosobranch Molluscs of Britain and Denmark. Part 8 - Neogastropoda. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, Supplement 15: 435-556.
- GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI R., PUSATERI F. & BARTOLINI, S. 2018. A revision of the Mediterranean Raphitomidae (Gastropoda: Conoidea) 5: loss of planktotrophy and pairs of species, with the description of four new species. *Bollettino Malacologico*, 54 (suppl. 11): 1-77.
- GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI R., PUSATERI F. & BARTOLINI S. 2019. A revision of the Mediterranean Raphitomidae, 8: on two poorly known species of *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847: *R. pumila* (Monterosato, 1890) and *R. hispidella* nomen novum (Gastropoda Conoidea). *Biodiversity Journal*, 10: 57-66.
- GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI R., PUSATERI F., PRKIĆ J., BARTOLINI S., RUSSINI V., FASSIO G. & OLIVERIO M. 2020. Revision of Mediterranean and NE Atlantic Raphitomidae (Gastropoda, Conoidea) 8: The genus *Leufroyia* Monterosato, 1884. *Zoosystema*, 42 (22): 433-473.
- GIRIBET G. & PEÑAS A. 1997. Fauna malacológica del litoral del Garraf (NE de la Península Ibérica). *Iberus*, 15 (1): 41-93.
- GOFAS S. 2011. Familia Conidae y afines. In Gofas S., Moreno D. & Salas C. (coords.) *Moluscos marinos de Andalucía*. Servicio de Publicaciones e Intercambio Científico, Universidad de Málaga, pp. 324-342.
- GOFAS S., KANTOR Y. & LUQUE A. 2014a. A new *Aforia* (Gastropoda: Conoidea: Cochlespiridae) from Galicia Bank (NW Iberian Peninsula). *Iberus*, 32 (1): 45-51.

- GOFAS S., LUQUE A.A., OLIVER J.D., TEMPLADO J. & SERRANO A. 2021. The Mollusca of Galicia Bank (NE Atlantic Ocean). *European Journal of Taxonomy*, 785: 1-114.
- GOFAS S., LUQUE A.A., TEMPLADO J. & SALAS C. 2017. A national checklist of marine Mollusca in Spanish waters. *Scientia Marina*, 81 (2): 241-254.
- GOFAS S., SALAS C., RUEDA J.L., CANOURA J., FARIAS C. & GIL J. 2014b. Mollusca from a species-rich deep-water *Leptometra* community in the Alboran Sea. *Scientia Marina*, 78 (4): 1-17.
- GRACIA C.A., ARDILA N.E. & DÍAZ J.M. 2004. Gastropods collected along the continental slope of the Colombian Caribbean during the INVEMAR-Macrofauna campaigns (1998–2001). *Iberus*, 22 (1): 43-75.
- GUERRA-GARCÍA J.M., TATO R. & MOREIRA J. 2018. Caprellidae (Crustacea: Peracarida: Amphipoda) from deep-sea waters off Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula) with the description of a new genus and three new species. *Zootaxa*, 4532 (2): 151-202.
- HALLAN A., CRISCIONE F., FEDOSOV A. & PULLANDRE N. 2021. Few and far apart: Integrative taxonomy of Australian species of *Gla-diobela* and *Pagodibela* (Conoidea: Raphitomidae) reveals patterns of wide distributions and low abundance. *Invertebrate Systematics*, 35 (2): 181-202.
- HASEGAWA K. 2009. Upper bathyal gastropods of the Pacific coast of northern Honshu, Japan, chiefly collected by R/V Wakataka-maru. In: T. Fujita (ed.), Deep-sea fauna and pollutants off Pacific coast of northern Japan. *National Museum of Nature and Science Monographs*, 39: 225-383.
- HOARAU A. & HORST D. 2020. *Les genres Cyrillia, Leufroyia & Raphitoma vivants de Méditerranée française*. AFC, Paris, and ConchBooks, Hackenheim, 98 pp.
- HØISÆTER, T. 2009. Distribution of marine, benthic, shell bearing gastropods along the Norwegian coast. *Fauna Norvegica*, 28: 5-106.
- HØISÆTER T. 2016. A taxonomic review of the Norwegian species of *Raphitoma* (Gastropoda: Conoidea: Raphitomidae). *Fauna Norvegica*, 36: 9-32.
- HORRO J. & ROLÁN E. 2017. Two new species of *Teretia* (Gastropoda: Raphitomidae) from West Africa. *Iberus*, 35 (2): 143-157.
- HORRO J., RYALL P. & ROLÁN E. 2018. *Bela schoenherri* (Gastropoda: Mangeliidae), a new species from West Africa. *Conchylia*, 49 (1-2): 43-50.
- JANSSEN R. 1989. Benthos-Mollusken aus dem Tiefwasser des östlichen Mittelmeeres, gesammelt während der "METEOR"-Fahrt 5 (1987). *Senckenbergiana Maritima*, 20 (5/6): 265-276.
- JANSSEN R. 1993. Taxonomy, evolution and spreading of the turrid genus *Spirotropis* (Gastropoda: Turridae). *Scripta Geologica*, Special Issue, 2: 237-261.
- KANTOR Y.I., HARASEWYCH M.G. & PULLANDRE N. 2016. A critical review of Antarctic Conoidea (Neogastropoda). *Molluscan Research*, 36 (3): 153-206
- KANTOR Y.I., STRONG E.E. & PULLANDRE N. 2012. A new lineage of Conoidea (Gastropoda: Neogastropoda) revealed by morphological and molecular data. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 78 (3): 246-255.
- KILBURN R.N. 1983. Turridae (Mollusca: Gastropoda) of southern Africa and Mozambique. Part 1. Subfamily Turrinae. *Annals of the Natal Museum*, 25: 549-585.
- LOCARD A. 1897-1898. *Expéditions scientifiques du Travailleur et du Talisman pendant les années 1880, 1881, 1882 et 1883. Mollusques testacés*. Paris, Masson. vol. 1 [1897], p. 1-516 pl. 1-22; vol. 2 [1898], p. 1-515, pl. 1-18.
- LUCAS Y., SAN MARTÍN G. & PARAPAR J. 2012. Two new species of Syllidae (Annelida: Polychaeta) from DIVA-Ártabria I project (cruise 2002) to deep areas off NW Spain. *Zootaxa*, 3589: 77-88.
- LUNDBERG J., SCHANDER C. & STOKLAND O. 1996. A preliminary cladistic analysis of North Atlantic *Oenopota* Moerch, 1852 and *Propebela* Iredale, 1918 (Gastropoda: Conoidea). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 62: 289-298.
- MANOUSIS T., KONTADAKIS C., MBAZIOS G. & POLYZOULIS G. 2018. The family Raphitomidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Conoidea) in the Greek Seas with the description of two new species. *Journal of Biological Research-Thessaloniki*, 25 (14): 1-38.
- MARIOTTINI P., DI GIULIO A., SMIRGLIO C. & OLIVERIO M. 2008. Notes on the *Bela brachysytoma* complex, with description of a new species (Mollusca, Gastropoda: Conidae). *Aldrovandia*, 4: 3-20.
- MARIOTTINI P., SMIRGLIO C., DI GIULIO A. & OLIVERIO M. 2009. A new fossil Conoidean from the Pliocene of Italy, with comments on the *Bela menckhorsti* complex (Gastropoda: Conidae). *Journal of Conchology*, 40 (1): 5-14.
- MARIOTTINI P., DI GIULIO A., SMIRGLIO C. & OLIVERIO M. 2015. Additional notes on the systematics and new records of East Atlantic species of the genus *Sorgenfreispira* Moroni, 1979 (Gastropoda Mangeliidae). *Biodiversity Journal*, 6 (1): 431-440.
- MORASSI M. & BONFITTO A. 2015. New Indo-Pacific species of the genus *Teretia* Norman, 1888 (Gastropoda: Raphitomidae). *Zootaxa*, 3911 (4): 560-570.

- MOREIRA J., LUCAS Y. & PARAPAR J. 2011. Sphaerodorids (Polychaeta, Sphaerodoridae) from the continental margin off NW Iberian Peninsula, with first records of *Sphaerodoropsis sibuetae* and *S. amoureuixi* after original description. *Graellsia*, 67: 23-33.
- MOREIRA J. & PARAPAR J. 2007. Sphaerodoridae (Annelida: Polychaeta) from the DIVA-Artabria I project (2002 cruise) with description of a new species from the Ártabro Gulf (NW Iberian Peninsula). *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 48: 373-379.
- MOREIRA J. & PARAPAR J. 2008. Hesionidae y Pilargidae (Annelida: Polychaeta) del proyecto DIVA-Artabria I (campana 2002) recogidos en la plataforma y talud continental del Golfo Ártabro (Galicia, España). *Nova Acta Científica Compostelana* (Biología), 17: 105-115.
- NEGRI M.P. & CORSELLI C. 2016. Bathyal Mollusca from the cold-water coral biotope of Santa Maria di Leuca (Apulian margin, southern Italy). *Zootaxa*, 4186: 1-97.
- OLIVER J.D., GOFAS S., URGORRI V., DÍAZ-AGRAS G. & TEMPLADO J. (in press). Rissoidae Gastropods of the outer continental shelf and slope 1 off Galicia (NW Spain). *Zootaxa*.
- OLIVER P.G., MORGENROTH H. & SALVADOR A. 2017. Type specimens of Mollusca described by Col. George Montagu in the Royal Albert Memorial Museum & Art Gallery, Exeter, and the Natural History Museum, London. *Zoosystematics and Evolution*, 93 (2): 363-412.
- ORTEGA J.R. & GOFAS S. 2019. The unknown bathyal of the Canaries: new species and new records of deep-sea Mollusca. *Zoosystema*, 41 (26): 513-551.
- ÖZTÜRK, B. 2021. *Mangelia* (Gastropoda, Conoidea) species of the Turkish coasts with description of *Mangelia vanaartseni* n. sp. *Zootaxa*. 4933 (2): 241-262.
- ÖZTÜRK B. & GEYRAN K. 2021. *Raphitoma* (Gastropoda: Conoidea: Raphitomidae) species distributed along the Turkish Coasts. *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 20 (6): 431-451.
- PASTORINO G. & SÁNCHEZ N. 2016. Southwestern Atlantic species of conoidean gastropods of the genus *Aforia* Dall, 1889. *Zootaxa*, 4109 (4): 458-470.
- PARAPAR J. & MOREIRA J. 2009. Polychaeta of the 'DIVA-Artabria I' project (cruise 2002) in the continental shelf and upper slope off Galicia (NW Spain). *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 50: 57-78.
- PELORCE J. & HORST D. 2020. *Raphitoma echinata* (Brocchi, 1814) et *Raphitoma echinata* sensu auctores sur la côte méditerranéenne du département des Alpes-Maritimes (France). *Xenophora Taxonomy*, 28: 28-35.
- PEÑAS A. & GIRIBET G. 2003. Adiciones a la fauna malacológica del litoral del Garraf (NE de la Península Ibérica). *Iberus*, 21 (1): 177-189.
- PEÑAS A., ROLÁN E. & BALLESTEROS M. 2008. Segunda adición a la fauna malacológica del litoral del Garraf (NE de la Península Ibérica). *Iberus*, 26 (2): 15-42.
- PEÑAS A., ROLÁN E., LUQUE A., TEMPLADO J., MORENO D., RUBIO F., SALAS C., SIERRA A. & GOFAS S. 2006. Moluscos marinos de la Isla de Alborán. *Iberus*, 24 (1): 23-151.
- PINNA G. & SPEZIA L. 1978. Catalogo dei tipi del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale di Milano. V. I tipi dei Gasteropodi fossili. *Atti della Società Italiana di Scienze Naturali e del Museo Civico Storia Naturale di Milano*, 119 (2): 125-180.
- POWELL A.W.B. 1966. The molluscan families Speightiidae and Turridae. *Bulletin of the Auckland Institute and Museum*, 5: 1-157.
- PRKIĆ J., GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI R., PUSATERI F., RUSSINI V., FASSIO G. & OLIVERIO M. 2020. Three new species of *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847 (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Raphitomidae) from Croatian waters (NE Adriatic Sea). *Zoosystema*, 42 (16): 215-237.
- PULLANDRE N., FEDOSOV A.E. & KANTOR Y. 2016. Systematics and Evolution of the Conoidea. In Gopalakrishnakone P. & Malhotra A. (eds.) *Evolution of venomous animals and their toxins, toxinology*. Springer Dordrecht, 1-32 pp.
- PULLANDRE N., KANTOR Y., SYSOEV A., COULOUX A., MEYER C., RAWLINGS T., TODD J.A. & BOUCHET P. 2011. The dragon tamed? A molecular phylogeny of the Conoidea (Mollusca, Gastropoda). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 77 (3): 259-272.
- PULLANDRE N., SAMADI S., BOISSELIER M.C., SYSOEV A.V., KANTOR Y.I., CRUAUD C., COULOUX A. & BOUCHET P. 2008. Starting to unravel the toxoglossan knot: molecular phylogeny of the "turrids". *Molecular Phylogenetic and Evolution*, 47: 1122-1134.
- PULLANDRE N., SYSOEV A.V., OLIVERA B.M., COULOUX A. & BOUCHET P. 2010. Loss of planktotrophy and speciation: geographical fragmentation in the deep-water gastropod genus *Bathytoma* (Gastropoda, Conoidea) in the western Pacific. *Systematics and Biodiversity*, 8 (3): 371-394.
- PUSATERI F. & GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI R. 2008. A new raphitomine neogastropod from the Mediterranean Sea (Conoidea). *Iberus*, 26 (2): 119-126.
- REX M.A., ETTER R.J., CLAIN A.J. & HILL M.S. 1999. Bathymetric patterns of body size in deep-sea gastropods. *Evolution*, 53 (4): 1298-1301.
- RIOS E.C. 1994. *Seashells of Brazil*. 2nd Edition, Rio Grande, Brazil, 368 pp., 13 pls.
- ROLÁN E., OTERO-SCHMITT J. & FERNANDES F. 1998. The Family Turridae s.l. in Angola (West Africa). 1. Subfamily Daphnellinae. *Iberus*, 16 (1): 95-118.

- ROSENBERG G. 2009. *Malacolog 4.1.1: A Database of Western Atlantic Marine Mollusca*. [WWW database (version 4.1.1)] URL <http://www.malacolog.org/>
- RUSSINI V., GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI R., PUSATERI F., PRKIĆ J., FASSIO G., MODICA M.V. & OLIVIERO M. 2020. Candidate cases of poecilogony in Neogastropoda: implications for the systematics of the genus *Raphitoma* Bellardi, 1847. *Invertebrate Systematics*, 34: 293-318
- SCAPERROTTA M., BARTOLINI S. & BOGI C. 2010. Accrescimenti. *Stadi di accrescimento dei molluschi marini del Mediterraneo*. Vol II. L'Informatore Piceno, Ancona, Italia, 176 pp.
- SCAPERROTTA M., BARTOLINI S. & BOGI C. 2012. Accrescimenti. *Stadi di accrescimento dei molluschi marini del Mediterraneo*. Vol IV. L'Informatore Piceno, Ancona, Italia, 184 pp.
- SCAPERROTTA M., BARTOLINI S. & BOGI C. 2014. Accrescimenti. *Stadi di accrescimento dei molluschi marini del Mediterraneo*. Vol VI. L'Informatore Piceno, Ancona, Italia, 189 pp.
- SCAPERROTTA M., BARTOLINI S. & BOGI C. 2015. Accrescimenti. *Stadi di accrescimento dei molluschi marini del Mediterraneo*. Vol VII. L'Informatore Piceno, Ancona, Italia, 192 pp.
- SEÑARÍS M.P., GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ O. & URGORRI V. 2017. Four new species of Chaetodermatidae (Mollusca, Caudofoveata) from bathyal bottoms of the NW Iberian Peninsula. *Helgoland Marine Research*, 70 (28): 1-23.
- SMRIGLIO C., MARIOTTINI P. & GRAVINA F. 1988. Molluschi del Mar Tirreno Centrale: Segnalazione di *Pleurotomella packardii* Verrill, 1872. *Bollettino Malacologico*, 24 (5-8): 148-149.
- SYSOEV A.V. 1996. Deep-sea conoidean gastropods collected by the John Murray Expedition, 1933-34. *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum of London, Zoology*, 62: 1-30.
- SYSOEV A.V. 2014. Deep-sea fauna of European seas: An annotated species check-list of benthic invertebrates living deeper than 2000 m in the seas bordering Europe. *Gastropoda. Invertebrate Zoology*, 2014, 11 (1): 134-155.
- TATO R. & MOREIRA J. 2017. Two new species of the Suborder Senticaudata (Crustacea: Amphipoda) from the upper continental slope off Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula). *Zootaxa*, 4300 (2): 217-237.
- TATO R., MOREIRA J. & URGORRI, V. 2019. Redescription and first record of *Camacho faroensis* Myers, 1998 (Crustacea, Amphipoda) from the continental slope off Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula). *Marine Biodiversity*, 49: 897-904.
- TAYLOR J.D., KANTOR Y.I. & SYSOEV A.V. 1993. Foregut anatomy, feeding mechanisms, relationships and classification of the Conoidea (= Toxoglossa) (Gastropoda). *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum Zoology*, 59 (2): 125-170.
- URGORRI V., CANDÁS M., DÍAZ-AGRAS G., CUNHA-VEIRA X., GÓMEZ-RODRÍGUEZ C., MÍGUEZ-RODRÍGUEZ L. 2021. *Psolidium bathy-galego* nom. nov. (Echinodermata, Holothuroidea) from bathyal bottoms of Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula). *Marine Biodiversity*, 51: 20-34.
- URIBE J.E., ZARDOYA R. & PUILLANDRE N. 2018. Phylogenetic relationships of the conoidean snails (Gastropoda: Caenogastropoda) based on mitochondrial genomes. *Molecular Phylogenetic and Evolution*, 127: 898-906
- UTRILLA O., GOFAS S., URRÁ J., MARINA P., MATEO-RAMÍREZ A., LÓPEZ-GONZÁLEZ N., GONZÁLEZ-GARCÍA E., SALAS C. & RUEDA J.L. 2020. Molluscs from the benthic habitats of the Gazul mud volcano (Gulf of Cádiz). *Scientia Marina*, 84 (3): 273-295.
- VERRILL A.E. 1884. Second catalogue of Mollusca recently added to the fauna of the New England Coast and the adjacent parts of the Atlantic, consisting mostly of deep sea species, with notes on others previously recorded. *Transactions of the Connecticut Academy of Arts and Sciences*, 6 (1): 139-294, pl. 28-32.
- WARÉN A. 1975. *Spirotropis sarsi*, new name for *Spirotropis carinata* Sars, 1878 (Gastropoda: Prosobranchia). *Sarsia*, 59: 49-52.
- WARÉN A. 1980. *Marine mollusca described by John Gwyn Jeffreys with the location of type material*. Conchological Society of Great Britain and Ireland, Special Publication 1, 60 pp., 8 pls.
- ZAMARRO M., GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ O. & URGORRI V. 2013. Three new species of Pruvotinidae (Mollusca: Solenogastres) from Antarctica and NW Spain. *Helgoland Marine Research*, 67: 423-443.
- ZAMARRO M., GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ O. & URGORRI V. 2015. New anatomical and biogeographical data on Solenogastres Cavibelonia from the Galician Continental Margin (NW Spain). *Iberus*, 67: 423-443
- ZAMARRO M., GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ O. & URGORRI V. 2016. On the biodiversity of the family Simrothiellidae (Mollusca, Solenogastres) in the upper-slope of the NW Iberian Peninsula with the description of three new species. *Marine Biodiversity*, 46: 655-680.
- ZAMARRO M., GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ O. & URGORRI V. 2019. Biodiversity of the genus *Hemimienia* (Mollusca, Solenogastres, Neomeniamorpha) in Galician waters (NW Spain) with the description of three new species. *Iberus*, 37 (2): 177-207.
- ZHANG S. & ZHANG S. 2017. A new species of the genus *Phymorhynchus* (Neogastropoda: Raphitomidae) from a hydrothermal vent in the Manus Back-Arc Basin. *Zootaxa*, 4300 (3): 441-444.

Appendix 1. List of stations sampled during the different expeditions with data of the number of species collected in each one, coordinates, depth and type of bottom. Abbreviations for Conoidean species, Ac: *Aforia clytotropis*; Mu: *Mangelia costulata*; Ap: *Austrobelia pyrrogramma*; Nc: *Neopleurotomoides callebryon*; As: *Aforia* sp.; Ns: *Neopleurotomoides senharisi* n. sp.; Bm: *Bela menkhorsti*; Og: *Oenopota graphica*; Bn: *Bela nuperrima*; Ot: *Oenopota* cf. *tenuicostata*; Ca: *Cyrellia aequalis*; Pb: *Pleurotomella* cf. *benedicti*; Cg: *Comarmondia gracilis*; Pd: *Pleurotomella demosia*; Cl: *Cyrellia linearis*; Pe: *Pleurotomella eurybrocha*; De: *Drilliola emendata*; Pg: *Pleurotomella gibbera*; Dl: *Drilliola loprestiana*; Po: *Propebela* cf. *bergensis*; Gs: *Gymnobela subaraneosa*; Ps: *Phymorhynchus* sp.; Ks: *Kurtziella serga*; Re: *Raphitoma* cf. *echinata*; Le: *Leufroyia erronea*; Sb: *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma*; Li: *Leufroyia* cf. *inflata*; Sc: *Spirotropis confusa*; Mc: *Mangelia costata*; Sg: *Spirotropis galiciensis* n. sp.; Mp: *Micropleurotoma travailleuri*; Tm: *Taranis* cf. *moerchii*; Ms: *Micropleurotoma spirotropoides*; Tn: *Typhlomangelia nivalis*; Mt: *Mangelia tenuicostata*; Tt: *Teretia teres*.

Anexo 1. Relación de estaciones muestreadas durante las diferentes expediciones con datos del número de especies recolectadas en cada una, coordenadas, profundidad y tipo de fondo. Abreviaturas para las especies de Conoidea, Ac: *Aforia clytotropis*; Mu: *Mangelia costulata*; Ap: *Austrobelia pyrrogramma*; Nc: *Neopleurotomoides callebryon*; As: *Aforia* sp.; Ns: *Neopleurotomoides senharisi* n. sp.; Bm: *Bela menkhorsti*; Og: *Oenopota graphica*; Bn: *Bela nuperrima*; Ot: *Oenopota* cf. *tenuicostata*; Ca: *Cyrellia aequalis*; Pb: *Pleurotomella* cf. *benedicti*; Cg: *Comarmondia gracilis*; Pd: *Pleurotomella demosia*; Cl: *Cyrellia linearis*; Pe: *Pleurotomella eurybrocha*; De: *Drilliola emendata*; Pg: *Pleurotomella gibbera*; Dl: *Drilliola loprestiana*; Po: *Propebela* cf. *bergensis*; Gs: *Gymnobela subaraneosa*; Ps: *Phymorhynchus* sp.; Ks: *Kurtziella serga*; Re: *Raphitoma* cf. *echinata*; Le: *Leufroyia erronea*; Sb: *Sorgenfreispira brachystoma*; Li: *Leufroyia* cf. *inflata*; Sc: *Spirotropis confusa*; Mc: *Mangelia costata*; Sg: *Spirotropis galiciensis* n. sp.; Mp: *Micropleurotoma travailleuri*; Tm: *Taranis* cf. *moerchii*; Ms: *Micropleurotoma spirotropoides*; Tn: *Typhlomangelia nivalis*; Mt: *Mangelia tenuicostata*; Tt: *Teretia teres*.

Station	Nº sp.	Coordinates	Depth (m)	Habitat
DIVA-ARTABRIA I (2002). Acronym: DA-I(02) – Dates: 08-15/09/2002				
DRN-800	1: Tn	43° 51.265' N; 008° 54.480' W 43° 51.498' N; 008° 53.123' W	827-819	Phosphorites, small and large
AT-200	1: Cg	43° 40.036' N; 008° 43.789' W 43° 39.706' N; 008° 44.610' W	201-198	Muddy sand
AT-800	1: Tt	43° 47.188' N; 008° 53.053' W 43° 55.312' N; 008° 53.101' W	770-842	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts
AT-1000	6: Ks Mp Ms Sc Sg Tn	43° 57.030' N; 008° 54.795' W 43° 57.248' N; 008° 54.133' W	1191-1132	Phosphorites and coral gravel
EBS-150	6: Bm Bn Cg Mt Sb Tt	43° 35.451' N; 008° 34.432' W 43° 34.810' N; 008° 35.407' W	153-151	Sandy mud
EBS-200	3: Bn Sb Tt	43° 40.192' N; 008° 43.760' W 43° 40.943' N; 008° 42.366' W	207-212	Muddy sand
EBS-250	1: Sb	43° 41.113' N; 008° 44.297' W 43° 41.905' N; 008° 43.078' W	256-258	Muddy sand
EBS-300	1: Tt	43° 41.689' N; 008° 45.195' W 43° 42.556' N; 008° 44.226' W	298-303	Muddy sand
EBS-350	1: Tt	43° 42.427' N; 008° 45.921' W 43° 43.253' N; 008° 44.818' W	347-243	Muddy sand
EBS-400	1: Tt	43° 45.892' N; 008° 44.301' W 43° 46.966' N; 008° 43.766' W	390-381	Sandy mud

Station	N° sp.	Coordinates	Depth (m)	Habitat
DIVA-ARTABRIA I (2003). Acronym: DA-I(03) – Dates: 10-20/09/2003				
DRN-600	3: DI Sc Tf	43° 48.421' N; 008° 51.453' W 43° 49.160' N; 008° 51.091' W	599-607	Phosphorites
DRN-1000	6: DI Mp Og Po Sc Tn	43° 53.575' N; 008° 56.868' W 43° 54.015' N; 008° 56.959' W	965-974	Dead coral gravel
AT-800	2: Og Tf	43° 51.774' N; 008° 53.640' W 43° 52.516' N; 008° 53.478' W	798-801	Carbonate crusts
AT-1000	4: Mp Po Sc Tf	43° 53.847' N; 008° 57.324' W 43° 54.621' N; 008° 57.261' W	993-1004	Live and dead coral gravel
EBS-100	6: Ca Mc Mt Mu Sb Tf	43° 26.703' N; 008° 30.669' W 43° 27.452' N; 008° 29.612' W	103-102	Muddy sand
EBS-150	3: Ca Mt Sb	43° 34.127' N; 008° 36.562' W 43° 34.820' N; 008° 35.585' W	152-149	Muddy sand
EBS-200	1: Tf	43° 40.250' N; 008° 43.755' W 43° 40.760' N; 008° 42.120' W	207-197	Muddy sand
EBS-300	2: DI Tf	43° 41.590' N; 008° 45.328' W 43° 42.396' N; 008° 44.286' W	301-301	Muddy sand
EBS-350	1: Tf	43° 42.348' N; 008° 45.889' W 43° 43.269' N; 008° 45.289' W	344-354	Muddy sand
EBS-600	5: DI Mp Og Po Tf	43° 48.587' N; 008° 51.402' W 43° 49.545' N; 008° 51.197' W	610-598	Sand
EBS-800	5: DI Mp Po Sc Tf	43° 51.873' N; 008° 53.683' W 43° 53.120' N; 008° 53.301' W	802-788	Stones and white clay
VERTIDOS (2004). Acronym: VE(04) – Dates: 17-21/09/2004 and 24-28/09/2004				
AG-EBS-150	3: Mu Sb Tf	42° 30.391' N; 009° 19.517' W 42° 29.428' N; 009° 17.924' W	147-148	Muddy sand
AG-EBS-250	1: Bn	42° 31.176' N; 009° 23.380' W 42° 32.132' N; 009° 24.151' W	242-248	Muddy sand
CA-EBS-150	2: Bm Sb	42° 50.507' N; 009° 25.773' W 42° 48.810' N; 009° 25.198' W	151-148	Muddy sand
GA-DRN-1000	3: DI Mp Sc	43° 38.812' N; 009° 07.949' W 43° 39.841' N; 009° 07.405' W	999-1001	Dead corals and small phosphorites
GA-AT-110	10: Bm Bn Ca Cg Cl Mc Mt Mu Sb Tf	43° 29.412' N; 008° 28.362' W 43° 29.779' N; 008° 28.240' W	110-111	Muddy sand
GA-AT-150	2: Cg Sb	43° 32.026' N; 008° 37.520' W 43° 32.806' N; 008° 35.993' W	150-151	Muddy sand
GA-AT-800	1: Mp	43° 38.105' N; 009° 02.006' W 43° 37.738' N; 009° 00.905' W	836-826	Phosphorites, carbonate crusts and stones
GA-EBS-150	1: Cg	43° 31.970' N; 008° 37.670' W 43° 32.697' N; 008° 3.171' W	151-151	Muddy sand
GA-EBS-400	2: DI Tf	43° 35.611' N; 008° 58.536' W 43° 36.104' N; 008° 57.284' W	384-345	Muddy sand
GA-EBS-600	2: Tn Tf	43° 36.544' N; 009° 03.064' W 43° 36.816' N; 009° 04.339' W	601-619	Muddy sand
APLACOFORA (2006). Acronym: APLA(06) – Dates: 04-05/07/2006				
Est1 EBS	1: Sb	43° 36.686' N; 008° 33.855' W 43° 38.066' N; 008° 35.075' W	166-165	Muddy sand

Station	N° sp.	Coordinates	Depth (m)	Habitat
SARRIDAL (2006-07). Acronym: SAR(06-07) – Dates: 05/01/06 – 19/04/07 – 15/07/07 – 01/08/07 – 12/11/07				
SARRI-1	2: Pd Tn	All samples are from an area delimited	720	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts in all samples
SARRI-2	1: Mp Tt	by the following 4 points, in A Selva	480-600	
SARRI-3	1: Sc	44° 10.000' N; 009° 00.000' W	417-668	
SARRI-4	3: Dl Po Tt	44° 10.000' N; 008° 35.000' W	417-668	
SARRI-5	1: Po	44° 00.000' N; 009° 00.000' W	420-650	
		44° 07.000' N; 008° 35.000' W		
A SELVA:2008. Acronym: SE(08) – Dates: 15-24/07/2008				
DRN-7	15: Ap Dl Ga Gs Ks Mp Nc Og Pd Pe Pg Po Sc Tn Tt	44° 11.652' N; 008° 58.152' W 44° 11.539' N; 008° 57.574' W	908-1106	Sand with live and dead corals
DRN-7C	7: Ap Dl Ga Pd Pg Po Tt	44° 08.65' N; 008° 55.305' W 44° 08.771' N; 008° 55.104' W	581-566	Sand and corals
DRN-7-1	5: Dl Gs Ms Og Tn	44° 08.461' N; 009° 04.634' W 44° 08.607' N; 009° 04.413' W	917-896	Muddy sand, small phosphorites and dead corals
DRN-7-2	2: Dl Sc	44° 06.84' N; 009° 03.692' W 44° 07.075' N; 009° 03.655' W	911-886	Small phosphorites and muddy sand
DRN-7-3	1: Og	44° 05.043' N; 008° 57.977' W 44° 05.186' N; 008° 57.821' W	829-813	Muddy sand
DRN-10-2	1: Tt	44° 04.648' N; 008° 47.849' W 44° 04.858' N; 008° 47.599' W	484-473	Small stones
DRN-10-2B	4: Dl Sc Tn Tm	44° 06.113' N; 008° 45.102' W 44° 06.282' N; 008° 44.606' W	434-433	Slightly muddy sand
DRN-11	2: Dl Sc	44° 09.896' N; 008° 39.581' W 44° 10.129' N; 008° 39.494' W	438-459	Sand and small phosphorites
DRN-11-4	3: Ca Po Tn	44° 07.628' N; 008° 45.871' W 44° 07.989' N; 008° 45.542' W	412-411	Slightly muddy sand
DRN-11-5	1: Tt	44° 07.309' N; 008° 48.289' W 44° 07.488' N; 008° 48.047' W	445-438	Sand
DRN-15-1	4: As Dl Sc Tn	43° 58.356' N; 008° 52.149' W 43° 57.685' N; 008° 52.903' W	1054-1064	Small stones and small phosphorites
DRN-15-2	9: Ap As Dl Li Mp Ms Og Sc Tn	43° 56.478' N; 008° 54.199' W 43° 55.934' N; 008° 54.849' W	620-933	Phosphorites and dead corals
DRN-15-2B	6: Ap Dl Mp Og Sc Tn	43° 55.886' N; 008° 54.846' W 43° 55.291' N; 008° 55.65' W	933-930	Phosphorites and stones
DRN-16-1	2: Sc Le	43° 56.51' N; 008° 49.869' W 43° 57.448' N; 008° 749' W	781-839	Phosphorites and small limestones
DRN-17	1: Dl	43° 42.289' N; 008° 49.804' W 43° 43.019' N; 008° 49.24' W	629-542	Muddy gravel
DRN-20	3: Cg Mt Sb	43° 58.719' N; 008° 15.691' W 43° 58.942' N; 008° 15.362' W	231-233	Sand
DRN-22	3: Bm Mc Sb	43° 29.13' N; 008° 43.233' W 43° 29.596' N; 008° 42.838' W	149-151	Mud
DRN-30-1	2: Dl Sc	43° 48.511' N; 008° 51.393' W 43° 49.092' N; 008° 50.959' W	312-576	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts
AT-11-2	3: Re Pd Sc	44° 07.495' N; 008° 46.999' W 44° 07.675' N; 008° 45.225' W	416-407	Phosphorites and stones
AT-12	3: Ns Pb Ps	44° 14.929' N; 008° 30.255' W 44° 15.367' N; 008° 30.438' W	2121-2516	Large stones, phosphorites, sand and coral

Station	N° sp.	Coordinates	Depth (m)	Habitat
AT-13	2: Sc Tf	44° 06.496' N; 008° 23.522' W 44° 07.16' N; 008° 23.201' W	337-324	Phosphorites and sand
AT-14	1: Ac	44° 00' N; 008° 32' W 44° 01' N; 008° 32' W	344-343	Sand
EBS-10-2B	1: DI	44° 05.923' N; 008° 45.586' W 44° 06.046' N; 008° 43.886' W	432-453	Sand
EBS-11	1: Tf	44° 08.516' N; 008° 40.788' W 44° 09.688' N; 008° 39.721' W	436-428	Slightly muddy sand and few phosphorites
EBS-14	2: DI Tf	44° 00.806' N; 008° 33.098' W 44° 01.967' N; 008° 32.57' W	346-344	Muddy sand
EBS-20	1: Tf	43° 58.84' N; 008° 15.625' W 43° 59.621' N; 008° 14.285' W	233-237	Muddy sand
DIVA-ARTABRIA II (2008). Acronym: DA-II(08) – Dates: 15-30/09/2008				
DRNp-02	1: Po	43° 33.35' N; 009° 08.31' W 43° 36.81' N; 009° 07.34' W	546-523	Small phosphorites and shells
DRNp-03	3: De Mp Po	43° 33.53' N; 009° 13.28' W 43° 33.90' N; 009° 12.93' W	725-737	Small phosphorites, stones and shells
DRNp-04	4: As Ga Sc Tn	43° 34.19' N; 009° 22.12' W 43° 35.77' N; 009° 21.23' W	1005-1070	Sand
DRNp3-08	4: Ap Mp Pg Sc	43° 24.64' N; 009° 31.56' W 43° 25.38' N; 009° 30.97' W	880-814	Small phosphorites, sand and carbonate crusts
DRNr-10	1: DI	43° 33.24' N; 009° 30.39' W 43° 33.7' N; 009° 29.75' W	1207-1206	Sand
DRNp-14	2: Ot Sg	43° 19.29' N; 009° 45.95' W 43° 20.17' N; 009° 45.08' W	1580-1518	Phosphorites
DRNp-15	2: Ap Ga	43° 20.00' N; 009° 38.06' W 43° 20.63' N; 009° 37.59' W	1268-1293	Gravel of <i>Megabalanus</i> plates
DRNp-16	2: Ot Sc	43° 20.49' N; 009° 34.03' W 43° 21.22' N; 009° 32.96' W	846-771	Sand with phosphorites, calcareous plates and stones
DRNr-17	2: Mp Sc	43° 17.26' N; 009° 36.4' W 43° 18.12' N; 009° 36.32' W	947-1011	Sand
DRNr-18	3: Mp Sc Tn	43° 16.50' N; 009° 34.52' W 43° 16.71' N; 009° 33.79' W	565-503	Mud with stones
DRNp-21	2: Gs Pp	43° 09.47' N; 009° 44.63' W 43° 10.23' N; 009° 44.22' W	2099-2104	Stones with mud
DRNp-22	2: As Ps	43° 05.28' N; 009° 41.77' W 43° 06.25' N; 009° 40.99' W	1727-1763	Calcareous plates and muddy sand
DRNr2-24	1: Pa	43° 04.16' N; 010° 01.83' W 43° 05.00' N; 010° 01.31' W	3154-3160	Small stones
DRNp-31	1: Sc	43° 23.19' N; 009° 32.35' W 43° 23.89' N; 009° 31.36' W	866-804	Phosphorites
EBS-04	4: Ap Mp Ot Tf	43° 34.86' N; 009° 21.95' W 43° 36.44' N; 009° 20.71' W	1010-1112	Coarse sand with gravel
EBS-15	4: Ap DI Ga Tf	43° 19.92' N; 009° 38.13' W 43° 21.25' N; 009° 37.11' W	1267-1286	Sand
EBS-27	1: Ms	42° 45.9' N; 009° 41.68' W 42° 47.00' N; 009° 42.12' W	1499-1373	Mud with gravel

Station	N° sp.	Coordinates	Depth (m)	Habitat
EBS-28	1: Sc	42° 38.21' N; 009° 51.46' W 42° 39.45' N; 009° 50.73' W	1961-1971	Mud with gravel
EBS-30	1: Of	42° 31.58' N; 009° 40.14' W 42° 33.87' N; 009° 38.75' W	2030-1886	Mud
FORSAGAL (2009). Acronym: FOR(09) – Dates: 14-25/02/2009				
DRN-18	2: Sc Tn	42° 23' N; 009° 24' 33.40" W 42° 23' N; 009° 23' 32.05" W	455-378	Glauconitic sand
DRC-2	1: Sc	42° 23.135' N; 009° 35.76' W 42° 22.45' N; 009° 35.59' W	1043-1062	Mud with rocks